

XXV International Conference of Young Geologists

May 14 - 17, 2026
Kostelec nad Černými lesy
Czech Republic

ABSTRACT BOOK

**XXV International
Conference of Young Geologists**

ABSTRACT BOOK – ICYG 2026

**14-17 May 2026
Kostelec nad Černými lesy, Czech Republic**

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Introduction

The XXV International Conference of Young Geologists (ICYG 2026) was held from 14 to 17 May 2026 in Kostelec nad Černými lesy, Czech Republic. This annual international meeting brings together emerging geoscientists, from bachelor's students presenting their first scientific results to master's and doctoral candidates and early-career researchers across the geosciences.

ICYG 2026 is hosted for the first time in the Czech Republic and provides a platform for scientific exchange, presentation of research results, networking, and international cooperation in a friendly and accessible environment.

This abstract book contains the accepted conference abstracts. Abstracts are arranged alphabetically according to the surname of the first author.

About the Conference

The annual ICYG conference was first held in 2000 at the Educational and Training Facility of the Technical University of Košice in Herľany, Slovakia. It was organised by the Faculty of Mining, Ecology, Process Control and Geotechnologies of the Technical University of Košice and the Faculty of Natural Sciences of Comenius University in Bratislava under the original title "Scientific Conference of Students and Doctoral Students". The concept was initiated by two doctoral students, Marianna Kováčová and Julián Kondela, and the first scientific guarantors were prof. Shah Wali Faryad and doc. Pavel Uher. From the outset, the conference attracted students from Slovakia, the Czech Republic, and Poland.

In 2005, the Faculty of Geology, Geophysics and Environmental Protection of AGH University of Science and Technology in Kraków, Poland, joined the organising institutions. Since then, the conference has rotated between the Košice region (Herľany), southern Poland, and the Bratislava region.

Since 2010, the best student presentation has been recognised each year with an award. In 2013, this prize was named the Rudolf Mock Award, in honour of doc. RNDr. Rudolf Mock, CSc.

Since 2024, Charles University (Prague, Czech Republic) has joined the group of organising universities. The 25th edition of ICYG, held in 2026, is therefore hosted in the Czech Republic for the first time. It is also the first edition in the history of the conference to exceed 100 participants.

Over time, the organising team and the group of scientific guarantors have gradually developed and expanded. At present, the conference is organised on the Slovak side by the Slovak Geological Club, the Technical University of Košice, and Comenius University in Bratislava; on the Polish side by AGH University of Science and Technology in Kraków and the University of Wrocław; and on the Czech side by Charles University. The participating faculties provide the scientific guarantee of the conference each year.

ICYG 2026 Information

Conference title: XXV International Conference of Young Geologists (ICYG 2026)

Dates: 14-17 May 2026

Venue: Kostelec nad Černými lesy, Czech Republic

Conference hall: Knights' Hall of the Renaissance Castle in Kostelec nad Černými lesy

Website: www.icyg.eu

This year, ICYG 2026 brought together more than 100 participants of various nationalities, representing universities and other institutions from 14 countries: Czech Republic, Finland, France, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Morocco, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, and the United States of America. During the two conference days, a total of 50 oral and 29 poster presentations were delivered.

Thanks to the generous support of our sponsors and the strong interest of student participants, awards will this year be presented to the authors of the three best student oral presentations and the three best student poster presentations.

On the final day of the conference, participants joined a post-conference excursion to the wider Kutná Hora region. The field programme will combine geological and historical themes, including Bohemian garnet at Ratboř, the geology of the Bohemian Massif at the Kutná Hora Geopark, the historic silver mining heritage of Kutná Hora, and Cretaceous and Quaternary sediments at Červené Pečky.

Conference Scope

ICYG is an annual international conference for emerging geoscientists. Contributions are welcomed from the full spectrum of geoscience topics, including general geology, economic geology and mineral deposits, environmental geosciences, geomorphology, hydrogeology, engineering geology, geophysics, geoinformatics, mineralogy, geochemistry, petrology, structural geology, sedimentary geology, and palaeontology.

Organising Institutions

- ▶ Faculty of Science, Charles University
- ▶ SGA - Student Chapter Prague, z. s.

Faculty of Science
Charles University

Cooperating Institutions

- ▶ University of Wrocław, Faculty of Earth Sciences and Environmental Management
- ▶ University of Krakow, Faculty of Geology, Geophysics and Environmental Protection
- ▶ Comenius University, Faculty of Natural Sciences
- ▶ Technical University of Košice, Faculty of Mining, Ecology, Process Control and Geotechnologies
- ▶ Geological Club Bratislava

Support and Accessibility

Thanks to generous support from Charles University and Faculty of Science, ICYG 2026 offers financially accessible participation for students, including on-site accommodation and full board.

Keynote Speaker and SGA Support

As part of the SGA Keynote Speaker Program, ICYG 2026 hosts Prof. Simon M. Jowitt (Nevada Bureau of Mines and Geology) as an invited keynote speaker.

SGA also supported the conference through travel grants for selected students working on topics related to economic geology and mineral deposits.

Journal of Geosciences Special Issue

On the occasion of ICYG 2026, a special issue connected with the conference is announced in the Journal of GEOsciences. The special issue is dedicated to the innovative work of emerging talents in Earth Sciences and aligns with the journal's scope in fundamental and applied geological research.

Conference organizing committee

- ▶ Mgr. Jan Kulhánek, Ph.D., Lead organizer
- ▶ Mgr. Filip Tomek, Ph.D., Organizer & Excursion Coordinator
- ▶ Mgr. Klára Jůzlová, Organizer
- ▶ Bc. Martin Král, Treasurer & SGA Representative
- ▶ Mgr. Doris Foxová, Organizer
- ▶ Jan Řezáč, Graphic Designer (Logos, Flyers, Visuals)
- ▶ Mgr. Eliška Vošvrdová, Web Designer & Developer, Administrator

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- ▶ prof. Ing. Shah Wali Faryad, CSc., Faculty of Science, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic
- ▶ prof. RNDr. Pavel Uher, CSc., Faculty of Natural Sciences, Comenius University, Bratislava, Slovakia
- ▶ doc. Mgr. Julián Kondela, Ph.D., Faculty of Mining, Ecology, Process Control and Geotechnologies, Technical University of Košice

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Acknowledgement of Partners and Sponsors

The organisers of **ICYG 2026** would like to express their sincere gratitude to all partners and sponsors whose generous support has contributed significantly to the organisation of the conference. Their support has helped make the conference accessible to young geoscientists and has contributed to the scientific programme, awards, and overall quality of the meeting.

- ▶ **Charles University**
- ▶ **Přírodovědci.cz, communication project of the Faculty of Science, Charles University**
- ▶ **SGA - Society for Geology Applied to Mineral Deposits**
- ▶ SG Geotechnika
- ▶ Czech Geological Survey
- ▶ 4C Minerals
- ▶ Journal of GEOsciences
- ▶ Czech Geological Society
- ▶ Petrolab - Laboratory Thin Sections
- ▶ BeGeo Scientists

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4C Minerals

Programme Overview

Thursday, 14 May 2026

- 15:00 Reception at the castle
- 18:40 Joint departure from the castle to the brewery
- 19:00 Ice-breaker at the brewery

Friday, 15 May 2026

- 07:00 Breakfast
- 09:00 Opening talk

Session 1: From Extraterrestrial Surface Processes to Environmental Mineralogy

- 09:12-10:15 Oral presentations 1-6
- 10:30 Coffee break

Session 2: Igneous Rocks, Paleomagnetism and Tectonic Processes

- 11:00-12:15 Oral presentations 7-13
- 12:30 Lunch

Session 3: Ore Systems, Critical Metals, and Mineral Resources

- 14:00-17:00 Oral presentations 14-23
- 14:50 SGA keynote lecture by Prof. Simon M. Jowitt
Who needs mining, and who does mining need? The role of the minerals industry in modern society and climate change mitigation and opportunities for young geologists.
- 15:35 Coffee break
- 17:15 Pico poster presentations
- 17:45 Poster session
- 19:30 Dinner

Saturday, 16 May 2026

- 07:00 Breakfast

Session 4: Applied Geophysics, Geothermal Energy, and Subsurface Characterization

- 09:00-10:15 Oral presentations 24-30
- 10:30 Coffee break

Session 5: Hydrogeology, Remote Sensing, and Geoheritage

- 11:00-12:15 Oral presentations 31-37
- 12:30 Lunch

Session 6: Paleontology - Fossils and sediments

- 14:00-15:00 Oral presentations 38-42
- 15:00 Faculty keynote lecture by Martin Košťák
Fossils and sediments as modern sources of information: Case studies
- 15:50 Coffee break

Session 7: Sedimentary Records, Stratigraphy, and Paleoenvironmental Change

- 16:20-17:35 Oral presentations 44-50
- 17:50 Poster session
- 19:00 Banquet, award and closing ceremony
- 20:30 After-conference party with the band Corebells

Sunday, 17 May 2026

- 07:00 Breakfast
- 08:30 Post-conference excursion

Detailed schedule may be found at the ICYG website.

Table of Content

AHMED ABDELDAIM Astrochronology and orbital forcing of the Cenomanian–Turonian OAE2 succession in central Tunisia	8
MOHAMED ABDELRADY Integrating airborne geophysical and remote sensing data to map structures and hydrothermal alteration zones: studies in the Dagbaga and El-Bakriya area, Southeastern Desert, Egypt	10
HAFEDH ALMUSAEDI Characterizing soil properties using conventional and unconventional quasi-null ERT arrays for agricultural optimization	12
SAMAH AL-SURURI Mapping the volcanic diversity of Sana'a Basin, Yemen: Insights from modern remote sensing	14
ABOUTAROUK AYOUB Hydrothermal alteration mapping in the Igherm inlier (Western Anti-Atlas, Morocco) using integrated PRISMA hyperspectral, SAR data, and field-based spectroradiometry validation	16
MOHAMED BALASH Applications of seismic attributes and play fairway analysis for a basement geothermal reservoir characterization	18
AMÍN BHIJA Mammuthus meridionalis (Nesti, 1825) from Stříbrný terrace (Ústí nad Labem, Czech Republic)	20
SOUMYADEEP BISWAS Modern ooids of the Mediterranean coast of Egypt	22
ALEKSANDER BŁASIAK One LCT family, two fractionation pathways: Nb-Ta-Fe-Mn systematics in amblygonite-type (Viitaniemi) and lepidolite-type (Alvarrões) pegmatites	24
GAL BUBNIČ World-class mercury deposits: comparative insights from Almadén (Spain) and Idrija (Slovenia)	26
INTI CLARO-VARGAS Geochemistry, radiogenic isotopes and geochronology of the Tertiary volcanic rocks in the Veneto Volcanic Province (VVP), NE Italy. Petrogenetic implications and metallogenic potential	28
FRANCESCO ALEXANDR COLOSIMO Improving real-time earthquake source characterization using diffusion model based broadband envelope synthetics	30
VEGAS COUPÉ ARTeMIS: A European training through research program for exploration geologists	32
WERONIKA CZWOŃDA Characteristics and interpretation of the heavy minerals from sediments in selected caves in Cracow	34
OLGA DEMINA Progressive microstructural evolution of titanite during post-magmatic hydrothermal alteration of Mesoproterozoic granitoids, southern Lithuania	36
MOHAMED AYED ELBALAWY Unlocking geothermal potential in Pannonian Basin carbonate reservoirs using machine learning	38
ABDELKHALEK MOHAMED ELKAZAZ De-risking facies prediction using an integrated statistical–machine learning seismic workflow: Pannonian Basin case study	40
BEREKET FENTAW Structural patterns and petrography of the Birbir shear zone in the Western Ethiopian Shield: implications for a late tectonic evolution of the East African Orogen	42
DORIS FOXOVÁ The largest fossil of the segmented spider Parvithela muelleri Wunderlich, 2017 (Mesothela: Parvithelidae) from Cretaceous Burmese amber	44
BOTOND G. GERECSI Comparison of fluid inclusion thermometry and mineral geothermometry methods applied to sphalerite from the Ostra ore deposit, Romania	46
TADEÁŠ HÁJEK Fabric pattern and gravity modelling of the Weinsberg Composite Pluton (Bohemian Massif): Implications for late Variscan magmatic and tectonic processes	48
HAEDEER HASSAN Stress- and saturation-dependent permeability from core to logs	49
POLINA IAKUNINA Methane and carbon dioxide emissions from subsurface evidenced by field measurements and remote sensing: Case study in southern Moravia	51
BADRELDIN IBRAHIM Integration of petrography and whole-rock geochemistry to characterize hydrothermal alteration of porphyry Cu-Au system Jebel Ohier, Red Sea Hills, Northeast Sudan	53
ŠTĚPÁN JAROMĚŘSKÝ Non-destructive Raman identification of garnet in a historical artwork: A portable Pietra Dura altar depicting Saint Margaret of Antioch	55
TYMON KALBARCZYK Clastic infills of gas vesicles in basaltic trachyandesites from Regulice near Cracow	57

AHMED OSAMA KAMAL Factor-analysis-assisted hyperparameter inversion for enhancement of well-log interpretation efficiency	59	MARLENA MAŁYSZCZUK Geoeducation as a tool for building awareness of geodiversity: insights from a questionnaire-based study	87
ABDO WUDAD KEMAL Quantitative assessment of geodiversity in Ethiopia using grid-based analysis	61	JABBOUR MARIEME Geological setting and metallogenic evolution of critical Co–Ni–Fe arsenide mineralization in the Bou Azzer–El Graara inlier (Anti-Atlas, Morocco): A key cobalt-mining district for the energy transition	88
CHRISFANEL EURODE KIANGUEBENE-KOUSSINGOUNINA Geochronology and geochemistry of Variscan granitoids of the Fatic basement with Alpine tectono-metamorphic overprint (Inner Western Carpathians)	63	MAREK M. MICHALSKI Mineralogy of arsenic and antimony in soils: partitioning between clays and Fe (oxyhydr)oxides	90
PIOTR KLECZYŃSKI Preliminary petrographic and geochemical investigation of realgar mineralization in the Bystre Slice, Polish Carpathians	65	MARTYNA MOTYLSKA Integrated structural analysis of the Baligówka peat bog using seismic refraction tomography and shallow drilling, and its relationship to soil gas composition	92
ONDŘEJ KRÝZA Metastable liquid water on present- and past-day Mars: experimental constraints on grain transport in thin boiling flows under reduced pressure	67	JAN MRÁČEK Experimental and Raman study of copper and tin selenides	94
MARTIN KUBÍČEK Climate-driven sedimentary cycles in paralic setting of the Late Mississippian in the Upper Silesian Basin; an example from the Poruba Member of the Ostrava Formation	69	BOJANA NIKOLIĆ Variability and petrogenesis of the Blatná Composite Pluton (Central Bohemian Plutonic Complex)	96
MICHAŁ KULIŃSKI Hydrothermal alteration and metamictization of Th-U-bearing phases in NYF-type pegmatites from the Kola Alkaline Province	71	RADEK NOVOTNÝ Phase changes in lunar breccia during space weather simulation using Focused ion beam and Raman spectroscopy	98
DAVID-AARON LANDA Tracer tests in the Vřídlo feeding conduit (Karlovy Vary Spa, Czechia)	73	NIKOLA ORZOŁ MultiGravel: advancing multivariate approach to pebble morphometry with the example of Quaternary Pre-Metuje River gravels	100
MAKSIMILJAN LAVRENČIČ Trace element composition of sphalerite from the Ruš zinc deposit, Slovenia	75	EMMANUEL OWUSU-ACHEAMPONG Initial geodiversity assessment of Ghana using GIS methods: implications for geoheritage and geoconservation	102
MARTIN LICHOVNÍK Quantitative mineralogy of non-ferrous metallurgical slags to guide the potential recovery of valuable metal(loid)s	77	ALEX A. ORELLANA PACHECO Exploration of lithium-rich pegmatites and host rocks using XRF scanning in the SN-1 core from Las Navas (Cáceres, Spain)	104
DAMIAN GERARD LODOWSKI Towards understanding of the Jurassic/Cretaceous transition – the Neuquén Basin (Argentina) perspective	79	IVÁN MATEO ESPINEL PACHÓN A porphyry ore deposit in the making: unique insights into magmatic processes leading to ore fertility through the Taapaca volcano	106
ANASTÁZIE LUDVÍKOVÁ Microsporangiate Cones of Conifers from the Cretaceous of the Lusitanian Basin, Portugal, and Bohemian Cretaceous Basin, Czech Republic	81	MARTA PASTOR Geomorphodynamic analysis of post-eruptive tephra remobilisations triggered by non-Newtonian flows (lahars) at Tajogaite volcano	108
ANNA MACIEJEWSKA Multi-proxy analysis of organic matter maturity in the Polish Outer Carpathians – preliminary results	83	KAMIL POTERSKI The Brzechów Lagerstätte – an exceptionally preserved fauna in Cambrian coarse sandstones of the Holy Cross Mountains (Poland)	109
REBAR MAHMMUD Multi-isotope insights into groundwater recharge and residence time in the Zagros Basin, Kurdistan region of Iraq: A case study from Sulaimani City	85	JAKUB PRCÚCH Fluid characteristics and genesis of the Bieber podložná vein in Banská Štiavnica	111

EDINA PÁL-HAJDÚ RGB or LiDAR? A quantitative comparison of UAV-based 3D geosite models	113	ZOLTÁN VÁCI Undercooling mediated pyroxene growth kinetics in basalt and andesite	139
ALEKSANDER SACZKA Sorption of selenium on iron oxide-based composite material	115	KATHERINE VILLAVICENCIO-VALERO Seasonal controls on rock-glacier kinematics: thermal forcing, zero-curtain dynamics, and hydrological drivers in the Adamello–Presanella Group (Italian Alps)	141
KILLIAN SANDFORD Electrical resistivity tomography and time-domain induced polarization for stibnite vein exploration in the Trojane Area, Slovenia	117	PETR VITOUŠ Rock-magnetic and paleomagnetic constraints on the late-Paleozoic Gréixer Rhyolite Complex (Southern Pyrenees): evidence for a graben-caldera origin?	143
VÁCLAV SANTOLÍK New ore exploration efforts and geochemical research linking magmatism and mineralization in western Bohemia	119	ADAM VRBENSKÝ Plagioclase growth rate from silicate melts: towards a general kinetic model	145
NADA SATTAR Development of a GIS-based biodiversity credit assessment platform for Natura 2000 areas in Hungary	121	ALICE WANTZ Modelling feedback effects between magma chambers evolution and feeder dykes capture	147
KRZYSZTOF SETKIEWICZ Investigation of unusual phases found in flue dust samples from a copper smelter waste heat boiler, Głogów, Poland	123	MATEUSZ WOLSZCZAK From waste to resource? Metal-bearing phases in incineration bottom ash	149
SANAH SHAIKH Ghost of seagrasses past: Early Pleistocene assemblages from Rhodes Island	125	WU YUFENG Integrating geological structures into machine learning-based landslide susceptibility mapping: A case study of the Krušné hory fault zone	151
AHMED SIDIQ Theoretical CO₂ storage capacity of coal seams of the Ostrava Formation: characterization and CSLF-based estimation	127	ABDALLAH M. ZIDAN Impact of the OAE2 on the fauna and paleoenvironments around the Cenomanian–Turonian boundary in the Wadi Araba, Eastern Desert, Egypt	153
HUBERT SIEMIŃSKI Mineralogical characteristics and resource potential of inactive hydrothermal chimneys within the Polish contract area on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge	129		
TAPIO SOUKKA Development of characterization methods for platinum group mineral inclusions occurring within platinum mineral nuggets using focused ion beam electron microscopy and single crystal X-ray diffraction	131		
DÁVID SZABÓ Gas-phase formation of ammonium metal(loid) iodides under a coal-fire environment: Szarlota coal mine (Rydułtowy, Poland)	132		
WITOLD TADEUSZAK Geogenic gases (H₂, He, CO₂) in fault zones of the Podhale Basin: surface geochemical indicators of natural hydrogen occurrence and geothermal system activity	134		
MARTIN TECL Pressure-temperature history of eclogite facies rocks with reaction overstepping during metamorphism (case study from Svetlik)	136		
TATIANA TKÁČIKOVÁ Strain evolution and emplacement of ophiolite nappes based on the magnetic susceptibility anisotropy of the Ibar ophiolite, Serbia	138		

Astrochronology and orbital forcing of the Cenomanian–Turonian OAE2 succession in central Tunisia

AHMED ABDELDAIM^{1,2}, SHERIF FAROUK³, WOLFGANG RUEBSAM⁴,
MOHAMMAD ALSUWAIDI⁵, ZAINAEB ELAMRI⁶ & FELICITASZ VELLEDEITS²

1 – Institute of Exploration Geosciences, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Sciences and Engineering, University of Miskolc; Miskolc, Hungary;

ahmed.abdeldaim.ewaida.oraby@student.uni-miskolc.hu

2 – Geology Department, Faculty of Science, South Valley university; Qena, Egypt

3 – Exploration Department, Egyptian Petroleum Research Institute; Nasr City, Egypt

4 – Department of Organic and Isotope Geochemistry, Institute of Geoscience, University of Kiel; Kiel, Germany

5 – Institute of Arts and Crafts, University of Kairouan Kasserine, Tunisia

6 – Department of Earth Sciences, Khalifa University; Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates

The Cenomanian–Turonian transition represents one of the most profound paleoenvironmental disturbances of the Late Cretaceous, marked by Oceanic Anoxic Event 2 (OAE2) and widespread perturbations to the global carbon cycle (Gangl et al., 2019; Owens et al., 2016). This study presents a high-resolution astrochronological framework for the Oued Ettalla section in central Tunisia, integrating cyclostratigraphic analyses of magnetic susceptibility (MS), stable carbon and oxygen isotopes, carbonate content, and microfossil assemblages.

The MS and carbonate data show an inverse relationship (Fig. 1), indicating that variations in the carbonate content were a major factor controlling the MS data. The MTM power spectral analyses against robust AR(1) red-noise background identify statistically significant cyclicities corresponding to Milankovitch forcing. Astronomical tuning yields a refined time scale spanning approximately 2.18 Myr (94.73–92.58 Ma), providing improved temporal constraints on carbon isotope excursions, paleoceanographic change, and biotic turnover marked by general decreased foraminiferal species number and extinction of *Rotalipora cushmani*, *Thalmaninella* spp., and *Globigerinelloides bentonensis*, along with several calcareous nannofossils (Fig. 1). The main OAE2 interval is estimated to have lasted ~0.8 Myr and coincides with an obliquity antinode modulation, suggesting amplified climate sensitivity during this interval, likely strengthened summer warming at high latitudes, seasonal extremes and latitudinal temperature gradients, fostering enhanced nutrient delivery, productivity, and stratification breakdown, which collectively amplified the environmental perturbations characteristic of OAE2.

A prominent eccentricity node at the Cenomanian–Turonian boundary corresponds with reduced orbital amplitude and major ecological disruption, including plankton turnover and enhanced organic carbon burial. Conversely, eccentricity maxima align with intensified seasonality, elevated surface-water productivity, and increased detrital input as seen during upper zone 2 and zones 3 which correspond to elevated magnetic susceptibility reduced carbonate content and enhanced planktonic assemblage (Fig. 1).

Correlation with global reference sections (Farouk et al., 2025; Jarvis et al., 2006; Kuhnt et al., 2017; Sageman et al., 2006) confirms that the Tunisian record preserves a near-complete archive of OAE2, reinforcing the role of low-latitude basins in capturing astronomically paced climate dynamics.

Figure 1. Integrated astrochronological and chemostratigraphic framework of the Cenomanian–Turonian transition at the Oued Ettalla section (Central Tunisia). The eccentricity and obliquity signal were extracted using Gaussian bandpass filtering at 0.4–0.51 and 0.024–0.0288 cycles/kyr, respectively.

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Integrating airborne geophysical and remote sensing data to map structures and hydrothermal alteration zones: studies in the Daghbag and El-Bakriya area, Southeastern Desert, Egypt

MOHAMED ABDELRAKY^{1,2} & FERENC MOLNÁR¹

1 – Department of Mineralogy, Institute of Geography and Earth Sciences, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Eötvös Loránd University; Budapest, Hungary; moh200@student.elte.hu

2 – Department of Geology, Faculty of Science, Assiut University; Assiut, Egypt

The Daghbag and El-Bakriya area, located in the Central Eastern Desert of Egypt within the Golden Triangle mining province of the Arabian-Nubian shield, represents one of the most promising regions for gold exploration. Previous studies have identified auriferous quartz veins and associated hydrothermal alteration zones (Fawzy, 2017; Abdelrady et al., 2023; El-Fatah et al., 2023; Salem et al., 2024). However, integrating advanced aeromagnetic, radiometric, and digital elevation data with modern structural analysis techniques provides deeper insights into subsurface architecture and mineralization controls. This study aims to delineate hydrothermal alteration zones and the geological structures controlling gold mineralization within the Neoproterozoic basement rocks. Airborne magnetic and gamma-ray spectrometric data were processed using multiple techniques, including reduction to the pole (RTP), analytical signal (AS), first vertical derivative (FVD), tilt derivative (TDR), theta map (TM), horizontal gradient magnitude (HGM), and power spectrum analysis. Additionally, source parameter imaging (SPI), 3D magnetic modeling, and Centre for Exploration Targeting (CET) grid analysis were applied to evaluate structural complexity. CET analysis, including Texture Analysis (TA), Lination Vectorization (LV), Lination Detection (LD), and Structural Complexity (SC), was used to generate maps such as contact occurrence density and orientation entropy. These maps highlight highly deformed and fractured zones that are favourable pathways for hydrothermal fluid circulation and mineral deposition. Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM-DEM) data were also integrated to improve structural interpretation and automate surface lineament extraction using ArcMap 10.8 and Geomatica software. Lineament density maps proved essential in identifying structurally controlled mineralization zones. A strong spatial correlation was observed between lineament density, contact occurrence density, and orientation entropy, supporting the reliability of the identified targets.

The results reveal dominant structural trends, oriented N–S, NNW–SSE, NNE–SSW, NE–SW, NW–SE, and E–W. High lineament density zones commonly coincide with intrusive centers and known gold occurrences, indicating strong structural control on mineralization. Depth estimates from power spectrum analysis, SPI, and 3D modelling indicate concealed magnetic source bodies at depths ranging from approximately 190 m to 1200 m, with an average basement depth of about 645 m. High-frequency anomalies in FVD, HGM, TDR, TM, and AS maps correspond to structurally complex zones, suggesting that hydrothermal fluids were concentrated along fault intersections and fracture networks.

Radiometric analysis shows that altered granitoids are characterized by low eTh/K and eU/K ratios and relatively high K, eTh, eU, and K/eTh values. A clear spatial relationship exists between alkaline intrusions and gold mineralization, particularly in the western sector near the El-Bakriya mine. In contrast, potassium variations in the Daghbag area and northern zones suggest multiple intrusive phases and a stronger influence of regional fault systems on alteration patterns. Composite radioelement ratios, potassium deviation (Kd), and F-parameter mapping effectively delineate hydrothermal alteration zones and subtle lithological variations.

A predictive mineralization potential map integrating structural complexity, radiometric indicators, circular features, and alteration indices shows strong agreement with known gold occurrences. Several new prospective zones beyond currently mined areas were identified and are recommended for further exploration.

Overall, this integrated geophysical and remote sensing approach demonstrates that combining advanced magnetic processing, CET structural analysis, radiometric techniques, and DEM-based lineament mapping significantly enhances mineral exploration targeting in arid Precambrian terrains. The findings confirm that gold mineralization in the study area is primarily structurally controlled and closely associated with alkaline intrusions and hydrothermal alteration processes.

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Characterizing soil properties using conventional and unconventional quasi-null ERT arrays for agricultural optimization

HAFEDH ALMUSAEDI¹, SÁNDOR SZALAI^{1,2}, KRISZTIÁN BARACZA³ & MARCELL KÁRPI³

1 – Department of Geophysics, University of Miskolc; Miskolc, Hungary; hafedhnaseerali@gmail.com

2 – Institute of Earth Physics and Space Science (ELKH-EPSS); Sopron, Hungary

3 – Research Institute of Applied Earth Sciences, University of Miskolc; Miskolc, Hungary

The variability of the subsurface and its effect on crop productivity are of immense importance in poor-quality soils. Complex relationships in varying subsurface characteristics are negligible in the traditional methods of farming. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the distribution of subsurface soil resistivity, so that the subsurface land distribution can be analysed using 2D Electrical Resistivity Tomography (ERT). Geoelectrical methods are non-invasive geophysical techniques used to determine the distribution of subsurface resistivity by injecting a controlled electrical current into the ground through electrodes. Among these, ERT is particularly effective for mapping complex geological structures and moisture distribution by providing a high-resolution image of the soil and rock layers (Ward, 1990). By measuring the potential difference at the surface, variations in electrical conductivity can be correlated with lithological changes and water content, which are critical parameters in agricultural planning. The Iris Syscal device was used to collect the data using 72 electrodes with a 0.5-meter electrode spacing. Two (Dipole-Dipole) DD arrays, and quasi-null arrays (improve sensitivity of the measurement and depth of detectability over traditional arrays) (Szalai et al., 2020) were used to evaluate the purpose of the surveys (see Fig. 1).

The data of the traditional array were processed using the RES2DINV (Geotomo Software, 2006) tomographic inversion software, and the data of the quasi-null were processed with the Res2D-Hu inversion code (Prácser, 1999). The analysis of the subsurface sections reveals a detailed structural section of the subsurface, identifying four distinct layers and a significant lack of continuity in the limestone layer. This fractured zone acts as a preferential drainage pathway, causing accelerated moisture depletion in the overlying soil, which directly impacts crop-available water.

These zones are critical in defining the water balance of a system. For example, in this study, in the areas with discontinuous limestone, water drained out of the moist layer, resulting in increased soil drying. The dry soil layer resulting from limestone discontinuity is of great importance in water balance studies. The quasi-null arrays, in this study, focused on resolving the limestone surface more effectively, providing higher-resolution definition of fractures than the traditional DD array.

A quasi-null array can determine the thickness of the layer, the topography of the layers, and the location of the fractured zones, which are important to the management of irrigation, soil mapping, and defining drainage patterns. With this subsurface information, resource allocation and productivity can be enhanced for organic farmers, especially where soil health and moisture management is concerned. More distinctly and proving more effective in finding fractures between singular blocks as compared to the traditional DD array. By knowing the subsurface features, farmers can optimize resource use, especially in organic farming, where soil management and moisture control are crucial.

Figure 1: Principles of electrical resistivity measurements and the electrode arrays utilized in this study (Adapted from Knödel et al., 2007).

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Mapping the volcanic diversity of Sana'a Basin, Yemen: Insights from modern remote sensing

SAMAH AL-SURURI^{1,2}, BASSIM AL-KHIRBASH², TAREK AL-HIBSH² & MÁTYÁS GEDE³

1 – *Doctoral School of Earth Sciences, Faculty of Sciences, Eötvös Loránd University; Budapest, Hungary; samah123@student.elte.hu*

2 – *Department of Earth Science, Faculty of Petroleum and Natural Resources, Sana'a University; Sana'a, Yemen*

3 – *Institute of Cartography and Geoinformatics, ELTE Eötvös Loránd University; Budapest, Hungary*

The Sana'a Basin (SB) is located in the Central Yemen Highlands and is characterized by a complex geological environment, being surrounded by extensive volcanic formations of the Tertiary and Quaternary ages (Baker et al., 1997). Due to the significant lithological overlap and the diversity of volcanic rock types, such as basaltic lava flows, rhyolitic ignimbrites, and various tuffs, the traditional methods of geological field mapping have become increasingly difficult, time-consuming, and expensive. Consequently, this research focuses on applying modern Remote Sensing (RS) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) techniques to accurately identify, classify, and map these volcanic units, providing a much-needed update to the existing geological records of the region.

The methodology of this study integrated field observations, petrographic analysis of 24 rock samples, which identified four primary groups of basaltic rocks—massive, porphyritic, trachytic, and vesicular basalt (scoria)—alongside felsic rhyolitic units, and advanced digital image processing of Landsat-8 OLI/TIR imagery (December 2018). Pre-processing included radiometric and atmospheric corrections using the Fast Line-of-sight Atmospheric Analysis of Spectral Hypercubes (FLAASH) for accurate surface reflectance.

Enhancement techniques, such as False Color Composites (7,6,4), Band Ratios (7/6, 6/4, 5/3) and (7/6, 6/4, 6/2), and Principal Component Analysis (PC1, PC2, PC4), effectively discriminated lithological units (Sabins, 1996; Gupta, 2018). Supervised Classification using the Maximum Likelihood Classifier (MLC) was found to be the most accurate method, closely matching ground truth data (Fig. 1). To refine the results, a Majority-filter (4 neighbors) was applied post-classification to eliminate digital "noise" and smooth the final map (Stuckens et al., 2000).

The study successfully produced an updated digital lithological map of the Sana'a Basin, incorporating significant corrections to previous maps and integrating newly detected volcanic cones. For instance, several areas previously classified as basalt were correctly identified as rhyolitic rocks. This research concludes that the integration of modern RS and GIS with field validation provides a robust, low-cost tool for geological exploration and mapping in Yemen, highly recommended for updating national geological maps and utilizing higher-resolution imagery in future studies for finer mineralogical detail.

Figure 1. Supervised classification of lithological units of the study area.

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Hydrothermal alteration mapping in the Igherm inlier (Western Anti-Atlas, Morocco) using integrated PRISMA hyperspectral, SAR data, and field-based spectroradiometry validation

ABOUTAROUK AYOUB¹, ALIKOUSS SAIDA¹, ZAFATY OMAR², NAJI AYOUB¹,
MNISSAR HIMYARI SALOUA³, ENNABIR MOHAMED⁴, OUHOUSSA LHOUSSAYN³,
SAMIR MOHAMED¹ & BAROUDI ZOUHIR¹

1 – *Laboratory of Geosciences, Geomatics and Environment, Faculty of Sciences Ben M'sick, Hassan II University of Casablanca; Casablanca, Morocco; ayoub.abouttarouk-etu@etu.univh2c.ma*

2 – *National Institute of Archaeology and Heritage Sciences; Rabat, Morocco*

3 – *National Office of Hydrocarbons and Mines (ONHYM); Rabat, Morocco*

4 – *Managem group; Casablanca, Morocco*

Elongated in an E–W direction, the Igherm inlier is located on the northern margin of the West African Craton, south of the Anti-Atlas cratonic domain. It is composed of a crystalline Paleoproterozoic basement made up of metamorphic rocks, including schists, gneisses, and migmatites, intruded by granitoids and basic dykes. This basement is unconformably overlain by Neoproterozoic units consisting of carbonates and quartzites, conglomerates with volcanic rocks, and volcano-sedimentary sequences. The Paleozoic cover succeeds unconformably, comprising the Base Series, the Lower Limestones, the Lie-de-Vin Series, and the Tata Group, which forms the uppermost unit with dolomites and sandstones. All these units are intersected by a Hercynian basic dyke generally oriented in a NE–SW direction. This inlier hosts several stratiform copper deposits, including Ouarmdaz, Cheikh Imi N'rfi, Tizert, Talat n'Ouaman, Tifrki, and Tazert, occurring within Lower Cambrian shales, sandstones, limestones, and Tamjout Dolostone.

This study aims to enhance mineral exploration efficiency in the Igherm inlier integrating remote sensing data (PRISMA hyperspectral imagery), spectroradiometry reflectance, and fieldwork. By combining spectral signatures derived from PRISMA imagery with field-based reflectance measurements obtained using the ASD TerraSpec Halo Mineral Identifier, a rapid and robust workflow was developed for identifying weathering minerals and characterizing alteration zones. This workflow consists of PRISMA pre-processing (removing unsuitable bands, georeferencing, radiometric and atmospheric correction, spectral smoothing, and vegetation and building masking) and PRISMA processing using the Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM) integrating spectroradiometry reflectance data. The TerraSpec Halo enabled near-instantaneous detection of diagnostic absorption features in dry samples, significantly improving the accuracy and speed of mineral identification. This integrated approach provides a comprehensive spatial understanding of alteration patterns, supporting more targeted and effective exploration strategies in the region.

Abundance maps revealed distinct spatial alteration patterns linked to lithological and structural features. The most prominent alteration minerals identified include chlorite, hematite, illite, phengite + chlorite, epidote, goethite, phengite + hematite, and dolomite. Among the carbonates, dolomite is the most abundant alteration mineral, commonly associated with calcite, and is concentrated within the Infracambrian sedimentary cover. In contrast, phyllosilicates (phengite, chlorite), oxides/hydroxides (hematite, goethite), silicates (epidote) are predominantly distributed within the crystalline basement rocks of Proterozoic to Paleoproterozoic age.

Field spectroscopy results confirm PRISMA imagery outputs and reinforce the hydrothermal alteration mineral mapping of the Igherm inlier. Five distinct alteration assemblages were identified, each reflecting specific physicochemical conditions of hydrothermal fluid-rock interaction. At the deepest and highest-temperature end of the hydrothermal system, propylitic alteration (200–350 °C) is ex-

pressed by chlorite, epidote, and clinozoisite, developed peripherally around mineralized centers within mafic and intermediate volcanic units. Phyllic alteration (200–450 °C), characterized by muscovite and phengite, overprints earlier assemblages and reflects the introduction of potassium-rich acidic fluids responsible for feldspar replacement. At lower temperatures, argillic alteration (<250 °C) is dominated by kaolinite, montmorillonite, and illite, recording hydrogen metasomatism under acidic conditions. Carbonatization (100–300 °C), the most spatially extensive facies, reflects pervasive dolomitization of the Cambrian carbonate cover by Mg²⁺-rich hydrothermal fluids. Near the surface, supergene oxidation (<100 °C) produces goethite, hematite, malachite, and azurite through weathering of primary copper sulfides. The complete mineral assemblage identified for each alteration type is summarized in Table 1.

Alteration Type	Detected Minerals	Hydrothermal Conditions & Interpretation
Argillic Alteration	Kaolinite, Dickite, Montmorillonite, Beidellite, Smectite, Illite, Pyrophyllite, Palygorskite, Sepiolite, Vermiculite.	Low-temperature hydrothermal (<250 °C); acidic fluid-driven hydrogen metasomatism.
Phyllic Alteration	Muscovite, Phengite, Paragonite, Hydrobiotite, Biotite, Stilpnomelane, Tourmaline.	Moderate temperature (200–450 °C); potassium-rich moderately acidic fluids.
Propylitic Alteration	Epidote, Clinozoisite, Chlorite, Antigorite, Clinochrysotile, Lizardite, Gypsum.	Low- to moderate-temperature (200–350 °C); low fluid/rock ratio; peripheral hydrothermal facies dominated by chlorite + epidote + carbonate.
Carbonatization	Calcite, Dolomite, Aragonite, Ankerite, Magnesite, Siderite, Kutnohorite, Rhodochrosite, Smithsonite, Strontianite, Witherite.	Mesothermal conditions (100–300 °C); Mg ²⁺ -rich CO ₂ -bearing fluids; pervasive carbonate vein infilling and replacement of limestone host rocks.
Supergene Oxidation	Goethite, Hematite, Malachite, Azurite, Hydrozincite, Lazulite, Montebasite.	Near-surface low-temperature conditions (<100 °C); oxidation of primary iron-bearing and copper sulfides.

Table 1. Hydrothermal Alteration Assemblages Identified by ASD TerraSpec Halo in the study area.

These results confirm the potential of PRISMA hyperspectral data in advancing mineral exploration methodologies, as demonstrated by the successful mapping of hydrothermal alteration assemblages associated with copper mineralization in the Igherm inlier, particularly in the Ouarmdaz, Cheikh Imi N'rfi, and Talat n'Ouaman sectors. The spatial coincidence of high lineament density, intense hydrothermal alteration, particularly along the transition between the Precambrian basement and the Paleozoic cover, defines the most prospective zones for future copper exploration in the Western Anti-Atlas.

Applications of seismic attributes and play fairway analysis for a basement geothermal reservoir characterization

MOHAMED BALASH^{1,2}, MOHAMED AYED ELBALAWY^{1,3},
ERNŐ TAKÁCS^{1,4} & FELICITÁSZ VELLEDEITS¹

*1 – Institute of Exploration Geosciences, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Sciences and Engineering, University of Miskolc; Miskolc, Hungary;
mohamed.sayed.eid.balah@student.uni-miskolc.hu*

2 – Geology Department, Faculty of Science, Qena University Qena; Egypt

3 – Geophysics Department, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University; Cairo, Egypt

4 – Supervisory Authority for Regulatory Affairs; Budapest, Hungary

Introduction

Deep crystalline basement formations of the Pannonian Basin represent thermally favorable but structurally complex targets for geothermal exploration (Horváth et al., 2006; Tari et al., 1999). In south-east Hungary, the Battonya-Pusztaföldvár Ridge is characterized by elevated heat flow (Lenkey et al., 2002), fractured granitoid and metamorphic rocks, and an overlying marl sequence acting as a regional seal. However, the distribution of permeability and structural heterogeneity remains a key uncertainty for geothermal development. This study applies a seismic-driven Play Fairway Analysis (PFA) framework to evaluate geothermal potential within the fractured pre-Tertiary basement of the Mezőkovácsháza area. The PFA methodology follows the risk-based exploration principles described by Grant et al. (1996).

Method

The workflow is built on three methodological components.

1. Structural framework and reservoir mapping: a 3D post-stack seismic cube was interpreted and tied to five wells to identify the top basement horizon, major fault systems, and the Endrőd Marl Formation acting as a seal.
2. Fracture characterization using seismic attributes: variance, ant tracking, spectral decomposition, and colored inversion attributes were generated to delineate fracture-controlled permeability within the upper 500 m of the crystalline basement. Stress-state analysis under the regional NE–SW compressional regime was incorporated to assess slip and dilation tendencies and to weight fracture probability.
3. Risk integration and volumetric assessment: Common Risk Segment (CRS) maps were created for heat source, reservoir permeability, and seal integrity. These were integrated into a Composite Common Risk Segment (CCRS) map. Volumetric Heat-In-Place (HIP) and Recoverable Heat (Hrec) were calculated using the 3DHIP-Calculator following the methodology of Piris et al. (2021).

Results

The CCRS map identifies four structurally favorable, low-risk zones within the study area. Regional heat flow values up to 120 mW m⁻² and calibrated geothermal gradients confirm elevated thermal conditions in the fractured basement. Stored thermal energy ranges between 2,540 and 10,491 PJ per prospect area. Depending on the selected production scenario (10–30 year plans), the recoverable heat potential reaches up to 968 MWth. Fracture probability maps derived from seismic attributes show strong spatial correlation with stress-favored fault orientations.

Conclusion

The integration of seismic attribute-based fracture mapping with Play Fairway Analysis (Grant et al., 1996) and probabilistic volumetric assessment using the 3DHIP-Calculator (Piris et al., 2021) provides a structured and data-driven framework for geothermal assessment in fractured crystalline basement settings. The results indicate significant geothermal potential in the Mezőkovácsháza area and demonstrate that risk-based seismic interpretation can effectively support geothermal exploration in structurally complex regions of the Pannonian Basin.

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Mammuthus meridionalis (Nesti, 1825) from Stříbrníky terrace (Ústí nad Labem, Czech Republic)

AMÍN BHIJA¹

1 – Institute of Geology and Palaeontology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; Bhijaa@natur.cuni.cz

Mammuthus meridionalis remains have historically been rare in Central Europe, being known from a few sites such as Nova Vieska, Strekov (Slovakia), Altlichtenwarth (Austria), Süttő, Kisláng, Ercsi (Hungary) and others (Thenius, 1975; Vlačiky et al., 2008; Virág & Gasparik, 2012). The bulk of the studied material originates from several southern European Villafranchian localities such as Upper Valdarno (Italy) or Apollonia-1 (Greece) (Konidaris, 2020). Early Pleistocene megafauna is very rare in the Czech Republic in general, with the total number of specimens being somewhere under a few dozen.

One of the most historically significant and one of the stratigraphically oldest finds of a mammoth in the Czech Republic is the record and description of a single third molar originating from a high terrace near Ústí nad Labem (Hibsch, 1904; Liebus, 1929; Fejfar, 2008). The specimen was found within reddish-grey gravel-sand sediments which lie southeast of Stříbrníky. The Stříbrníky terrace (Tyráček et al., 2004) is roughly 8 m thick and situated 260–270 m above sea level. Originally, the discovered specimen was described as a molar of *Elephas antiquus* (*Palaeoloxodon antiquus*) by J. E. Hibsch in 1904 (Hibsch, 1904). Subsequently, it was redescribed by A. Liebus in 1929 as *Elephas trogontherii* (Liebus, 1929). The specimen was subsequently lost. Several authors later utilised the photograph and description published by Liebus (1929) to tentatively mention the presence of *M. meridionalis* at Stříbrníky (Liebus, 1929; Šibrava, 1972; Tyráček et al., 2004). However, the specimen itself had not been available until its rediscovery in 2025 within the collections of the Regional Museum of Ústí nad Labem's Quaternary collection.

In 2008, due to the rediscovery of new material in the geological collections of the Regional Museum Litoměřice, the specimen from Stříbrníky was reclassified yet again as *M. rumanus* by O. Fejfar (2008), based on the low lamellar count visible in the photograph published in 1929 (Liebus, 1929; Fejfar, 2008).

Due to the recent rediscovery of the Stříbrníky specimen, it can be assessed using a multivariate approach. The angle at which the occlusal surface is positioned relative to the posterior enamel loops and tubercles, along with the molar's sheer size, suggests it represents an upper third molar. The molar is split in half, with preserving agents and glue present at the break. Roughly 2–3 lamellae are missing from the anterior, having been lost during deposition and partially through natural wear. The estimated total lamellar count is likely to be 13–14 lamellae; the lamellar frequency is low at 5.5 lamellae per 100 mm and enamel thickness averages 2.75 mm. This fits well within the published measurement ranges of typical *M. meridionalis*. Coupled with the height of the Stříbrníky terrace, which is roughly 130 m above the current Elbe River level, this suggests an Early Pleistocene origin for the Stříbrníky terrace (Tyráček et al., 2004). It is thus more appropriate to correlate the material from Stříbrníky with the *M. meridionalis* from Upper Valdarno rather than *M. rumanus* from the British Red Crag or Romania (Lister & van Essen, 2003). All measured traits of the molar resemble typical *M. meridionalis* far more than *M. rumanus*.

Using all of this information, it can be said that the specimen from Stříbrníky represents the first reliably confirmed record of *M. meridionalis* from the Czech Republic, based on the morphology and morphometry of the molar. This specimen extends the known range of early *M. meridionalis* in Central Europe further to the northeast and provides us with possibly the oldest remains of a large Quaternary mammal known from the Czech Republic.

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Modern ooids of the Mediterranean coast of Egypt

SOUMYADEEP BISWAS¹ & MICHAŁ MATYSIK¹

*1 – Institute of Geological Sciences, Jagiellonian University; Kraków, Poland;
soumyadeep.biswas@doctoral.uj.edu.pl*

Carbonate sediments are key geological archives of the past climate because they form directly in seawater and record regional conditions. A particular type of carbonate grains are ooids, which are concentrically laminated grains produced by carbonate precipitation and abrasion, typically forming above the wave base on tropical to subtropical carbonate platforms (Davies, 1978). Ooids are widely used to reconstruct seawater history (Wilkinson, 1986; Trower, 2020) and thus Earth's climate. Consequently, they are generally thought to be absent from non-tropical seas undersaturated with respect to CaCO₃. The Mediterranean Sea contradicts this hypothesis, as ooids occur locally in beach and coastal sediments of Egypt. Their origin is unclear; some are considered recycled Pleistocene ooids based on bulk-sediment radiocarbon ages, but even then, the environmental and climatic conditions that enabled their Pleistocene formation remain unconstrained. This study aims to identify the environmental factors controlling ooid formation in the non-tropical Mediterranean Sea during the Quaternary and to explain why suitable conditions developed only in particular areas and time intervals. This, in turn, will refine our understanding of ooid-forming processes, improve interpretations of oolitic records in the geologic past, and sharpen predictions of future coastal geomorphological and sedimentological changes under the ongoing climatic and oceanographic change.

Fifty loose sand samples were collected into 50 ml plastic vials along the Mediterranean coast of Egypt from Alexandria to Marsa Matruh, from the backshore, foreshore, and shoreface (depth of 2–3 m), and grouped into 15 transects. Granulometric analyses determined grain-size distribution. One thin section per locality was examined under an optical microscope for ooid characteristics and grain counting. SEM-EDS analyses were performed on whole, knife-halved and hammer-crushed ooids, as well as on selected carbon-coated thin-section areas. The ooids were also analyzed for major, minor, trace, and rare earth elements using LA-ICP-MS. Radiocarbon dating of ooids from selected localities was used to compare their ages.

Grain size analysis of loose sediments along the Egyptian coast indicates mainly fine to coarse sand, with few samples of very coarse sand (mean: 481.54 μm). Sorting is poor to moderately good, with most samples ranging from moderately to well-sorted. Skewness ranges from symmetrical to very coarse skewed; most samples are symmetrical, with some coarse to very coarse skewed, suggesting stronger erosion (Duane, 1964; Symphonia, 2018). Kurtosis ranges from very platykurtic to very leptokurtic. The sediments are mainly loose carbonate rich in ooids, peloids, and bioclasts, with minor local quartz. Ooid content decreases westward from Alexandria to Marsa Matruh (65.2% to 43.1%), while bioclasts and peloids increase to 9.7% and 24.2%, respectively. Peloids are oval to sub-rounded. Bioclasts include foraminifera, echinoderms, coralline red algae, and bryozoans. Most ooids are normal, with concentric cortices up to 410 μm thick. SEM-EDS analysis revealed alternating light and dark cortical laminae, each composed of randomly organized micron-scale needles that contain slightly elevated Sr concentrations, indicating aragonite. Shale-normalized REE+Y patterns of the cortices show: (1) HREE enrichment over LREE, (2) positive La anomalies, and (3) positive Ce anomalies. Radiometric ages fall within the overall range of approximately 1600 AD to 8000 BC and increase (get older) from outer cortex to nucleus.

The study of ooids along the Mediterranean coast of Egypt shows marked variability in sediment composition and a westward decrease in ooid content, which correlates with westward decrease in the number of submarine nearshore bars, suggesting that those bars are the main sites of ooid formation. The radiometric ages suggest that some ooids formed almost 10,000 years and that the ooid growth generally ceased with the emergence of the Little Ice Age around 1650 AD.

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One LCT family, two fractionation pathways: Nb-Ta-Fe-Mn systematics in amblygonite-type (Viitaniemi) and lepidolite-type (Alvarrões) pegmatites

ALEKSANDER BŁASIAK¹

1 – Department of Economic Geology, Faculty of Geology, Geophysics and Environmental Protection, AGH University of Krakow; Kraków, Poland; ablasiak@student.agh.edu.pl

Highly fractionated pegmatites of the LCT (Li-Cs-Ta) family may share a common genetic framework, yet their ore-mineral chemistry can record fundamentally different fractionation trajectories and late-stage processes (Černý & Ercit, 2005). This contribution presents a comparative study of Sn-Nb-Ta oxide mineralization in two rare-element LCT pegmatites: the Viitaniemi pegmatite, located in the Eräjärvi district, southern Finland (Lahti, 1989), representing an amblygonite-type system (Kluza et al., 2022), and the Alvarrões pegmatite, located in Central Iberian Zone, Portugal, classified as a complex lepidolite-type (Sousa et al., 2018). Although both intrusions belong to the same LCT family, their oxide chemistry reveals divergent metallogenic pathways.

The comparison integrates petrographic observations and electron microprobe analyses (EPMA) of cassiterite and columbite-group minerals (CGM) from both pegmatites, including wodginite where present (Viitaniemi). In Alvarrões, the dataset is complemented by additional LA-ICP-MS trace-element analyses of cassiterite. Compositional data were evaluated using the columbite-tantalite quadrilateral and ternary (Sn+Ti - Ta+Nb - Mn+Fe) systematics to track Mn-Fe partitioning and Nb-Ta evolution.

In Viitaniemi, CGM compositions show a clear predominance of Ta-dominant members, with abundant tantalite and subordinate columbite. The quadrilateral plot (Fig. 1A) reveals a broad and dispersed compositional field, reflecting complex evolution. Cassiterite is systematically Ta-enriched (Ta₂O₅ up to 8.16 wt.% and Nb₂O₅ up to 2.15 wt.%) and contains on average 0.43 wt.% FeO, with a mean FeO/MnO ratio of 13.7, indicating Fe-dominant conditions during oxide crystallization. Textural and chemical evidence demonstrates significant late-stage hydrothermal overprint. Nb-Ta-Fe were partially leached from cassiterite by S-bearing fluids, as supported by the occurrence of the herzenbergite-teallite series and documented redistribution processes (Kluza et al., 2022). This secondary modification explains the compositional scatter observed in the quadrilateral diagram (Fig. 1A) and indicates that the present oxide chemistry reflects not only magmatic fractionation but also hydrothermal remobilization (Kluza et al., 2022).

In contrast, Alvarrões is characterized by a strongly Mn-dominant CGM population clustering near the Mn-columbite field (Fig. 1B), with columbite compositions clearly prevailing over tantalite (Sousa et al., 2018). Cassiterite reaches up to 4.71 wt.% Ta₂O₅ and 2.68 wt.% Nb₂O₅ and contains on average 0.31 wt.% MnO, with a mean MnO/FeO ratio of 68, documenting extreme Mn enrichment and Fe depletion in the evolving system. LA-ICP-MS data reveal elevated concentrations of high field strength elements (HFSE), including Zr (up to 0.37 wt.%) and Hf (up to 0.03 wt.%), consistent with trace-element systematics typical of highly evolved pegmatitic cassiterite (Kumar et al., 2024). Although hydrothermal leaching comparable to that documented in Viitaniemi has not been directly confirmed in Alvarrões, textural relationships suggest that fluid–oxide interaction may also have influenced late-stage mineral chemistry.

Despite belonging to the same LCT family, the Viitaniemi (amblygonite-type) and Alvarrões (lepidolite-type) pegmatites record distinct Nb-Ta-Fe-Mn fractionation patterns, reflecting different evolutionary pathways and late-stage processes. Viitaniemi represents a Ta-dominant, Fe-influenced system modified by hydrothermal remobilization, whereas Alvarrões preserves a Mn-dominant assemblage consistent with highly evolved magmatic conditions. Such variability is consistent with CGM systematics, where Fe-Mn and Nb-Ta substitutions govern compositional trends (Ercit et al., 1995), but fractionation trajectories in LCT pegmatites may be complex and variable (Galliski & Černý, 2006).

Consequently, although it has long been recognized that LCT classification alone does not fully predict oxide chemistry or metal distribution, this study highlights that Nb-Ta-Fe-Mn systematics in CGM provide a sensitive tool for distinguishing fractionation pathways within rare-element pegmatite provinces, particularly in relation to the degree of magmatic fractionation, evolving Fe-Mn partitioning and Nb-Ta enrichment trends, fluorine activity, and late-stage fluid-driven remobilization processes.

Figure 1. Columbite quadrilateral illustrating the composition of columbite-group minerals from two LCT pegmatites: (A) amblygonite-type Viitaniemi (Finland) and (B) complex lepidolite-type Alvarrões (Portugal).

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World-class mercury deposits: comparative insights from Almadén (Spain) and Idrija (Slovenia)

GAL BUBNIČ¹ & JORGE L. COSTAFREDA²

1 – Department of Geology, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering, University of Ljubljana; Ljubljana, Slovenija; gb78843@student.uni-lj.si

2 – Escuela Tecnica Superior de Ingenieros de Minas y Energia, Universidad Politecnica de Madrid; Madrid, Spain

World-class mercury mineral systems are exceptionally rare and concentrated in only a few geological provinces worldwide. The majority of historically produced mercury originates from the Almadén district (Spain; ~250 000 t Hg, 30–35 % global production) and the Idrija deposit (Slovenia; ~105 000 t Hg, 12–15 %), which are now closed. Both have been extensively investigated individually in the past, but a comparison between these two giant mercury deposits is lacking. In this work, we focus on geological, structural, mineralogical and geochemical constraints to determine whether Almadén and Idrija represent distinct metallogenic classes or a common hydrothermal system.

The two giant systems developed in distinct geological settings. Almadén mineralization is hosted within the Lower Silurian Criadero Quartzite, associated volcano-sedimentary sequences, and the Frailesca unit, a basaltic diatreme complex (Higuera et al., 2012). In contrast, Idrija consists primarily of strongly deformed sedimentary rocks that were originally a part of the Slovenian carbonate platform. Tertiary thrusting further divided and fractured the deposit into several blocks. Hydrothermal fluids focused along fractures enriched the surrounding rocks, producing the highest-grade ore (Mlakar & Drovenik, 1971). In Almadén, mercury enrichment is associated with Silurian submarine volcanism, which initiated hydrothermal activity. These contrasting structural architectures demonstrate different mechanisms of fluid pathways and ore geometry. However, both systems required sustained permeability and significant volatile flux to accumulate mercury at world-class scale.

Ore characteristics further point to the differences of mercury deposits. The Hg deposits of Almadén correspond to stratabound and stockwork types. Stratabound type is well-defined in aforementioned Criadero Quartzite, which were folded and sheared during the Variscan deformation. Stockwork mineralization occupies fractures and veins and locally replaces volcanic rocks deformed by Variscan shear zones (Palero-Fernández et al., 2014). On the other hand, Idrija has two principal styles of mineralization. The first is epigenetic, characterized by hydrothermal fluids precipitating cinnabar within fractures and veins, locally accompanied by replacement of carbonate host rocks. The second style is mostly syngenetic, where cinnabar occurs within strongly kaolinized plagioclase-rich lithologies (Mlakar & Drovenik, 1971). Mineralization in both deposits is essentially monometallic, dominated by cinnabar with subordinate pyrite. Despite their differences, both deposits have recorded large-scale mobilization of mercury by hydrothermal fluids.

Geochemical and isotopic data provide insights into the characteristics of cinnabar mineralization at Idrija and Almadén. The variety of trace elements observed in Almadén and Idrija pyrite, alongside Co/Ni ratios and mercury isotopes provide insight into the hydrothermal systems of the two largest mercury deposits in the world. LA-ICP-MS analyses of Almadén pyrite reveal relatively low trace element concentrations, with As reaching a maximum of 377 ppm. Median concentrations are 176 ppm for Mn, 156.5 ppm for As, and 93 ppm for Sn (Martín et al., 1988). In contrast, LA-ICP-MS analyses of Idrija pyrite indicate even lower trace element concentrations, with all elements remaining below 100 ppm. The most abundant elements are Pb, Ni, and As, with median values of 21.92, 17.92, and 10.78 ppm, respectively (Bubnič et al., 2026). Co/Ni ratios are below 1 in both deposits, ranging from 0.1 to 0.3 in Almadén and 0.01 to 0.1 in Idrija. Mercury isotope data for Almadén show average $\delta^{202}\text{Hg}$ (mass-dependent fractionation, MDF) of -0.56‰ and $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ (mass-independent fractionation, MIF) of -0.21‰ (Gray et al., 2013). Corresponding averages for Idrija are slightly higher, with $\delta^{202}\text{Hg} = -0.46\text{‰}$ and $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg} = -0.11\text{‰}$ (Božič et al., 2023).

Trace element composition of pyrite is relatively low in both deposits. This could potentially reflect limited metal-carrying capacity of hydrothermal fluids, possibly related to low salinity despite being very rich in Hg. Co/Ni ratios <1 in both deposits indicate a sedimentary origin of pyrite. Mercury isotope composition of both deposits likely points to a variety of hydrothermal processes that produced cinnabar mineralization. Negative $\Delta^{199}\text{Hg}$ values could imply the terrestrial source of mercury. Together, these observations suggest that while structural and depositional context of Almadén and Idrija differ, both deposits formed through hydrothermal mobilization of mercury within porous pathways.

This comparative work provides insights into the differences of two biggest mercury deposits in the world. Almadén and Idrija demonstrate that giant mercury deposits can form within contrasting tectonic and structural settings but still share fundamental hydrothermal controls. Trace element systematics, Co/Ni ratios, and mercury isotope data collectively indicate sedimentary-influenced hydrothermal systems capable of sustained mercury mobilization. We envision future work that both enhances the Almadén–Idrija comparison and extends the study to other deposits, such as Mt. Amiata, to better understand the global controls on mercury mineralization.

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Geochemistry, radiogenic isotopes and geochronology of the Tertiary volcanic rocks in the Veneto Volcanic Province (VVP), NE Italy. Petrogenetic implications and metallogenic potential

INTI CLARO-VARGAS¹ & MASSIMO CHIARADIA¹

1 – Department of Earth Sciences, Université de Genève; Geneva, Switzerland; inti.claro@etu.unige.ch

The Veneto Volcanic Province (VVP) represents the most significant magmatic district of the Adria plate, situated in north-eastern Italy in the provinces of Trento, Verona, Vicenza and Padova. This Paleogene suite of volcanic rocks is divided into five distinct districts: Val d'Adige, Lessini Mounts, Berici Hills, Euganean Hills, and Marostica Hills. They are mainly basic-ultrabasic (nephelinites to tholeiites) in composition, with localized acid volcanic and sub-volcanic bodies in the Euganean Hills. This volcanism is produced by intraplate magmatism, erupted through transtensional rifting during the collision of the European and Adria plates. The mechanisms responsible for this magmatism remain a subject of academic debate. Several mechanisms have been proposed, including decompression melting linked to transtensional faulting in Alpine convergence, slab breakoff generating a slab window, or poloidal mantle flow bypassing the Alpine slab, remaining isolated from subduction-related fluids. This latter one distinguishes the VVP's intraplate signature from the orogenic geochemistry observed in nearby regions like Adamello. Our study aims to assess the petrogenesis and metallogenic potential of the VVP using whole-rock geochemistry, radiogenic isotopes (Sr, Nd, Pb and Hf) and U-Pb zircon dating.

Available geochronological data reveal a clear south-eastward migration of volcanic activity over time. Magmatism began intermittently during the Paleocene and Eocene in the western sectors, specifically the Lessini Mts. and Val d'Adige, with ages spanning approximately from 51 to 38 Ma. By the Middle Eocene, activity shifted toward the Berici Hills. During the Oligocene (~32 Ma), volcanism became prominent in the Euganean Hills, followed by the Marostica Hills, where activity persisted into the Early Miocene, ending around 23–20 Ma. This temporal evolution is supported by previous Ar–Ar, K–Ar, and U–Pb zircon dating (Brombin et al., 2021; Visonà et al., 2007; Bartoli et al., 2014). We aim to determine the ages of multiple volcanic bodies in the Euganean Hills, Lessini Mts., and Berici Hills using U–Pb zircon dating combined with zircon trace-element analysis to better constrain the chronological and petrogenetic evolution of the district.

The south-eastward temporal evolution of volcanic activity is also matched by the geochemical evolution patterns of the province. Our data show that the most mafic rocks from Val d'Adige, Lessini and Marostica range from foidites to basanites and alkali-basalts. No ultramafic or tholeiitic rocks were found, and the most primitive rocks from these districts show similar geochemical characteristics. In comparison, the Euganean Hills rocks exhibit a wide range of compositions from tholeiitic basalts to rhyolites. Trace element compositions revealed that the mafic districts have similar signatures to OIBs, with a slight negative K anomaly. Additionally, the compositions of the Euganean Hills rocks indicate an influence of crustal assimilation and fractional crystallization, recognized in positive anomalies of Pb and K, and negative anomalies in Sr, P and Ti for the most felsic bodies (>62 wt% SiO₂).

Tectonic discrimination diagrams suggest that volcanism can be classified as within-plate magmatism, in late- to post-orogenic intracontinental domain, with minor influence of alkaline domain. Preliminary results on partial melting REE modelling indicate that the mantle source must have undergone a metasomatism to generate the enrichment in incompatible elements. This hypothesis is consistent with previous studies of the VVP, which suggest a complex mantle source influenced by varying degrees of melting and metasomatism.

To further support the geochemical data, previous studies of radiogenic isotopes (Sr, Nd, Pb) indicate affinities with the HIMU (High U/Pb ratio) and EAR (European Asthenospheric Reservoir) com-

ponents. Deeper, more alkaline melts show more pronounced HIMU signatures, while shallower sub-alkaline magmas retain a slight EMII (Enriched Mantle 2) signature, likely reflecting older lithospheric enrichment. However, our study indicates that Sr-Nd-Pb isotopic data show affinities with the HIMU end-member, close to the FOZO (FOcal ZOne, Stracke et al., 2005) and CiMACI (Circum-Mediterranean Anorogenic Cenozoic Igneous districts, equivalent to the EAR, Lustrino, 2007), and a possible mixing between DMM and HIMU-EMI components. The Pb isotopic data indicate signatures closer to the EMII end-member, similar to those of FOZO and CiMACI.

Regarding the metallogenic potential, according to Chiaradia (2022), subvolcanic and volcanic bodies related to Au-rich Cu-Au deposits have distinct geochemical characteristics. They have an average composition of SiO_2 ~63 wt%, MgO ~2 wt%, FeO_{tot} ~4.5 wt%, La/Yb ~15, Dy/Yb ~1.8 whereas Sr/Y exhibits a bimodality with peaks at ~55 and ~70. For this study, the district that best fits these constraints are the intermediate to felsic bodies of the Eugani for major elements. The best fits for the trace elements ratios are the mafic bodies for Sr/Y, while the other ratios are up to 3 times higher than the values estimated for prospective Au-rich deposits.

Considering that the starting composition of the most primitive samples can be used to estimate a nature of the source, we will perform AFC (Assimilation-Fractional Crystallization) modelling to reproduce the compositions of the most evolved bodies from the province. This will also allow us to evaluate the metallogenic potential of the area, considering the aforementioned parameters.

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Improving real-time earthquake source characterization using diffusion model based broadband envelope synthetics

FRANCESCO ALEXANDR COLOSIMO¹, DARIO JOZINOVIC¹ & MAREN BÖSE¹

1 – Swiss Seismological Service (SED), ETH Zürich; Switzerland; fcolosimo@ethz.ch

Reliable real-time earthquake source characterisation requires the rapid selection of solutions from competing algorithms while minimising false alarms. To address this challenge, Jozinović et al. (2024) proposed a ground-motion-envelope-based goodness-of-fit approach that ranks candidate source solutions using amplitude ratios and cross-correlation between observed and predicted waveform envelopes. In its current implementation, however, this approach relies on the ground-motion envelope prediction model of Cua (2005), which was calibrated initially for small-to-moderate earthquakes ($M < 6.5$) and therefore under-represents the variability and complexity of large-magnitude ruptures. Consequently, events near the edge of the calibration magnitude range may be mischaracterised, leading to biased magnitude estimates, overconfident likelihood scores, and potential mis-ranking of competing source solutions during the earliest seconds of an event, when P-wave information is most limited.

In this work, we investigate the benefits and limitations of replacing this empirical model with envelopes derived from machine-learning-generated broadband (up to 50 Hz) synthetic waveforms (Palgunadi et al., 2025). In seismology, machine-learning-based waveform generation offers a way to address the limited availability of recordings for rare large-magnitude events and specific source–path–site configurations. Traditional physics-based simulations can reproduce many aspects of earthquake ground motion but remain computationally expensive, particularly when modelling broadband waveforms with realistic high-frequency content (Palgunadi et al., 2024). In contrast, recent generative models provide a fast, data-driven alternative for producing large ensembles of plausible ground motions.

In our framework, these synthetics are generated using a denoising diffusion model conditioned on preliminary source parameters (magnitude, hypocentral distance, depth, azimuthal gap) and site effects (V_s30). While such models are stochastic and not based on an explicit physical rupture model, they are trained on observed strong-motion data and are able to reproduce key statistical properties of real ground motions. This enables efficient sampling of a rich ensemble of physically plausible broadband waveforms for a given source without the computational burden of full kinematic simulations.

For large-magnitude events ($M > 6.5$), we further superpose multiple point-source synthetics to construct realistic finite-fault rupture waveforms using the SWEET workflow (Colosimo, 2025). This approach approximates rupture propagation, directivity, and spatially variable slip while avoiding the need for a full finite-fault inversion in real time. The resulting framework produces a flexible synthetic database that can be queried on the fly to evaluate candidate solutions, enabling probabilistic envelope-based ranking that is not tied to a single empirical scaling relation derived from sparse strong-motion observations.

We find that the diffusion-based synthetics extrapolate across a broader magnitude and distance range (up to 200 km) and reproduce observed envelope characteristics comparably to the empirical prediction model, particularly for high-frequency content and complex site responses. This approach strengthens the decision stage of EEW systems by enabling a probabilistic envelope-based plausibility check of candidate source solutions produced by algorithms such as the Virtual Seismologist (VS) and FinDer.

Beyond performance evaluations on benchmark datasets (e.g., the 2019 Ridgecrest California M7.1), our results suggest a pathway for integrating modern generative models into operational earthquake early warning (EEW) systems. By decoupling envelope predictions from fixed empirical laws and tying them to data-driven synthetics trained on strong-motion catalogues, our workflow supports EEW advancements. In general, it also enables scenario simulations to test and optimise EEW algorithms or improve network geometry, as explored in Colosimo (2025).

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ARTeMIS: A European training through research program for exploration geologists

VEGAS COUPÉ¹, ELENI INTZEVIDOU², ZSOMBOR ÉLIÁS³, STEPHANIE LEONAKI⁴ KILLIAN SANDFORD¹, DIMITRIS PAPAPOPOULOS², SZABOLCS JÁNVÁR³, GEORGE SOULAMIDIS⁴, JAKUB PRCÚCH⁵ & MARJOLÈNE JATTEAU¹

1 – *Université de Lorraine, Faculty of Science and Technology, Nancy, France*

2 – *Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece; eintzev@geo.auth.gr*

3 – *Eötvös Loránd University, Budapest, Hungary*

4 – *National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Athens, Greece*

5 – *Comenius University Bratislava, Bratislava, Slovakia*

ARTeMIS (Action for Research and Teaching Mineral Exploration Inclusive School) is an ERASMUS+ training-through-research initiative aimed at enhancing employability and interdisciplinary skills in economic geology and mineral exploration. The program connects European universities and industrial partners to promote collaborative training and research in mineral exploration, primarily for postgraduate students. Now in its second three-year cycle, it builds on a successful pilot phase that demonstrated the value of integrating portable geochemical tools into field-based education. It expands interdisciplinary training and inter-university collaboration, incorporating portable analytical technologies, digital workflows and research-driven field methodologies. A central objective is to explore how modern analytical tools can be effectively integrated into university training to address contemporary exploration challenges and European strategic metal needs. Beyond the annual program, specialised training sessions are conducted on hydrothermal deposits in Lavrion (Greece) and Banská Štiavnica (Slovakia).

The annual activities of the ARTeMIS project are organised into two main phases. The first phase brings together students and professors for a one-week course on mineral resource geochemistry, metallogeny, and deposit characterisation, combined with practical training using portable analytical tools (pXRF, pLIBS, pVNIR-SWIR, pRAMAN). This phase also includes discussions on the economic and geopolitical context of raw materials within the European Union. Students are trained in instrument operation, safety procedures, and analytical reliability, preparing them for modern field-based geochemical exploration.

The second phase includes three days of lectures and practical exercises, followed by a ten-day field investigation in NE Greece (Chalkidiki, Kavala, Maronia, Sapes, and Kallintiri), within the Rhodope metallogenic province. This region is a major Cenozoic extensional domain characterised by detachment systems and metamorphic core complexes associated with slab rollback processes (Jolivet and Brun, 2010). Oligocene magmatism and associated magmatic-hydrothermal activity generated porphyry, skarn, carbonate replacement and epithermal mineralisation systems (Voudouris et al., 2019).

Fieldwork provides students with hands-on training in modern mineral exploration techniques. With the guidance of professors, students connect field observations to metallogenic and geotectonic models, enhancing their interpretation of complex hydrothermal systems. Rapid elemental analyses (pXRF, pLIBS) are combined with in situ mineralogical identification (pVNIR-SWIR, pRAMAN) to characterise alteration systems and mineral assemblages at outcrop scale. Structural and analytical data are recorded using digital mapping tools (QField, FieldMove Clino), enabling real-time data integration and interpretation while strengthening students' exploration-scale reasoning skills. Konos Hill (Sapes) is a telescoped hydrothermal system affected by multiple overprinting alteration events and provides an excellent example for field-based identification of alteration assemblages. Portable spectroscopic techniques were employed for in situ mineral identification and high-resolution mapping of alteration zones. The outcome was the development of a hydrothermal alteration map of the area, which was compared with previously established alteration zones (Mavrogonatos et al., 2018), allowing a critical assessment of consistency. The results delineate a porphyry-style advanced argillic lithocap with

potassic, phyllic and propylitic assemblages. Additionally, the project develops approaches to identify rhenium in molybdenite using portable spectroscopic tools, despite the metal not being directly measurable.

Beyond the geological outcomes, the program produces significant educational benefits through collaborative data analysis and interpretation. Each year, international teams of four students analyse datasets and create scientific reports, which are evaluated for academic credits. They also contribute to the ARTeMIS database, supporting ongoing research on hydrothermal systems and mineral exploration. Through this process, participants develop analytical, teamwork and communication skills preparing them for future careers in both academia and the mineral exploration industry.

In addition to its educational impact, the ARTeMIS program has produced scientific outputs, including a dedicated field guide, methodological frameworks, and peer-reviewed publications on portable analytical methods and exploration indicators (Jatteau et al., 2025; Soulamidis et al., 2026). The collaborative environment also supports research exchanges, MSc theses, and doctoral projects among partner universities, strengthening international academic collaboration.

Overall, ARTeMIS illustrates how training-through-research approaches can enhance student expertise, generate scientifically valuable datasets, and advance exploration methodologies while contributing to the European effort to secure strategic metal resources.

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Characteristics and interpretation of the heavy minerals from sediments in selected caves in Cracow

WERONIKA CZWONDA¹

1 – Institute of Geological Sciences, Faculty of Geography and Geology, Jagiellonian University, Cracow, Poland; weronika.czwonda@student.uj.edu.pl

Heavy minerals analysed in this research were separated from the sandy sediments collected in caves located in Cracow– Pychowicka Cave and Twardowski Cave– for the author's bachelor's thesis. The aim of this research is to analyse and characterise found heavy minerals under an optical microscope and scanning electron microscope with energy dispersive spectroscopy.

Cracow is situated in southern Poland, in the Carpathian Foredeep Basin filled with Neogene molasse (Golonka, 2007) covering Paleozoic and Mesozoic basement. The study area is located on the border of the Cracow-Częstochowa Upland– within the Silesian-Cracow Monocline built up of Mesozoic sedimentary rocks– known for the Upper Jurassic carbonate rocks dipping gently to the NE (in the studied region mainly Oxfordian limestones, locally dolomitised in the Upper Oxfordian), carbonate buildups and karst caves (Rutkowski, 1989; Matyszkiewicz et al., 2006; Matyszkiewicz, 2008). Selected caves are located within the Zakrzówek horst– one of seven horst structures in Cracow formed during Miocene tectonic movements. Other deposits observed in the vicinity of the study area are also Cretaceous carbonate rocks, Miocene sediments and Quaternary alluvial deposits of the Vistula River (Sermet & Rolka, 2013).

Samples (three from Twardowski Cave and six from Pychowicka Cave) were prepared according to Mange & Maurer (1992), the heavy fraction was then separated in sodium polytungstate (density of 2.89 g/cm³) and mounted on the slides. Some samples were further prepared for SEM-EDS analysis– prepared material was placed on a carbon tape, covered with gold film for better imaging and set onto the sample holder. Samples observed under an optical microscope contained translucent minerals such as zircon, tourmaline, rutile, garnet, amphibole, staurolite, kyanite, andalusite, sillimanite, epidote, zoisite, clinozoisite, apatite and titanite. Additionally, SEM-EDS analysis revealed several grains of chromian spinels in some samples.

Based on the mineral assemblage, characteristics of the grains and studied literature– namely Garzanti & Andò (2007) and Bucher & Grapes (2011)– it was determined that host rocks for those sediments were most likely metamorphic rocks such as schists, amphibolites and gneisses and, to a lesser extent, plutonic rocks. The heavy mineral composition found in the samples and ZTR index was analogous to the fluvio-glacial sands near Cracow dating back to the Sanian Glaciation stage in the Pleistocene (Raciniowski, 2000; Raciniowski, 2010) and to the other glacial deposits in the further parts of Poland (Gwóźdź & Raciniowski, 1968). Other characteristics, such as roundness and mineral composition non-typical for Carpathian flysch, as well as limits of the Vistula river system during the Pleistocene, further suggest glacial-river transport of sediments from the north (Rutkowski, 1989; Oszczytko & Salata, 2005; Grzebyk & Leszczyński, 2006; Bonova et al., 2018; Salata & Uchman, 2020).

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Progressive microstructural evolution of titanite during post-magmatic hydrothermal alteration of Mesoproterozoic granitoids, southern Lithuania

OLGA DEMINA¹, GRAŽINA SKRIDLAITĖ¹ & LAURYNAS ŠILIAUSKAS¹

1 – State Scientific Research Institute Nature Research Centre; Vilnius, Lithuania;
olga.demina@gamtc.lt

The Marcinkonys granitoids crystallised at ca. 1.51 Ga (Sundblad et al., 1994) and experienced a post-magmatic hydrothermal reworking at ca. 1.48 Ga (Stein et al., 1998), as recorded by U-Pb zircon and Re-Os molybdenite ages, respectively. The post-magmatic hydrothermal overprint is recorded by albitisation, chloritisation and widespread modification of accessory minerals, such as titanite, zircon and REE-bearing phases. This study integrates petrography and electron microprobe (EPMA) mineral chemistry to trace the successive textural and compositional changes of titanite during fluid-rock interaction.

Titanite occurs in diverse textures, from large euhedral grains with preserved magmatic cores to porous pseudomorphic aggregates and compact secondary overgrowths (Fig. 1A). Three texturally and chemically distinct titanite types indicating successive stages of alteration within a single grain are recognised. Type-1 titanite forms homogeneous inner domains interpreted as magmatic in origin. During fluid infiltration, these cores underwent coupled dissolution-precipitation, producing porous Type-2 titanite characterised by patchy zoning, internal voids and abundant micro-scale replacement textures. This stage is commonly associated with the formation of anatase, calcite and local accumulations of Ca-REE-rich phases within dissolved domains. These features indicate a breakdown of primary titanite and redistribution of Ca, Ti and REE. Later, the compact, inclusion-free and non-porous Type-3 titanite, and it overgrows along grain margins and Fe-oxide interfaces. Type-3 titanite overgrowths are depleted in REE and enriched in F relative to types 1 and 2, suggesting reprecipitation from the evolved, F-bearing fluids after partial removal of incompatible elements during the earlier alteration stages. The sharp textural boundaries between porous and type-3 titanite indicate their modification proceeded via coupled dissolution-precipitation rather than solid-state diffusion (Putnis, 2002).

EPMA data reveal systematic chemical trends from Type-1 to Type-3 titanite, indicating decreasing REE and Y contents, increasing fluorine concentrations, and shifts in Fe/Al ratios. Chondrite-normalised REE patterns obtained by LA-ICP-MS from titanite in a representative sample further illustrate these differences between titanite generations (Fig. 1B). A key feature of the titanite breakdown is the decoupling of Ti and REE behaviour: Ti is locally retained and reprecipitated as secondary titanite or TiO₂ phases, whereas REE are preferentially mobilised and partly incorporated into discrete secondary phases including anatase, calcite and Ca-REE-rich phases or removed from the system. This element-specific redistribution reflects fluid composition, redox evolution and local mineral-fluid buffering reactions, comparable to hydrothermal titanite modification described in Proterozoic granitoids elsewhere (Morad et al., 2009).

Systematic changes in the studied titanite U-Pb isotope composition support our interpretation of primary magmatic domains. They record Mesoproterozoic ages within error of the reported zircon dating, whereas porous and recrystallised domains show isotopic disturbance consistent with the fluid-assisted modification.

These results demonstrate that titanite in the Marcinkonys granitoids records a multistage history of magmatic crystallisation, post-magmatic hydrothermal alteration and secondary reprecipitation. The integration of microstructures and mineral chemistry provides new insights into HFSE and REE redistribution during post-magmatic alteration in AMCG-related granitoid systems. The direct correlation between microtexture and isotopic behaviour highlights the importance of process-based interpretation of accessory mineral geochronology.

Figure 1. (A) BSE image showing progressive titanite alteration: a preserved magmatic core (Type-1) is partly replaced by porous Type-2 titanite formed by coupled dissolution–reprecipitation, while compact, inclusion-free Type-3 titanite forms later overgrowths along grain margins. Associated minerals: Chl - chlorite, Cal - calcite, Py - pyrite, Kfs - K-feldspar, Pl - plagioclase. **(B)** Chondrite-normalised REE patterns of titanite from a representative sample obtained by LA-ICP-MS. Type-1 and Type-2 show overlapping REE compositions, whereas Type-3 displays lower REE concentrations, indicating progressive hydrothermal modification.

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Unlocking geothermal potential in Pannonian Basin carbonate reservoirs using machine learning

MOHAMED AYED ELBALAWY^{1,2}, ERNŐ TAKÁCS^{1,3} & FELICITÁSZ VELLEDETS¹

1 – Institute of Exploration Geosciences, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Sciences and Engineering, University of Miskolc; Miskolc, Hungary;

elbalawy.mohamed.ayed.ibrahim.fahd@student.uni-miskolc.hu

2 – Geophysics Department, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University; Cairo, Egypt

3 – Supervisory Authority for Regulatory Affairs; Budapest, Hungary

Introduction

Deep Mesozoic carbonate reservoirs are among Hungary's most promising yet least constrained geothermal targets. Their complex fracture networks, elevated temperatures, and importance for district-heating expansion demand evaluation methods that are explicitly probabilistic and uncertainty-aware. This study develops an integrated workflow that links geological interpretation, 3D temperature modelling, and volumetric heat-in-place (HIP) and recoverable heat (Hrec) assessment to quantify the geothermal potential of a fractured Triassic carbonate system in the western Pannonian Basin. The average geothermal gradient calculated from several wells (≈ 54.2 °C km⁻¹) together with a lithology-dependent conductive heat-transfer model suggests reservoir temperatures of ~95–110 °C at depths of 1.7–2.0 km. Using the 3DHIP-Calculator with Monte-Carlo simulation, we estimate a stored resource of 16,400 PJ and an average recoverable capacity of 535 MW_{th}, with uncertainty ranges reflecting variability in porosity, reservoir thickness, thermal properties, and recovery factors.

Method

This study applies an integrated workflow linking geological interpretation, 3D seismic derived reservoir geometry, and probabilistic HIP and Hrec estimation to evaluate a fractured Triassic carbonate system in the Dány block, Pannonian Basin. The approach is built on three methodological pillars:

1. Structural stratigraphic framework and reservoir geometry: Triassic carbonate geometry, thickness, and compartmentalization were mapped using 3D post-stack seismic data and five wells providing the deterministic backbone for probabilistic volumetrics.
2. Machine-learning facies and geobody mapping: a PCA-SOM workflow (Principal Component Analysis - Self-Organizing Maps) utilizing seven seismic attributes explaining 92.8% of the data variance (PC1 = 68.1%, PC2 = 24.66%), followed by SOM clustering to separate carbonate from shale facies. The resulting carbonate geobody, calibrated to well control, defines reservoir thickness and spatial extent and serves as fixed geometric input for HIP/Hrec modelling.
3. Probabilistic HIP/Hrec modelling: Stored and recoverable heat were computed using the 3DHIP-Calculator (Piris et al., 2021) with Monte Carlo simulation of geological and thermal uncertainties.

Results

Seismic attributes and PCA: Ten post-stack seismic attributes were extracted to enhance structural and stratigraphic signals for carbonate-facies mapping. Two attribute families were most diagnostic: textural Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) attributes and amplitude/energy attributes. PCA; Hotelling, 1933) was used to remove redundancy and isolate dominant variability.

SOM: Following PCA, an unsupervised Self-Organizing Map (Kohonen, 1982, 2001) was trained and projected back into the survey as a facies map. Co-rendering the SOM with variance emphasizes structural edges and faults. The fixed SOM colour space ensures consistent interpretation: warm hues indi-

cate carbonate-like facies, cool hues represent shale-prone textures, and intermediate tones highlight transitional carbonate–shale contacts. A 3D carbonate probability model further refines reservoir interpretation. High probabilities (0.7–1.0) outline the buildup core, intermediate values (0.4–0.6) define rim zones, and low values (<0.3) correspond to Miocene–Pliocene clastics. This probability volume captures margin geometry, internal heterogeneity, and NW–SE fault segmentation, providing a continuous, uncertainty-aware basis for geothermal reservoir delineation and volumetric analysis.

Geothermal Potential of the study area: The 3DHIP-Calculator was applied to quantify the geothermal potential of the study area by estimating the HIP (PJ km^{-2}) and Hrec (MWth km^{-2}). HIP values range from 155 to 170 PJ km^{-2} . The estimated Hrec varies between 1.5 and 5.5 MWth km^{-2} . Modelled temperatures at the top of the Triassic reservoir indicate favourable thermal conditions for geothermal exploitation.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that integrating machine-learning seismic facies mapping with probabilistic resource assessment provides a powerful, uncertainty-aware framework for evaluating geothermal potential in fractured Triassic carbonates of the Pannonian Basin. PCA–SOM facies mapping yields geologically coherent reservoir geometry that improves carbonate delineation and fault-controlled segmentation, forming a robust foundation for volumetric modelling. The estimated geothermal gradient ($\sim 55 \text{ }^\circ\text{C km}^{-1}$) and resulting temperature field support resources ($>90\text{--}100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) at accessible depths. Probabilistic HIP and Hrec estimates (16,400 PJ and 535 MW_{th}) confirm a substantial resource potential. Overall, the workflow offers a robust, transferable template for de-risking geothermal development in carbonate-dominated basins.

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De-risking facies prediction using an integrated statistical–machine learning seismic workflow: Pannonian Basin case study

ABDELKHALEK MOHAMED ELKAZAZ^{1,2},
MOHAMED AYED ELBALAWY^{1,3} & ERNŐ TAKÁCS^{1,4}

1 – Institute of Exploration Geosciences, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Sciences and Engineering, University of Miskolc; Miskolc, Hungary;

abdelkalek.mohamed.abdelkalek.elkazaz@student.uni-miskolc.hu

2 – Geophysics Department, Faculty of Science, Tanta University, Cairo, Egypt

3 – Geophysics Department, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt

Introduction

Accurate facies prediction is fundamental to reliable reservoir characterization and de-risked development planning, particularly where well control is limited. Building on earlier Pannonian Basin work that used simultaneous inversion and Extended Elastic Impedance (EEI) to infer lithology and fluid distributions (Adipta et al., 2023a, 2023b), this study advances a more integrative, uncertainty-aware workflow to improve classification robustness and reduce boundary ambiguity. Specifically, we combine Bayesian probability-based facies modelling with unsupervised Self-Organizing Maps (SOM; Kohonen, 1982, 2001) and supervised voxel-wise Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) classification to generate consistent facies predictions and associated confidence measures across the 3D seismic volume. The field contains three vertically stacked gas-bearing reservoirs (Sand1–Sand3). The workflow is demonstrated on Sand2 and is designed to be transferable to Sand1 and Sand3 for consistent field-wide evaluation.

Method

Facies definition begins in rock-physics space using a V_p/V_s versus Lambda-Rho ($\lambda\rho$) cross-plot from well logs to separate shale, gas sand, and shaly sand (transitional) clusters. These clusters serve two roles: (i) priors for Bayesian classification and (ii) labeled training targets for the supervised MLP. Four inversion-driven volumes— $\lambda\rho$, Mu-Rho, Acoustic Impedance (AI), and V_p/V_s —are extracted and aligned with seismic and well control to form the attribute feature space. Three complementary classifiers are then applied:

1. Bayesian classification produces most-likely facies and facies probability volumes, explicitly capturing uncertainty at facies boundaries.
2. SOM (unsupervised) is trained on multivariate attribute similarity (notably V_p/V_s , $\lambda\rho$, and AI) to delineate facies patterns independently of labels, providing an objective cross-check on geometry and continuity.
3. Voxel-wise MLP (supervised) is trained on the labeled facies derived from the crossplot and well calibration to generate a final facies prediction and probabilistic evaluation volumes.

Performance and agreement are assessed using normalized confusion matrices and one-vs-rest precision–recall analysis to quantify class-wise reliability and diagnose boundary-driven confusion.

Results

Despite different underlying assumptions, Bayesian, SOM, and MLP converge on a consistent Sand2 gas-sand body geometry enclosed by shale, confirming the internal robustness of the workflow and the information content of the selected inversion attributes. Bayesian probability volumes show high-confidence gas-sand in the core and increasing uncertainty along the margins, where transitional shaly-sand is expected. Within the gas-sand facies, well-calibrated AI trends are used to derive res-

ervoir-property volumes: porosity shows an inverse relationship with AI (reported correlation ~0.71), whereas water saturation increases with AI (reported correlation ~0.82). Applying these transforms within the predicted gas-sand domain highlights a high-quality reservoir core with porosity

~20–25% and water saturation ~20–40%, consistent with gas charge and supporting the geological plausibility of the facies interpretation. The MLP evaluation indicates strong class performance for the dominant (gas sand and shale), while shaly sand remains the least stable class due to its transitional nature and lower representation; most errors concentrate at facies boundaries, reinforcing that ambiguity is geologically meaningful rather than purely algorithmic. The integrated outputs support proposing a new drilling location inside a high-confidence gas-sand fairway identified consistently across methods.

Conclusion

Integrating probability-based Bayesian modelling, unsupervised SOM clustering, and supervised voxel-wise MLP classification provides a practical, uncertainty-aware framework for seismic-scale facies prediction in heterogeneous Pannonian Basin reservoirs. Method-to-method agreement strengthens confidence in Sand2 reservoir geometry and continuity, Bayesian probabilities enable risk-aware boundary interpretation, and AI-derived property mapping adds reservoir-quality context within the predicted gas-sand body. The approach is explicitly designed to be transferable to additional stacked intervals (Sand1 and Sand3) and to support actionable development decisions (e.g., well placement) grounded in both prediction and uncertainty characterization.

Acknowledgement: The authors acknowledge the AASPI consortium (University of Oklahoma) for providing the AASPI software used to compute seismic attributes and machine-learning classifications. We also acknowledge Schlumberger (SLB) for providing Petrel software for seismic visualization and interpretation.

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Structural patterns and petrography of the Birbir shear zone in the Western Ethiopian Shield: implications for a late tectonic evolution of the East African Orogen

BEREKET FENTAW¹, KRYŠTOF VERNER^{1,2}, ADAM PAŘÍZEK¹,
DAVID BURIÁNEK³ & ŠTĚPÁN DVOŘÁK^{1,2}

1 – *Institute of Petrology and Structural Geology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; mekonenb@natur.cuni.cz*

2 – *Czech Geological Survey; Prague, Czech Republic*

3 – *Czech Geological Survey; Brno, Czech Republic*

The structural and petrographical analysis of the Birbir shear zone (BSZ) in the Western Ethiopian Shield (WES) has been investigated to understand the deformational phases of the shear zone and its tectonic evolution within the East African Orogen (ca. 650–620 Ma). Several Neoproterozoic shear zones in the WES exhibit diverse structural styles, ranging from simple shear to transpressive systems, reflecting varying tectonic stress conditions (Johnson et al., 2004; Yihunie and Hailu, 2007). The study area, the southern part of WES, comprises high-grade gneissic and migmatitic domains to the east and west, called Geba and Baro domains, respectively. These domains are separated by low to medium grade rocks of metamorphosed volcano-sedimentary sequences (hornblende, biotite schist), mylonitized amphibolite and biotite-gneiss and mafic to ultramafic rocks (dominantly meta-quartz diorite) of the Birbir domain. The Birbir domain was sheared to a varying degree to the east and west of the gneissic domains at BSZ. All these domains were intruded by diverse suites of syn-to post-tectonic plutons (Ayalew, 1997; Ayalew and Johnson, 2002; Bowden et al., 2019; Verner et al., 2021).

To understand the key role of the BSZ in shaping the tectonic setting of the Neoproterozoic WES in its later deformational stage, several structural measurements in the mylonitic rocks of the Birbir domain and the high-grade gneissic rocks of Geba and Baro domains, as well as mafic to felsic dykes were analysed and interpreted along with the petrographic description and microstructural interpretation. In the Geba and Baro domains, the gneissic rocks, metagranitic and metagabbroic rocks are dominated by K-feldspar, plagioclase, quartz, biotite and amphibole. Significant dynamic recrystallization of quartz in these rocks is recorded dominantly by grain boundary migration and sub-gran rotation, rarely by bulging. In garnet-bearing hornblende, biotite paragneiss, garnet has been partly replaced by epidote and biotite. Mylonitic amphibolite and biotite paragneiss rocks of the BSZ are fine-grained, with several porphyroclasts of amphibole and feldspar, respectively, which are often fully or partially replaced by epidote. The amphibole porphyroclasts are rotated, and their tail-stepping direction shows a dextral sense of shearing. The breakdown of amphibole to epidote and chlorite possibly suggests greenschist to lower amphibolite retrograde metamorphism by fluid activity resulted in the Qtz + Fsp + Bt + Ep + Amp + Chl assemblage. Within the Birbir domain, mylonites of biotite paragneiss and garnet-bearing chlorite-rich orthogneiss show prominent shear banding fabrics, rotated and boudinage porphyroclasts of feldspar and garnet, and highly stretched quartz. The fine-grained matrix is dominated by biotite, feldspar and recrystallized quartz. In the mylonitic biotite paragneiss, the orientation of deflected mylonitic foliations and tails of sigmoidal feldspar porphyroclasts shows sinistral kinematics. The mineral assemblage of biotite paragneiss is Pl + Qtz + Mus + Bt, while for garnet-bearing chlorite-rich orthogneiss it is Fsp + Qtz + Chl + Grt + Bt. The early structural elements developed during the D1 deformational phase include the E–W- and NE–SW-striking, flat-lying gneissic foliations (S1). Relicts of this foliation are often preserved in the gneissic and migmatitic units of the Geba and Baro domains, while it is rare in the Birbir. Openly folded S1 foliations were observed in the eastern part of the Geba domain on garnet-bearing biotite gneiss with a fold axis (F2) plunging shallowly to the NNE parallel to L2 lineations.

The axial planes of these folds are oriented into NNE and NNW dipping to the west, subparallel to S2 foliation. A regional S2, ~N–S trending foliations defined by systematically oriented planar fabrics of

compositional banding, axial planes of the F2 folding and planes defined by preferred orientation of aggregate minerals, are widespread all over the WES. All these observed structural patterns collectively provide evidence for E–W-directed compression during the D2 deformational phase. Linear features (L2) usually plunge gently to the north or south, however some lineations at the boundary between the Baro and Birbir domains are gently plunging to the east. The mylonitic foliations in the Birbir shear zone are trending N–S, dipping steeply to the west and east, and separated by less strained rocks, suggesting strain partition during the prolonged E–W convergence during D3 deformation. Linear features (L3) defined by stretched minerals are steeply to gently plunging to the north and south. In the mylonitic orthogneiss of the Birbir domain, ~N–S trending steeply west-dipping C-planes are conjugated by NE–SW trending steeply southeast-dipping S-planes.

An early deformed mafic dyke and rotated amphibole porphyroclasts in the BSZ, happened to perceive a dextral kinematic sense. However, observations of rotated augen feldspars in biotite gneiss, S/C and shear band fabrics, significant displacement of the later, less deformed dykes, which cut the mylonitic foliations, and asymmetrically folded mylonitic foliation indicate that the BSZ underwent a later sinistral sense of movement. Therefore, it can be suggested that, upon progressive shearing during the D3 deformational event, the BSZ underwent first dextral and later on sinistral sense of movements. Moreover, linear features gently plunging to the east at the eastern boundary of Baro with the Birbir domain suggest westerly-directed tectonic transport of the Birbir domain.

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The largest fossil of the segmented spider *Parvithele muelleri* Wunderlich, 2017 (Mesothele: Parvithelidae) from Cretaceous Burmese amber

DORIS FOXOVÁ¹, JASON A. DUNLOP²

1 – Institute of Geology and Palaeontology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czechia; foxovad@natur.cuni.cz

2 – Leibniz Institute for Evolution and Biodiversity Science, Museum für Naturkunde; Berlin, Germany

Mesothelae represent the most basal lineage of extant spiders, frequently described as “living fossils” due to their plesiomorphic morphology and deep evolutionary roots extending to the Late Carboniferous (Selden et al., 2013). However, molecular evidence suggests that the diversification of their only surviving family, Liphistiidae, occurred relatively recently during the Palaeogene (Xu et al., 2015), highlighting the importance of the fossil record for understanding early mesothele evolution.

The described specimen (Fig. 1) of *Parvithele muelleri* Wunderlich, 2017 (Araneae: Mesothelae) from mid-Cretaceous (ca. 99 Ma) accords with the holotype of *P. muelleri* in size and morphology, representing the largest mesothele currently known from Burmese amber. It was examined using stereomicroscopy under incident and transmitted light. Photographs were produced by stacking multiple focal planes, supplemented by *camera lucida* drawings refined digitally. The pedipalps are particularly well preserved and display three prominent retrolateral tibial macrospines, resembling four macrospines found in the extant genus *Liphistius*, although a distinct tibial apophysis, typical of modern liphistiines (Schwendinger et al., 2022), is absent. The presence of tibial macrospines suggests either retention of a plesiomorphic character state or a more complex pattern of character loss and modification within crown-group Mesothelae. The morphology of the cymbium and paracymbium further demonstrates that relatively elaborate male palpal structures had already evolved by the mid-Cretaceous.

The opisthosoma is distinctly segmented and terminates in a conspicuous anal tubercle, considerably larger than in extant spiders and possibly representing a vestigial remnant of the ancestral pygidium. Its morphology, including slight constrictions suggestive of segmentation, supports the hypothesis that Cretaceous mesotheles represent an intermediate evolutionary grade following the loss of a flagelliform tail, as seen in chimerarachnids (Wang et al., 2018) with little knowledge of their stem group and few insights into the sequence of character acquisition during spider evolution. Here, we describe *Chimerarachne yingi* gen. et sp. nov., a remarkable arachnid from the mid-Cretaceous (approximately 100 million years ago). Spinnerets are positioned relatively posteriorly. However, given documented ontogenetic and intraspecific variability in living mesotheles, spinneret position is interpreted cautiously as a taxonomic character (Huber & Haug, 2021) or if developmental studies are pursued, especially in Euarthropoda, they focus on embryonic development. Araneae (spiders).

In conclusion, the specimen supports the assignment of *P. muelleri* to the extinct family Parvithelidae and provides significant insights into mesothele evolution. It demonstrates that complex male palpal structures and liphistiid-like tibial macrospines were already established at that time. Also, the pronounced anal tubercle documents a morphology not retained in extant taxa. Together, these features help bridge morphological gaps between Carboniferous mesotheles, Cretaceous amber forms, and living representatives, refining our understanding of character evolution and early spider diversification.

Figure 1. MB.A. 6829, *Parvithele muelleri* Wunderlich, 2017, from Cretaceous Burmese amber. **a** Photograph of the dorsal side; **b** Interpretative line drawing of the dorsal side; **c** Photograph of the ventral side; **d** Interpretative line drawing of the ventral side. Abbreviations: als = anterior lateral spinnerets, at = anal tubercle, cx = coxa, et = eye tubercle, msp = median spinnerets, L1-4 = legs, pc = paracymbium, pd = pedipalps, pls = posterior lateral spinnerets, tms = tibial macrospines, 1–5 = numbered tergite plates. Scale bar equals 2 mm.

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Comparison of fluid inclusion thermometry and mineral geothermometry methods applied to sphalerite from the Ostra ore deposit, Romania

BOTOND G. GERECZI¹, VIKTOR BERTRANDSSON ERLANDSSON² & GABRIELLA B. KISS¹

1 – Department of Mineralogy, Eötvös Loránd University; Budapest, Hungary;
gereczibg@student.elte.hu

2 – Montanuniversität Leoben, Chair of Geology and Economic Geology; Leoben, Austria

Although sphalerite is a common mineral in hydrothermal systems, while studying its formation conditions, no research has been conducted on the same sample that includes both fluid inclusion microthermometry and trace element composition based mineral geothermometry. With the present study we contribute to fill this knowledge gap.

The study area is the Ostra ore deposit in the Eastern Carpathians, which is classified as a Paleozoic Kuroko-type volcanogenic massive sulphide deposit. It contains sphalerite, galena, chalcopyrite and barite as main raw materials (Balázs et al., 2025).

In the studied samples, no compositional zonation is visible in sphalerite using SEM-EDS, and SEM-CL does not reveal growth zoning. Only zones containing galena or pyrite solid inclusions can be observed in sphalerite. As only one generation of sphalerite was observed (formed after pyrite, galena, and chalcopyrite, but before barite), measurements represent sphalerite of the same origin. Overall, 88 measurement points were analyzed by LA-ICP-MS from the same samples, that were also used for the fluid inclusion studies. However, only 21 spots did not contain any inclusions based on LA-ICP-MS spectra. The pure sphalerite has anomalously high Cd (max. 6740 ppm), Co (max. 84 ppm), and Ga (max. 973 ppm) contents, while the amounts of Cu (245 ppm (median)), Fe (max. 1.92 wt.%) and Mn (max. 480 ppm) are low, In (max. 0,05 ppm) are strikingly low. However, the Ag (max. 108 ppm) and Ge (max. 76 ppm) contents are as expected (compared to other VMS-type deposits) based on Frenzel et al. (2016). Based on previous studies, we can confirm that high Co content is present if there is a sudden change in physiochemical conditions, such as fS₂ and/or fO₂ (Bertrandsson Erlandsson et al., 2023; Gereczi et al., 2025). High Ga-content, and low Fe and Mn contents are related to low precipitation temperature, while low In-content is related to low Cu content (coupled substitution between Cu and In) (Cook et al., 2009).

As –based on detailed petrography– fluid inclusions were trapped from a homogeneous parent fluid, pressure correction must be applied to homogenisation temperatures (94-136°C) to get the trapping temperatures (i.e., sphalerite formation temperature). This allows the fluid inclusion data to be comparable with mineral chemistry-based temperatures. The estimated trapping temperatures of fluid inclusions in sphalerite vary between 96°C and 148°C. Sphalerite formation temperatures, based on its chemistry are as follows: 174 – 268°C (Zhao et al., 2024), 125 – 211°C [TFA6] (Zhang et al., 2022), 141–217°C (Frenzel et al., 2016), and <138°C (Kullerud, 1953), while the criteria of Keith et al. (2014)'s method are not fulfilled. Overall, none of the used geothermometers show absolutely identical results to the temperatures inferred from fluid inclusion data.

In addition, a temperature increase during the formation of sphalerite can be reconstructed based on fluid inclusions and geothermometers as well, which continued even after sphalerite formation. Barite formed together with and after sphalerite, and minimum formation temperatures (i.e., homogenisation temperatures) measured in barite (145–193 °C) by Balázs et al. (2025) are higher than those observed in sphalerite. The salinity of the fluid inclusions hosted in sphalerite is between 3.87 and 4.80 wt.% NaCl eq. (Bodnar, 1993; Bakker, 2018), reflecting an evolved seawater origin for the hydrothermal fluid. Inclusions in barite shows slightly higher salinities (5.26–7.59 wt.% NaCl eq.; Balázs et al., 2025), indicating the continuous development of the hydrothermal system.

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Fabric pattern and gravity modelling of the Weinsberg Composite Pluton (Bohemian Massif): Implications for late Variscan magmatic and tectonic processes

TADEÁŠ HÁJEK^{1,2}, KRYŠTOF VERNER^{1,2}, DAVID BURIÁNEK^{2,3}, FRIDRICH FINGER⁴,
JAN VALENTA^{5,6}, LETA MEGERSSA² & DAVID SCHILLER⁷

1 – *Institute of Petrology and Structural Geology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; tadeas.hajek@natur.cuni.cz*

2 – *Czech Geology Survey; Prague, Czech Republic*

3 – *Department of Geological Sciences, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University; Brno, Czech Republic*

4 – *Department of Geography and Geology, University of Salzburg; Salzburg, Austria*

5 – *The Institute of Rock Structure and Mechanics of the Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic; Prague, Czech Republic*

6 – *Institute of Hydrogeology, Engineering Geology and Applied Geology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic*

7 – *Department of Chemistry and Physics of Materials, University of Salzburg; Salzburg, Austria*

A structural, petrological, and geophysical analysis of the Weinsberg Composite Pluton (WCP) provides insights into magma emplacement mechanisms in the context of post-collisional plutonism in the Moldanubian Zone. According to new P-T modelling and published geochronological data, the crystallization of the studied granitoids occurred in several stages during changing regional stress conditions. A transition from regional N–S compression, dominant during 335–325 Ma, to regional NW–SE transtension during ~325–300 Ma is evident in the fabric patterns and structural relationships observed within the WCP. The younger regional stress fields significantly affected the final emplacement and cooling stages, with magma intrusions occurring at progressively shallower depths, leading to a complex structural overprint in the pluton.

Moreover, gravity modelling results based on the Bouguer anomalies and calculated Linsler indications provide an image of the pluton's geometry, revealing asymmetrical root segments extending to the depths over 12 km, and underlying structures that reflect the tectonic reconfigurations during the Variscan orogeny. The WCP records incremental emplacement of magmas over ~30 Myr (332–300 Ma). Three major tecto-magmatic stages are identified. (1) An early post-collisional phase (ca. 332–327 Ma) with the emplacement of the oldest Weinsberg-type granitoids (WTG I) along the eastern margin of the pluton. (2) A middle post-collisional phase (~326–318 Ma), which is characterized by the emplacement of the most voluminous and wide-spread WTG II subvariant in the central parts of the WCP and also the emplacement of the youngest WTG III subvariant (~320 Ma) into an already partially crystalline granitic mush. (3) In the late post-collisional stage (~317–300 Ma), numerous smaller intrusions, including the Mauthausen granite (~318 Ma) and the Freistadt granodiorite (~302 Ma), were emplaced into already solidified WTG units.

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Stress- and saturation-dependent permeability from core to logs

HADEER HASSAN¹, MOATAZ ABDELRAHMAN^{1,2},
NORBERT SZABÓ¹ & MIHALY DOBROKA¹

1 – Department of Geophysics, Institute of Exploration Geosciences, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Sciences and Engineering, University of Miskolc; Miskolc, Hungary; hm.geophysicist@gmail.com

2 – Department of Geophysics, Ain Shams University; Cairo, Egypt

Introduction

Permeability is an important parameter that affects the quality and fluid flow in the reservoir. However, there are some limitations with the estimates obtained from well logs, such as the absence of effective stress and fluid saturation. Although core analysis clarifies stress-dependent permeability behavior, transferring this relationship from the core scale to the well log scale is challenging. The research discusses an uncertainty-aware core-to-log transfer workflow that includes stress-dependent and fluid saturation-dependent permeability behavior from core analysis to well log estimates, with case study results from the Hosszúpályi field in Hungary.

Methodology

The workflow has two coupled stages. (1) Core laboratory stage: repeated dry (water saturation $S_w = 0$) permeability measurements at discrete pressures P_i are used to compute mean permeability \bar{k}_i and repeatability scatter s_i . A robust mixed error model combining an absolute noise floor and a proportional component is adopted and transferred to wet ($S_w > 0$) single-shot curves to enable statistically consistent weighting (Equation 1).

$$\sigma_k(k) = \sqrt{\sigma_{abs}^2 + (\sigma_{rel}k)^2}, \quad (1)$$

Permeability–pressure curves are inverted for each saturation level using a Weighted Least Squares (WLSQ) method (Levenberg, 1944; Marquardt, 1963) to estimate $m = [k_0, \Delta k_0, \lambda]^T$. A soft prior is applied to stabilize the parameter λ between successive saturation steps (Equation 2).

$$k = k_0 - \Delta k(1 - e^{-\lambda(1-S_w)\sigma}), \quad (2)$$

(2) Well logging stage: Shale volume is calculated from gamma ray logs using the Larionov formula (Larionov, 1969). Pore pressure is calculated from sonic logs using Eaton's method with shale-defined normal compaction trend (Eaton, 1975), and effective stress is calculated using the Biot relation. Water saturation is calculated using Archie's law for clean zones (Archie, 1942) and a shale resistivity model for shaly zones (Poupon & Leveaux, 1971).

Results

For both samples, the stress-sensitivity parameter λ remains stable around 0.08, with uncertainties ranging between ± 0.002 and ± 0.042 . For the 20HP-79-2 sample, the relative data misfit remains low (0.17–0.37%), indicating very good agreement between measured and modelled permeability. The 20HP-73-3 sample shows higher experimental scatter, reflected in larger measurement noise levels ($\sigma_{abs} \approx 0.144$ mD, $\sigma_{rel} \approx 2.7\%$) compared with the higher-permeability sample ($\sigma_{abs} \approx 0.122$ mD, $\sigma_{rel} \approx 0.37\%$) (Figure 2). Pore pressure estimated from sonic logs using Eaton's method is complemented by drilling indicators (IDR and ROP–WOB) to obtain a conservative pore-pressure profile for effective-stress calculation and calculate a continuous permeability log (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Laboratory permeability–pressure data with uncertainty intervals.

Conclusions

The measurement uncertainties from repeated dry experiments have been used to constrain the inversion, and these have been transferred to the wet saturation curves. The stress sensitivity parameter λ remains consistent over saturation states, suggesting that the dominant stress-controlled permeability behavior has been correctly modeled for the reservoir rocks. The pore pressures, determined from sonic logs and supported by drilling indicators such as IDR and ROP-WOB, offer a robust basis for calculation of effective stress and extension of the calibrated model to well logs. The continuous permeability log identifies clean sands in the shallow interval, becoming shaly with increases in shale intercalations at depth.

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Methane and carbon dioxide emissions from subsurface evidenced by field measurements and remote sensing: Case study in southern Moravia

POLINA IAKUNINA^{1,3}, OLGA BROVKINA², JAN HANUŠ² & JURAJ FRANCU³

1 – Department of Geological Sciences, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University; Brno, Czech Republic; polina.iakunina@geology.cz

2 – Global Change Research Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences; Brno, Czech Republic

3 – Geoenergy department, Czech Geological Survey; Brno, Czech Republic

Introduction

Driven by the greenhouse effect, global warming became accelerated during the last 150 years of the past 1,500 years. Current data show that temperatures are now higher than most of the Holocene time period. Observed warming is human-caused, with warming from greenhouse gases (Marcott et al., 2013). In this study, we utilized both field measurements of methane flux and remote sensing (RS) airborne methods to detect methane emissions in the vicinity of Milotice and Vacenovice in the South Moravian region of the Czech Republic. Field measurements were used for detecting point sources, whereas RS was applied to scan wider area. About 191 oil and gas production wells were drilled between 1940 and 1960 in the selected area. Some of these wells are probably not sufficiently tight and soil gas shows elevated values in these sites.

Materials and Methods

Soil gas composition (CH₄, CO₂, and O₂) was measured using portable Ecoprobe-5 equipment in a nine-point grid of 80 cm deep holes. Methane and carbon dioxide flux was evaluated using a chamber method at selected points within the grid (Fig.1). Linear part of the increase of gas content in the chamber is used to calculate gas flux from soil to atmosphere. Airborne hyperspectral data were acquired on September 22, 2025, using the SASI sensor (ITRES, Canada). The dataset consisted of 100 spectral bands with a bandwidth of 15 nm, covering the spectral range from 957.5 nm to 2,442.5 nm, and a spatial resolution of 3x3 m. Radiometric, geometric, and atmospheric corrections were performed. Methane detection employed the band ratio method to highlight gas absorption properties. Using the Raster Calculator, a methane index was defined as the ratio of radiance in the 2,307 nm band (strong absorption) to the 2,112 nm band (negligible absorption by methane).

Results

Within the measured grid, the soil gas contains 6.6-58%vol CH₄ and 2.5-32%vol CO₂. Lower methane content in soil gas directly above the wellhead (46%vol) indicate that probably a concrete panel diverts escaping gas by approx. 2 m. At the experimental site (abandoned production well VA-178), the methane flux over a 20 m² area was calculated between 1.38 and 162.4 mol/m²/d. Estimation of the total annual emissions would assume constant meteorological conditions. While field measurements provide information on the spatial distribution of methane and carbon dioxide concentrations and fluxes, the processed airborne data did not reveal the described point source. This suggests that the emission source at this locality is below the detection limit (sensitivity) of the airborne sensor. However, the airborne data detected a small methane plume consisting of 27 pixels of 3x3 m size located at 100 m from the closest abandoned well counter wind direction. A methane plume was detected near a marsh, which could also be a source of methane. Additionally, wind direction and speed can fluctuate over open terrain during airborne measurements. It remains possible that a shift in wind direction occurred at the exact moment of data acquisition, moving the plume from the abandoned well toward the marsh area.

Conclusions

Combining field and remote sensing methods improves greenhouse gas detection. While hyperspectral imaging covers broad areas, it is limited by pixel size and methane detection limits (LOD, which varies from 50 to 200 ppm·m depending on background characteristics and wind conditions). Future sensitivity testing should include lower-altitude flights under stable conditions, supported by ground measurements.

Figure 1. Map of studied area with topography, oil and gas wells, field measurement grid (yellow square) and airborne scanned area for methane (blue dashed line).

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Integration of petrography and whole-rock geochemistry to characterize hydrothermal alteration of porphyry Cu-Au system Jebel Ohier, Red Sea Hills, Northeast Sudan

BADRELDIN IBRAHIM¹, FERENC MÓRICZ² & FERENC MOLNÁR¹

1 – Department of Mineralogy, Institute of Geography and Earth Sciences, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Eötvös Loránd University; Budapest, Hungary; Mohammed05@student.elte.hu

2 – Department of Applied Mineralogy, Institute of Mineral Exploration, University of Miskolc; Miskolc, Hungary

Alteration mapping of hydrothermal systems is vital for understanding metal distribution and fluid evolution in porphyry Cu-Au systems. The classic models admit systematic description of vertical and lateral alteration zonation (Lowell and Guilbert, 1970; Sillitoe, 2010), still the mineralogical complexity of these systems requires integrated approaches combining mineralogical and geochemical datasets to constrain and reveal its reliability.

This research applies an integrated petrographic and whole-rock XRF geochemical workflow to characterize alteration patterns in a newly discovered porphyry Cu-Au deposit in Red Sea Hills Sudan. Thin-section petrography provides direct evidence of mineralogical composition but are specially limited, while whole-rock geochemistry offers more coverage but still requires validation. XRF data are evaluated using ioGAS Program in the context of alteration indices (Ishikawa et al., 1976; Large et al., 2001), molar-ratio diagrams (Cooke et al., 2014), and the porphyry copper alteration plot of Large (2025).

The geology of the study area is described in detail by Bierlein et al. (2016). The Jebel Ohier Porphyry Complex forms a part of the Gebeit terrane with arc magmatism of 720–830 Ma in the Arabian-Nubian shield. The ore system comprises volcanic and intrusive rock units, which compositionally ranges from gabbroic to granodioritic-dacitic units. The mineralized zones occur in thick massive and laminated dacitic units intruded by granodiorite with a feldspar-hornblende porphyritic texture, as well as a series of post-mineralization intermediate to mafic intrusive plugs, stocks and dykes, emplaced within the dacite and granodiorite.

Results of our studies of a representative sample set from the outcrops and shallow drill cores from the Jebel Ohier complex show that the geochemical characteristics of hydrothermal alteration correspond well to petrographic observations and the propylitic-chloritic, sodic-calcic, sericite-chlorite and argillic/advanced argillic classes of major alteration types in a porphyry system (Chang et al., 2011; Large et al., 2025) can be recognized (Fig. 1). However, the high concentrations (> 1 wt%) of copper are mostly connected to the argillic/advanced argillic and sericite (illite) alteration zones where the presence of malachite, atacamite, covellite and bornite secondary copper minerals was also detected. This relationship indicates that secondary enrichment processes associated with argillic alteration are responsible for formation of high-grade copper ores, whereas the preserved propylitic-sericitic and sodic-calcic alteration zones are characterized by Cu concentrations less than 1 wt%, which is typical for primary ores in porphyry copper systems.

Figure 1. Geochemical classification of alteration in rock samples from the Jebel Ohier porphyry copper system. The figure (A and B) shows the fields of major hydrothermal alteration classes of porphyry system with the corresponding Cu concentration. Molar ratios were calculated and Cu concentrations were obtained from the whole rock XRF data. Fields of types of alteration are delineated according to Large (2025).

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Non-destructive Raman identification of garnet in a historical artwork: A portable Pietra Dura altar depicting Saint Margaret of Antioch

ŠTĚPÁN JAROMĚŘSKÝ¹, RICHARD PŘIKRYL¹, ADAM CULKA¹ & FILIP KOŠEK¹

1 – Institute of Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Mineral Resources, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Albertov 6, 128 43, Prague, Czech Republic (stepan.jaromersky@natur.cuni.cz)

The Pietra Dura technique represents a highly sophisticated form of stone inlay that reached an exceptional artistic and technological level in early modern Florence (Giusti 2006). Garnet, during the same period, ranked among the most frequently used materials in jewellery and decorative arts due to its intense coloration and favourable optical properties. The precise mineralogical identification of garnets mounted in historical artefacts has progressively advanced in recent decades, and thanks to modern analytical technologies and previously published research (e.g., Jehlička et al. 2016), these approaches can now be applied to artworks that have not yet been systematically investigated.

The studied object, a portable altar dated to 1603 and currently preserved in the Lobkowitz Collections at Prague Castle, represents one of the surviving works of the prominent Prague workshop led by the Castrucci family. The artefact was executed in the Pietra Dura technique, based on the precise cutting and subsequent assembly of coloured natural stones into a compact mosaic composition. Surrounding the central mosaic depicting Saint Margaret of Antioch are red gemstones, step-cut in square shapes and set in metal mounts.

Garnet forms an isomorphous mineral group characterized by significant chemical variability (Grew et al. 2013). In historical decorative applications, almandine (Fe), pyrope (Mg), and grossular (Ca) components are most commonly represented (Jehlička et al. 2016; Tzankova et al. 2024). Over the past decades, Raman spectroscopy has become established as an effective non-destructive tool for distinguishing end-members of the garnet group (Mingsheng et al. 1994; Kolesov and Geiger 1998; Bersani et al. 2009). However, the majority of previous studies have relied on laboratory measurements of isolated samples, whereas the systematic application of portable Raman instrumentation for in situ analysis of mounted gemstones within a specific composite artwork has not yet been comprehensively evaluated.

The aim of the ongoing research is to confirm the presence of garnets (as opposed to glass imitations or other minerals) as well as to attempt to more precisely distinguish among the garnet species on the surface of historical Pietra Dura artworks. Study includes the assessment of reliability and limitations of portable Raman spectroscopy, in this case Inspector Raman, DeltaNu, 785 nm excitation fixed on a tripod mount enabling non-destructive and even contactless analyses. Measurements are conducted without sampling and without mechanical intervention into the structure of the object. The acquired spectra are compared with reference standards, spectral databases, and authors' archive spectral data.

Preliminary results indicate the presence of garnet; however, to achieve improved spectral quality and a more robust compositional interpretation, additional measurements with extended acquisition times and a higher number of analysed mounted gemstones will be conducted in the near future.

This study contributes to the methodological framework of non-invasive mineralogical analysis in cultural heritage research and evaluates the practical integration of portable Raman spectroscopy into conservation diagnostics. The results may further support research into material provenance, raw material sources, and technological practices of early modern workshops.

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Clastic infills of gas vesicles in basaltic trachyandesites from Regulice near Cracow

TYMON KALBARCZYK¹

1 – Faculty of Geology, Geophysics and Environmental Protection, AGH University of Cracow; Cracow, Poland; tkalbarczyk@student.agh.edu.pl

The occurrence of basaltic trachyandesite lava flows in Regulice is related to segments of the Kraków-Lubliniec Fault Zone (Słaby et al., 2010), which were subjected to alternating transpression, transtension, and subhorizontal extension from the Late Carboniferous to the Early Permian (Żaba, 1996; Żaba, 1999). This variable tectonic regime was accompanied by intensive bimodal mafic-intermediate and felsic magmatism (Słaby et al., 2010). Mafic-intermediate rocks are represented mainly by trachybasalts and trachyandesites known from numerous outcrops in the area (Płonczyński et al., 1988; Płonczyński et al., 1993), many of which were quarried.

One of such outcrops is located in Regulice, where trachyandesites were quarried in Czarna Góra area in a group of three quarries. The best preserved exposure occurs in North-Western quarry, where, without the need for extensive digging, three individual 'a'a' lava flows, previously described in literature, can still be distinguished (Kozłowski, 1955; Lewandowska et al., 2010). In the Regulice quarries, the lava flows are separated by volcanic breccia composed of basaltic trachyandesite blocks and fine clastic material (interpreted as pyroclastic) of felsic composition, containing visible light mica and quartz and forming the matrix of the breccia.

The origin of this clastic material remains debated; however, the prevailing interpretation assumes that it formed as a result of subaerial fallout of felsic tephra from an unidentified source with an admixture of reworked tephra and clastic material derived from Carboniferous arkoses (Chocyk, 1990; Lewandowska et al., 2010). Many studies have also indicated that this material penetrated fractures and voids in the underlying lava flow (e. g., Chocyk, 1990; Lewandowska et al., 2010), suggesting that the fallout of felsic tephra occurred shortly after emplacement of the lava flow. The petrography of the clastic matrix of the volcanic breccia has been relatively well recognized (e.g., Chocyk, 1990; Lewandowska et al., 2010), as have some structures associated with void infills in the underlying lava flow (Lewandowska et al., 2010). However, several structural features still require closer characterization and broader discussion.

Analysis of *in situ* outcrops and thin-section observations made it possible to identify a number of structural features which, to the best of the author's knowledge, have not yet been described in detail. These include: (1) zones of gas vesicles filled with clastic material extending for tens of centimetres away from feeder structures; (2) laminae parallel to the walls of larger vesicles, indicating a multi-stage infill history, locally torn during subsequent infilling episodes; (3) local mineralization by quartz, calcite and chalcedony within the clastic infills; and (4) zones of altered matrix colour, potentially related to redox processes (eg., reduction of Fe(III) to Fe(II)).

The results of microscopic observations, X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis and SEM-EDS investigations were compared with literature data, which made it possible to place the recognized structures in a broader petrographic and genetic context. In addition, a comparison was made with similar structures from other areas worldwide. The final part of the study proposes transport mechanisms that could account for the formation of such fine-grained infills and outlines directions for further research.

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Factor-analysis-assisted hyperparameter inversion for enhancement of well-log interpretation efficiency

AHMED OSAMA KAMAL^{1,2} & NORBERT PÉTER SZABÓ¹

1 – Department of Geophysics, Institute of Exploration Geosciences, Faculty of Earth and Environmental Sciences and Engineering, University of Miskolc; Miskolc, Hungary; ahmedosama@sci.asu.edu.eg

2 – Department of Geophysics, Faculty of Science, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt

Introduction

Well-log interpretation is central to formation evaluation, converting downhole measurements into petrophysical properties via a physics-based inverse problem that calibrates a forward model to observed log responses (Mayer and Sibbit, 1980). Bayesian approaches improve uncertainty handling and incorporate prior geology. However, conventional depth-by-depth local inversion may exhibit limited accuracy and reliability, particularly in noisy and heterogeneous formations, which can degrade the stability and consistency of estimated porosity, water saturation, and shale volume (Deng et al., 2023; Pan et al., 2023). To improve robustness, workflows increasingly combine inversion with machine learning; unsupervised methods provide compact representations that support quality control and constraint design (Dobróka et al., 2016; Kohonen, 2012). Building on the reported link between shale volume and the first factor (Szabó, 2011), this study compares local damped least-squares inversion with a factor-analysis-assisted hyperparameter strategy: shale volume is constrained globally using a linear relation to the dominant factor score, while the remaining parameters are updated locally, extending prior zone-level hyperparameter work (Szabó, 2024).

Method

In the conventional strategy, all petrophysical parameters, porosity (ϕ), water saturation (S_w), shale volume (V_{sh}), and flushed zone saturation (S_{xo}) are updated locally (depth-by-depth) using a Levenberg-Marquardt damped least-squares step based on Jacobian sensitivities. In the proposed strategy, standardized logs follow a one-factor model, and the first factor score, F_1 , is computed from maximum-likelihood factor analysis.

$$\hat{\mathbf{f}} = (\mathbf{\Lambda}^T \mathbf{\Psi}^{-1} \mathbf{\Lambda})^{-1} \mathbf{\Lambda}^T \mathbf{\Psi}^{-1} \mathbf{z}, \quad F_1 = \hat{f}^{(1)}$$

Instead of estimating V_{sh} independently at each depth, we impose a global constraint where α and β are hyperparameters shared across the interval.

$$V_{sh} = \alpha F_1 + \beta, \quad (2)$$

Estimation uses an alternating outer-inner scheme: the outer loop updates α , β by minimizing misfit subject to the constraint, while the inner loop updates ϕ , S_w , and S_{xo} locally with damped least squares. The proposed approach does not estimate only shale volume; instead, it constrains V_{sh} globally through F_1 , while ϕ , S_w , and S_{xo} are updated locally at each depth. Uncertainty is quantified by linearized covariance analysis using final sensitivity matrices and an effective noise level inferred from normalized residuals.

Results

Both inversion methods were run on the same single-well, multi-log dataset comprising neutron porosity (NPHI), sonic transit time (ΔT), gamma-ray (GR), potassium (K), deep resistivity (R_d), and bulk density (RHOB) logs over a sandy–shaly reservoir interval. In the factor-analysis-assisted hyperparameter inversion, shale volume is linked to the first factor score, with α and β treated as depth-invariant hyperparameters. A one-factor model captured the dominant inter-log covariance, and F_1 exhibited

a strong linear relationship with the initial shale indicator, supporting its use as a lithology proxy. The F_1 loadings were 0.96 (NPHI), -0.54 (ΔT), 0.99 (GR), 0.95 (K), -0.88 (R_d), and 0.97 (RHOB). The alternating outer–inner optimization converged quickly and produced stable hyperparameter estimates of $\alpha = 0.1799 \pm 0.0014$ (0.76% error) and $\beta = 0.2716 \pm 0.0012$ (0.44% error). The resulting petrophysical profiles match the measured logs closely, reduce the number of parameters updated locally, and remain physically consistent. Log uncertainty is modeled as depth-independent, Gaussian noise with constant standard deviations per log, yielding a diagonal data covariance matrix $\mathbf{C}_d = \text{diag}(\sigma_j^2)$. The $\pm 1\sigma$ envelopes indicate that the global hyperparameters are tightly constrained and that the imposed structure reduces the porosity–saturation trade-off in intervals where log sensitivities overlap. Following (Menke, 1984), uncertainties are computed from the sensitivity matrix \mathbf{J} and \mathbf{C}_d , by forming the model covariance \mathbf{C}_m . Validation was performed using data misfit and parameter uncertainty metrics; core measurements were not available.

Conclusions

We compared a conventional local (depth-by-depth) inversion with a factor-analysis-assisted hyperparameter inversion on the same multi-log dataset. In the hyperparameter approach, shale volume is constrained by a global, factor-controlled relationship (Eq. 2), adding geologically meaningful structure while maintaining an excellent fit to the measured logs. The inferred hyperparameters α and β were stable, indicating that the dominant factor score is a dependable proxy for shale content and produces a coherent, depth-consistent shale trend. By decreasing the number of parameters updated locally at each depth, the factor-assisted method reduces non-uniqueness and alleviates the porosity–saturation trade-off, yielding physically consistent estimates that honor both log responses and lithological trends. Overall, introducing low-dimensional latent structure through factor analysis provides a compact, interpretable, and robust framework for well-log interpretation.

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Quantitative assessment of geodiversity in Ethiopia using grid-based analysis

ABDO WUDAD KEMAL^{1,2} & MÁRTON PÁL²

1 – Doctoral School of Earth Sciences, Faculty of Science, ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Pázmány P. sétány 1/C, H-1117 Budapest, Hungary; awudad@student.elte.hu

2 – Geodiversity & Geoheritage Research Group, Institute of Cartography and Geoinformatics, Faculty of Informatics, ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Pázmány P. sétány 1/A, H-1117 Budapest, Hungary

Geodiversity is the natural variability of geological, geomorphological, pedological, and other abiotic characteristics of the landscape. While geodiversity plays a crucial role in sustainable land-use planning and geoconservation, quantitative assessment of geodiversity remains limited (Rong et al., 2022). The aims of quantitative evaluations depend on their scale: at small scales, we can identify patterns and areas to examine for geoheritage and find hotspots, while at large scales, we can locate geosites within well-defined geodiversity contexts. We present the first nationwide, standardised, grid-based quantitative geodiversity assessment for Ethiopia, integrating various abiotic characteristics into a single framework.

Geodiversity was evaluated within a 20 × 20 km grid using hexagons, the most favourable geometric unit due to neighbourhood and regularity attributes. The grid size was determined by the scale of available data and the assessment's purpose: to provide an overall picture of the country's geodiversity and highlight areas worth deeper analysis. Five abiotic factors, geology, pedology, geomorphology, palaeontology, and mineral occurrences, were assessed using GeodiversityCalculator v2.1 in QGIS. Geological and soil data were analysed using a variety of indices with unique attributes for each grid cell. These two datasets are from the EthioGIS (2018) and NSIS (2024). Geomorphological diversity (landform types) was calculated from the MERIT DEM (Yamazaki et al., 2017) using geomorphons. Hydrological diversity includes lakes, seas, and watercourses (Strahler-ordered), also derived from MERIT. Paleobiology (PBDB, n.d.) and mineral occurrence data were collected from international databases (Padilla et al., 2021) and analysed using point-based richness measures. Each thematic dataset was evaluated independently and normalised to mitigate scale differences and ensure equal weighting of subindices (Pál & Albert, 2021).

The initial results for the non-normalised indices showed considerable thematic dominance, with palaeontological information accounting for approximately 89.42% of the highest possible geodiversity, followed by pedology (6.73%), geomorphology (4.81%), geology (2.88%), and minerals (0.96%). On the other hand, the median analysis indicated that geomorphology (50%) and pedology (20%) were the principal contributors, whereas palaeontology and minerals had zero median contributions, suggesting that these two factors have a limited geographical distribution. Normalisation was then utilised to address these imbalances, resulting in a more equitable distribution of contributions across all subindices.

The range of normalised geodiversity values varied from 0.45 to 3.78, with an average of 2.03. Based on natural breaks, the data were grouped into five classes: very low (0.45–1.35), low (1.36–1.84), medium (1.85–2.13), high (2.14–2.46), and very high (2.47–3.78). The medium geodiversity class covered the largest area (34.74%), followed by high geodiversity (29.37%), low (16.17%), very low (10.30%), and very high (9.42%), indicating that Ethiopia has moderate to high geodiversity. The results of the geodiversity analysis revealed significant variation in geodiversity across Ethiopia. High geodiversity is found mainly in the northern, northeastern, and central parts of the country. The high geodiversity in this area is mainly attributed to the complex topography, varied soils, and diverse geological features. On the other hand, regions with low geodiversity are found mainly in the eastern, western, and northwestern lowlands of Ethiopia. This is because relatively flat and uniform topography, with less variation in geological and soil features (Fig. 1). By providing the first nationwide spatial assessment of geodiversity in Ethiopia, this study enables further regional analyses for geoconservation and land-use planning.

Figure 1. Non-normalised (f) and normalised (f') geodiversity maps of Ethiopia (authors, 2026).

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Geochronology and geochemistry of Variscan granitoids of the Fatric basement with Alpine tectono-metamorphic overprint (Inner Western Carpathians)

CHRISFANEL EURODE KIANGUEBENE-KOUSSINGOUNINA¹, MARTIN ONDREJKA¹,
MARIÁN PUTIŠ¹, ONDREJ NEMEC¹, PETER RUŽIČKA¹, DAVID CHEW² & JIŘÍ SLAMA³

1 – Department of Mineralogy, Petrology, and Economic Geology, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Comenius University; Bratislava, Slovakia; koussingounina1@uniba.sk

2 – Department of Geology, School of Natural Sciences, Trinity College Dublin; Dublin, Ireland

3 – Institute of Geology of the Czech Academy of Sciences; Prague, Czech Republic

The Western Carpathians host large Variscan granitoid bodies within the pre-Alpine crystalline basement (Broska and Uher, 2001; Plašienka et al., 1997). U–Pb zircon and apatite dating detected inherited zircon from an Early Ordovician (~480 Ma) protolith, while Late Devonian–Early Carboniferous zircon and apatite magmatic ages of ~364–343 Ma were determined in investigated granitoids. These granitic rocks include leucogranites, granites, granodiorites-tonalites suites, along with associated mylonites and blastomylonites. They are silica-rich, peraluminous (A/CNK=1–1.8; A/NK=1.2–1.9), mainly ferroan, and belong to calc-alkaline to high-K calc-alkaline series. These rocks exhibit I and S-type affinities, typical of magmatic arc and post-collisional settings. Major oxides and some of the trace elements (Sr, Ba, Zr, and Eu) decrease with increasing SiO₂, reflecting fractional crystallization of feldspar, zircon, biotite, muscovite, titanite, and apatite. Chondrite-normalized REE patterns show enrichment in LREE, depletion in HREE, HFSE, and pronounced negative Eu anomalies, consistent with feldspar fractionation and subduction-related arc magmatism. Whole-rock initial ⁸⁷Sr/⁸⁶Sr ratios of 0.706035–0.766529 and εNd₍₃₅₀₎ of 0.05 to -4.89 reflect the effects of post-magmatic disturbances of the isotopic system due to the superimposed processes such as alteration, hydrothermal fluids, and metamorphism. These isotopic characteristics indicate a dominant crustal source with variable mantle input, affected by open-system behavior during deformation. Variscan granitoids still locally preserve primary magmatic textures, including quartz, plagioclase, K-feldspar, Ti-rich biotite, and muscovite. The primary Variscan accessory assemblages include magmatic zircon, monazite-(Ce), titanite, apatite, and xenotime. These granitic rocks experienced Alpine tectono-metamorphic overprint mainly under greenschist-facies conditions (330–410°C, 350–500 MPa), based on Perple_X and GeoPS thermodynamic modelling, constrained by Ar–Ar phengite ages to ~100–80 Ma. This overprint relates to the closure of the Fatric Jurassic–Early Cretaceous Zliechov Basin, followed by the underthrusting of the thinned Fatric basement beneath the Veporic thrust sheet, while the detached Fatric Mesozoic cover nappes overlain the foreland Tatric Unit (Plašienka et al., 1997; Putiš et al., 2021) the studied area has been affected by at least two orogenic cycles – Variscan and Alpine. Based on structural analyses, it is possible to determine several deformation events. The older deformations (DV. Granitoids show significant microstructural modifications due to mylonitization. Primary magmatic assemblages were partly to completely destabilized under fluid-assisted recrystallization. Monazite-(Ce) experienced retrograde breakdown and was replaced by corona textures of fluorapatite II and allanite-(Ce)–clinozoisite, indicating Ca and fluid involvement influx. Primary allanite-(Ce) is partially replaced by epidote–clinozoisite. Magmatic titanomagnetite is often replaced by late-magmatic ilmenite-magnetite exsolutions during cooling (Fig.1a), while magmatic titanite is replaced by metamorphic rutile and calcite (Fig. 1b). These reactions are typically associated with dynamic recrystallization of quartz, while feldspars are replaced by phengite-rich white mica, albite, and epidote-clinozoisite, indicating syn-tectonic metamorphic re-equilibration (Kianguebene-Koussingounina et al., 2024; Ondrejka et al., 2022; Putiš et al., 2021) formation of titanite, in Carboniferous I-type granites/granitoids from the Tribeč Mountains (Slovakia. These results confirm the reworking of Variscan granitoids of the Fatric basement during the Alpine (Late Cretaceous) tectono-metamorphic event in the Western Carpathians.

Figure 1. BSE images detailing secondary textures. (a) Late magmatic re-equilibration of titanomagnetite to magnetite (Mag) and ilmenite (Ilm) exsolutions and metamorphic rutile (Rt_{me}) sample MAD-1. (b) Breakdown of titanite (Ttn_{ma}) to metamorphic rutile (Rt_{me}) and calcite (Cal), sample PHK-1A.

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Preliminary petrographic and geochemical investigation of realgar mineralization in the Bystre Slice, Polish Carpathians

PIOTR KLECZYŃSKI¹

1 – Polish Geological Institute – National Research Institute, Regional Geology and Mineral Resources Department; Warsaw, Poland; piotr.kleczyński@gmail.com

The Bystre Slice, located in the eastern part of the Polish Carpathians, has long been known for occurrences of realgar and other sulphide minerals (Gruszczyk, 1958; Nieć et al., 2016). Despite this early recognition, the origin and geological context of this mineralization have not been investigated in detail. This study presents the comprehensive petrographic and geochemical research aimed at constraining the genesis and characteristics of realgar mineralization within this area. The main objective of the project was to investigate the origin of realgar mineralization, identifying mineralized horizons, characterizing the style and spatial distribution of mineralization, and estimating the temperature conditions of the hydrothermal fluids responsible for mineral precipitation.

The geological succession of the Bystre Slice comprises flysch formations ranging in age from the Lower Cretaceous to the Oligocene (Jankowski & Ślączka, 2000; Jarmołowicz-Szulc et al., 2024).

Samples were collected from several stratigraphic units and localities within the study area. These include the Lgota Beds exposed in the Drobny Quarry, the Upper Istebna shales and sandstones from the Gruby Quarry, an exposure above the Rabe Stream, a small tributary of the Rabe Stream, and the Oligocene Menilite Beds represented by siltstones and sandstones.

The analytical work included petrographic analysis of sample thin sections and identification of organic matter macerals, fluid inclusion microthermometry, quantitative chemical spot analysis using scanning electron microscopy with energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS-SEM), and phase-composition identification by X-ray diffraction (XRD).

Zones of realgar occurrence have been identified in several horizons characterized by the presence of a network of tectonic fractures. Field observations and XRD and SEM analyses show that the realgar is accompanied by quartz and carbonates. The mineralization occurs in the form of layers, lenses, and impregnations. The realgar mineralization has been interpreted as epigenetic in origin, as realgar infilling open spaces within structures. Fluid inclusions were analysed using a Nikon Linkam freezing-heating stage. The temperature of homogenization for the realgar crystals has been preliminarily estimated to 66.1 °C. Microthermometric analyses were calibrated with Synflinc standards. EDS-SEM analyses indicate that the realgar is composed of nearly pure arsenic sulphide. The calculated structural formula of realgar, based on 4 atoms of S, is $As_{3.88-4.00}S_4$. Additionally, the phosphate mineral goyazite was identified with EDS-SEM as an associated phase – representing probably the first recorded occurrence of this mineral within the studied area as it is not reported by previous studies focusing on the epigenetic mineralization in the area (Jarmołowicz-Szulc et al., 2024).

A comprehensive dataset covering occurrence locations, mineralization characteristics, realgar composition, and homogenization temperatures is essential for possibly advancing future exploration in the Bystre Slice.

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Metastable liquid water on present- and past-day Mars: experimental constraints on grain transport in thin boiling flows under reduced pressure

ONDŘEJ KRÝZA^{1,2}, PETR BROŽ¹, VĚRA PĚNKAVOVÁ³, JAROMÍR HAVLICA³,
MÁRIA ZEDNÍKOVÁ³, ZOE EMERLAND⁴, MATTHEW SYLVEST⁴ & MANISH PATEL^{4,5}

1 – *Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences; Prague, Czechia; kryza@ig.cas.cz*

2 – *Department of Geophysics, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic*

3 – *Institute of Chemical Process Fundamentals of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic*

4 – *School of Physical Science, STEM, The Open University; Milton Keynes, UK*

5 – *Space Science and Technology Department, STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory; Oxford, UK*

Liquid water on present-day and late Amazonian Mars would have been thermodynamically unstable under typical surface pressures of only a few to a few tens of millibars. Any exposed liquid would rapidly undergo simultaneous boiling and freezing, producing a highly transient, metastable flow regime. While previous experimental studies have shown that such conditions can enhance runout, erosion, or even induce sediment levitation for fine grains (Conway et al., 2011; Raack et al., 2017), the effects on the transport capacity for coarser, sand- to fine-gravel-sized particles remain poorly constrained. Yet, the ability of metastable flows to entrain and redistribute these larger grains is central to understanding how short-lived liquid water episodes might contribute to the sedimentary record and morphology of Amazonian Mars.

Here we present a new set of low-pressure experiments that investigate grain transport by metastable, boiling water flows under Mars-like conditions. We use a cylindrical vacuum chamber (chamber “George” at the Open University, UK) to generate thin sheet flows of liquid water (typical thickness ~5 mm) over a flat, inclined tray (1°), at pressures of 1024, ~25 and ~4.5 mbar and near-ambient to low initial water temperatures (~20 - 0.5 °C). Our experimental design deliberately targets thin flows because (i) natural flows are expected to flatten rapidly upon sudden exposure at the surface, especially near effusion sites and at distal flow toes, and (ii) these thin, early stages strongly influence subsequent channelization, erosion and deposition. The chamber geometry (runout distances up to ~0.9 m) further favours the study of thin flows over fully developed, thicker streams.

To isolate the role of the fluid regime, we focus on transport of 2–4 mm calcite grains, representing a coarser sand to fine gravel fraction. This size range has not been systematically tested in earlier Mars-like boiling experiments, which concentrated rather on sub-millimetre grains, but it is critical for evaluating whether metastable flows can mobilize material at the coarser end of Martian sediment populations. The chosen fraction also provides a practical compromise: grains are large and angular enough to form realistic unconsolidated beds, while remaining individually trackable in high-resolution image sequences, enabling both static and dynamic analyses.

We combine three complementary approaches. First, we perform a qualitative and semi-quantitative assessment of entrainment and runout as a function of pressure, water volume and slope. Second, we analyse the final spatial distribution of grains using the Voronoi tessellation, radial and probability density function (RDF and PDF), and agglomerative hierarchical clustering and related metrics (cluster sizes, dominance ratios, Gini coefficients, centroid distances) to characterize how deposit geometry changes with decreasing pressure. This clustering approach is particularly suited to the filamentary lobate structures produced by unstable boiling flows and allows us to distinguish between compact lobes and more dispersed, chain-like deposits. Third, for a subset of experiments with optimal imaging geometry, we apply digital image correlation (DIC) to derive surface velocity fields and flow-parallel grain trajectories, providing direct constraints on the dynamic response of grains to bubble-rich flow.

Our results show that, within the tested pressure window, boiling and vigorous bubble production substantially modify both fluid behaviour and grain transport (Fig. 1). At higher pressures (~1024 mbar), flows remain relatively coherent and can mobilize a significant fraction of the 2–4 mm grains, producing lobes with clear internal clustering but limited fragmentation. As pressure decreases toward ~4.5 mbar, bubble production intensifies, flow fronts become more irregular, and deposits exhibit stronger longitudinal spreading and increased geometric complexity. For the tested coarser grains, the net effect is not a simple monotonic enhancement of transport; instead, we observe a nonlinear response in both transport efficiency and deposit structure corresponding to various pressures - from vigorous boiling to more steady flow near the point of freezing.

Taken together, these experiments demonstrate that metastable, boiling water under present-day Martian pressures can indeed mobilize millimetre-scale grains in thin flows, but that the transport capacity is smaller and highly sensitive to pressure and flow configuration. The observed nonlinear trends imply that extrapolations from fine-grain experiments to coarser sediment are not straightforward. Our findings thus provide new process-level constraints that can be incorporated into models of transient Amazonian flows. They also help to bracket the conditions under which short-lived episodes of liquid water could have contributed to erosion, deposition and the reworking of coarse sediments on Mars and other low-pressure planetary surfaces.

Figure 1. Flow regimes of liquid water under stable and metastable atmospheric conditions, contrasting 1024 mbar (Earth), 25 mbar (past Mars), and 4.5 mbar (present-day Mars). The left panel shows boxplot diagrams illustrating the pressure-dependent decrease in grain transport distance from the initial deposit location along the flow direction, while the right panel depicts the structure of the final grain clouds formed at each pressure.

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Climate-driven sedimentary cycles in paralic setting of the Late Mississippian in the Upper Silesian Basin; an example from the Poruba Member of the Ostrava Formation

MARTIN KUBÍČEK¹, STANISLAV OPLUŠTIL¹ & JIŘÍ LAURIN²

1 – *Institute of Geology and Paleontology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; kubicekma@natur.cuni.cz*

2 – *Institute of Geophysics, Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic; Prague, Czech Republic*

The Upper Mississippian represents a characteristic example of an icehouse climate during the Phanerozoic (Scotese et al., 2021). The Late Mississippian to Early Pennsylvanian interval (c. 330–320 Ma) was marked by significant fluctuations in glacial climate across a wide range of temporal scales (Montañez, 2022). Millennial-scale glaciations, described as C1 and C2, have been documented in glacial sediments from high latitudes of Gondwana (Fielding et al., 2023), whereas shorter-term oscillations within the orbital frequency band have been interpreted from paralic successions (cyclothems) in low-latitude regions (Fielding, 2021). An example of orbitally controlled paralic sedimentation is recorded in the Poruba Member of the Upper Silesian Basin. Recent radioisotopic and cyclostratigraphic data indicate that shallow-marine sedimentation of the Poruba Member occurred within the interval ~325.1–324.2 Ma (Jirásek et al., 2018; Opluštil et al., 2024). The sedimentary succession exhibits evidence of Milankovitch-scale orbital forcing, including obliquity-modulated eccentricity (~173 kyr), obliquity (~35 kyr), and eccentricity expressed through variations in sediment input (Laurin et al., 2025). The Poruba Member therefore record a relatively warm climatic interval between the C1 and C2 glacial phases documented in Australia (Fielding et al., 2023). This interval represents a subphase characterized by limited ice accumulation at high latitudes and reduced glacieustatic amplitude (Rygel et al., 2008). However, the processes responsible for the formation of the coal-bearing paralic strata of the Poruba Member remain unresolved.

The proposed master's thesis aims to expand the study area investigated by Opluštil et al., (2024) using archival drilling data, particularly from hydrocarbon exploration campaigns. Two composite sequences within the Poruba Member, P2 (lower part) and P5 (upper part) (sensu Opluštil et al., 2024), have been selected for detailed analysis.

The thesis will involve (1) construction of nine correlation cross-sections oriented in different directions relative to the basin axis, together with thickness maps of individual sequences and significant sedimentary bodies. The study primarily targets areas that have not been previously investigated. The objective is to correlate deltaic sand bodies and key flooding surfaces (marine, brackish, and freshwater bands, as well as major coal seams) to extend the existing stratigraphic framework. The study further aims to (2) interpret sedimentary mechanisms and controlling factors in relation to climate-driven fluctuations in sediment supply to the basin, and to define the sedimentary environments of individual facies based on detailed (3) sedimentological descriptions of drill core intersecting both sequences.

The expected outcome will be identification of lithofacies, interpretation of depositional mechanisms, and a sequence-stratigraphic framework for the sequences P2 and P5 of Poruba Member.

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Hydrothermal alteration and metamictization of Th-U-bearing phases in NYF-type pegmatites from the Kola Alkaline Province

MICHAŁ KULIŃSKI¹, BOGUSŁAW BAGIŃSKI¹ & MARCIN STACHOWICZ¹

1 – Department of Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Petrology, Faculty of Geology, University of Warsaw; Warsaw, Poland; mp.kulinski@student.uw.edu.pl

NYF-type (Nb-Y-F) pegmatites associated with the alkaline granite complexes of the Kola Peninsula represent globally significant repositories of high-field-strength elements (HFSE), REE and actinides. Within the Keivy alkaline province, peralkaline granites host rare-metal mineralization enriched in Zr, Nb, Y, REE, Th and U, reflecting advanced magmatic differentiation and subsequent fluid-rock interaction processes. Previous studies from the region (Macdonald et al. 2017; Zozulya et al. 2022) emphasized the importance of hydrothermal overprinting in modifying primary ThSiO₄ and related accessory phases. However, the microstructural evolution and geochemical redistribution of Th-U phases in NYF pegmatites remain incompletely constrained. The host rocks are of Neoproterozoic age (2656 ± 5 Ma), as constrained by zircon geochronology (Lyalina et al. 2012), which is critical for interpreting the significant accumulation of radiogenic Pb derived from long-term U and Th decay.

This study focuses on the textural and chemical evolution of U-thorite occurring in NYF pegmatites from the Kola alkaline province. U-thorite is present both as inclusions within zircon and as discrete crystals intergrown with zircon. Locally, inclusions of coffinite occur within U-thorite, as confirmed by EMPA analyses. Particular attention was paid to hydrothermal alteration processes leading to remobilization of actinides, enrichment in incompatible elements, and progressive metamictization of (Th,U)SiO₄.

Backscattered electron (BSE) imaging and EDS analyses were performed using a SEM Apreo 2 Thermo Fisher Scientific at the Laboratory of Electron Microscopy, Microanalysis and X-Ray Diffraction (University of Warsaw). BSE images (Fig. 1a-b) reveal pervasive fracturing, internal heterogeneity, patchy compositional zoning and domains of variable elemental composition within (Th,U)SiO₄ grains. These features are consistent with radiation-induced structural damage and fluid-assisted dissolution-reprecipitation processes described for altered thorite in peralkaline systems (Macdonald et al. 2017).

Preliminary EBSD analyses were conducted using a SEM Auriga 60 ZEISS to evaluate the degree of crystallinity of (Th,U)SiO₄ and assess the preservation of its crystal structure. The majority of investigated domains exhibit weak or absent diffraction patterns, indicating predominantly amorphous material. This observation is consistent with BSE imaging, which suggests extensive radiation damage and hydrothermal overprint. Only a minor proportion of the analyzed domains yielded indexable patterns corresponding to tetragonal thorite, indicating locally preserved crystalline domains. Quantitative EMPA analyses (Cameca SX100) reveal significant compositional variability within U-thorite. Th contents decrease from 52.8 wt.% in weakly altered domains (bright in BSE; Fig. 1a) to 27.2 wt.% in strongly altered zones, reflecting hydration and extensive metamictization. U ranges from 24.8 wt.% in U-thorite inclusions within zircon to 5.3 wt.% in larger crystals. Radiogenic Pb (0.9–2.3 wt.%) correlates with U-rich domains, consistent with dominant radiogenic Pb production from U decay. Y reaches up to 8.0 wt.% in altered areas, indicating fluid-driven enrichment, while F (up to 1.3 wt.%) reflects interaction with F-bearing hydrothermal fluids. Coffinite inclusions (Fig. 1b) contain 36.2–41.9 wt.% U with compositions that deviate from ideal stoichiometry due to substantial Pb substitution, reaching up to 32.0 wt.%. Low analytical totals further confirm hydration and fluid-mediated element exchange, with alteration dominated by structural degradation rather than recrystallization.

The combined microtextural and geochemical data indicate that hydrothermal alteration played a crucial role in the redistribution of actinides and other incompatible elements in NYF pegmatites of the Kola province, while metamictization enhanced permeability of (Th,U)SiO₄, facilitating fluid infiltration and partial re-equilibration. Ongoing work includes element mapping, Raman spectroscopy to

constrain H₂O content, and planned Pb isotopic analyses to refine the timing of actinide remobilization. The results provide a preliminary framework for understanding actinide mobility and structural destabilization of Th–U phases in alkaline granite systems.

Figure 1. Backscattered electron (BSE) images of selected microdomains within U-thorite (Th) associated with zircon (Zr) with a darker zone overgrowing U-thorite. (a) U-thorite intergrown with zircon (Zr), showing pronounced internal heterogeneity and fracturing; darker areas represent strongly amorphous domains altered by hydrothermal fluids. (b) Fractured U-thorite hosting a coffinite (U) inclusion, visible as the brightest areas in the image.

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Tracer tests in the Vřídlo feeding conduit (Karlovy Vary Spa, Czechia)

DAVID-AARON LANDA¹, JIŘÍ BRUTHANS¹ & TOMÁŠ VYLITA²

1 – Institute of Hydrogeology, Engineering Geology and Applied Geophysics, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; landadav@natur.cuni.cz

2 – Institute of Spa and Balneology; Karlovy Vary, Czech Republic

The study of hydrothermal systems is at a relatively advanced stage, allowing for the precise targeting of boreholes for geothermal energy extraction. However, there is still a lack of information regarding the flow characteristics of thermal water within the feeding conduits of fractured environments. This is primarily due to insufficient drilling exploration, which precludes the accurate characterization of anisotropy directly on such a local scale. Karlovy Vary (Carlsbad) in the Czech Republic represents a suitable location for studying this phenomenon.

The city of Karlovy Vary is well known for its thermal springs. The total discharge of the thermal spring system is approximately 33 L/s, with a total dissolved solids (TDS) content of 6.4 g/L, and a maximum temperature of 73.4 °C (Vrba, 1996). While dozens of springs emerge in Karlovy Vary, the hydraulic center of the system lies directly beneath the Vřídlo spring. As the hottest and highest-discharge spring in Karlovy Vary; Vřídlo accounts for more than 95 % of the total discharge of the system. All other springs are dependent on the hydraulic and pneumatic conditions within Vřídlo (Vylita, 1967). An increase in discharge in the Vřídlo feeding conduit (i.e., lower pressure) leads to a pressure drop across the entire structure, subsequently decreasing the discharge of peripheral springs. The Vřídlo feeding conduit thus acts as the primary pathway of water from depth approximately 2,0 – 2,5 km to the surface for the whole spring structure. Such highly permeable and high discharge feeding conduits within fractured rock environments are unique and atypical, since these environments are typical for low permeability that typically decreases with depth (Zhao 1998). Therefore, understanding of the formation of such an interconnected system is crucial.

Between 2024 and 2026, a total of seven tracer tests using Na-fluorescein were conducted in the Vřídlo feeding conduit. The tracer mass ranged from 0.4 to 30 g and the monitored concentrations were at the very limit of quantification (LOQ). The tracer was injected three times into a 162 m deep borehole BJ 201, once into a 69.5 m deep borehole BJ 70 and three times into a 15 m deep borehole BPJ 69. In total, during the last tracer test (Nov. 2025 – Jan. 2026), 17 points were monitored (+11 uncaptured springs), and approximately 900 water samples were collected for tracer analysis. The following equation was used for calculating the Vřídlo conduits' volume [m³]:

$$V = Q * R * MRT$$

where: Q is flow rate of the monitored point (L/s), MRT is mean residence time (s), and R is tracer recovery (-).

Despite the high discharge of Vřídlo and the initial assumption of a small feeding conduit volume, the tracer did not reach the monitoring points within minutes as expected. Based on the tracer test results, it was calculated that the volume of open fractures must exceed 500 m³ down to the injection depth of 95 m b.g.l. The analysis of all the tracer tests revealed two distinct hydrogeological zones (Fig. 1). The shallow zone, characterized by high porosity resulting from the interaction of strongly altered granites with aragonite sinter accumulation (vřídlovec). The deeper zone with lower porosity, restricted to open fractures at depth resulting in higher migration velocities.

Figure 1. Conceptual model of Vřídlo feeding conduit (not in scale).

The tracer tests confirmed significant flow velocity anisotropy within the structure, caused by variations in fracture aperture in the vicinity of Vřídlo compared to the rest of the spring structure. Furthermore, analysis of the breakthrough curves indicates significant *tailing*, with MRT from 70 to 300 hours, also suggesting a dual-porosity system. The total tracer recovery was relatively low (<40%), most likely due to flow into unmapped voids. This was supported by single-event sampling of 11 uncaptured springs in the Teplá riverbed, which confirmed that the tracer had dispersed throughout the broader spring structure.

The results of the tracer tests, based on isochrones etc., allowed for a more precise localization of the Vřídlo feeding conduit and, in particular, the determination of groundwater flow characteristics within these highly permeable zones (conduits). It was found that anisotropy varies not only in the x-y plane, but also with increasing depth. Peak velocities in the deeper zone reach up to 100 m/day, indicating a very rapid flow. The results of the study will also have practical applications, as they will be used for the siting of new Vřídlo boreholes in the future. Currently, the second phase of work is underway, focusing on laboratory analyses of drill cores.

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Trace element composition of sphalerite from the Ruš zinc deposit, Slovenia

MAKSIMILJAN LAVRENČIČ¹,
ALEŠ ŠOSTER¹ & VIKTOR BERTRANDSSON ERLANDSSON²

1 – Department of Geology, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering, University of Ljubljana; Ljubljana, Slovenia; ales.soster@ntf.uni-lj.si

1 – Chair of Geology and Economic Geology, University of Leoben; Leoben, Austria

The Ruš zinc deposit is located in Spodnje Jezersko in the southern Karavanke Alps, northeast of Kranj, in Slovenia (Buser, 1980). This area contains several occurrences of mineralization with Zn, Pb, Cu and Sb minerals in the form of small stratiform deposits in the areas of Stegovnik, Ruš and Virnikov Grintovec, which formed in the lower Carboniferous (Drovenik et al., 1980; Pirc & Herlec, 2009; Budkovič, 2009). The zinc-lead ores are hosted at the contact between the Upper Devonian limestones and the Carboniferous clastites of the Hochwipfel Formation (Drovenik et al., 1980; Buser, 1980; Pirc & Herlec, 2009). These deposits are largely unstudied and haven't been extensively mined in the past.

The main ore mineral of the Ruš deposit is sphalerite (Sph), while galena, pyrite and tetrahedrite are also present. The paragenesis of mineral formation was determined on the basis of mineral textures, microscopic observations and geochemical analysis. Sphalerite mineralization occurred in two phases. In the first phase Sph 1 mineralized in the form of black and brown breccia infills or veins, while in the second phase younger Sph 2 mineralized as orange or beige veins and impregnations, that often intersect Sph 1.

LA-ICP-MS analysis of trace elements of sphalerites, show that both types contain a similar composition of Mn, Fe, Ni, Cd, Hg and Tl, while Sph 2 contains higher contents of Co, Cu, Ga, Ge, As, Se, Ag, Sn, Sb and Pb, than Sph 1. Correlations between trace elements show that they were incorporated into sphalerites either by direct substitution for Zn²⁺, e.g., Fe²⁺, Mn²⁺, Hg²⁺, Cd²⁺, or by coupled substitution for Zn²⁺ with Cu⁺, e.g. Ga³⁺, Ge⁴⁺, As³⁺, Sb³⁺, Ag⁺. Concentrations of trace elements were used for the calculations of sphalerite formation temperatures, using the GGIMFis geothermometer (Frenzel et al., 2016), and determined formation temperature ranges of 110–240°C for Sph 1 and 60–210°C for Sph 2. Trace element concentrations were also used for the determination of an intermediate sulfidation state of fluids responsible for sphalerite formation.

We assume that both types of sphalerites mineralized as a result of fluid mixing. Sph 1 formed as result of the mixing of a Cl rich fluid, that mainly transported Zn and secondarily Fe and Mn, with a Cl depleted fluid, that contained Hg and Cd. Meanwhile Sph 2 formed as a result of the mixing of a fluid that was Cl-rich and carried Zn, and a fluid in which trace elements were present in the form of hydroxides, e.g. Ga(OH)₃, and contained high values of Cu, Ga, Ge and Ag.

We conclude that, based on, carbonate-host rock, low-temperature precipitation temperature (<250 °C) and the enrichment of sphalerite with trace elements, especially Ga, the Ruš deposit is a low-temperature hydrothermal zinc deposit of the Mississippi-Valley type.

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Quantitative mineralogy of non-ferrous metallurgical slags to guide the potential recovery of valuable metal(loid)s

MARTIN LICHOVNÍK¹ & VOJTĚCH ETTLER¹

1 – Institute of Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Mineral Resources, Charles University, Faculty of Science; Prague, Czech Republic; martin.lichovnik@natur.cuni.cz

Which processing route should be used? This is the key question when considering the extraction of valuable metals and metalloids from waste materials. Metallurgical slags can serve as an alternative source of critical/strategic elements, such as Co, Cu or Ni (Piatak & Ettler, 2021), yet their reprocessing is challenging. The two fundamental approaches are similar to the processing of ores: (1) crushing, milling and froth flotation to produce a sulfide-rich concentrate, followed by smelting and refining (the pyrometallurgical route) and (2) leaching using wet chemical agents, such as mineral acids, followed by solvent extraction or other chemical separation processes and electrodeposition of the target metals from purified solutions (the hydrometallurgical route) (Schlesinger et al., 2011). Among the numerous conditions and circumstances that need to be considered, the properties of the slag itself are principal, especially the content and distribution of the target elements. Mineralogical investigations using the quantitative approach can be particularly useful in providing answers.

In this contribution, we report the application of various quantitative mineralogical techniques based on scanning electron microscopy (SEM) to characterize slags from the metallurgy of copper from several localities in Africa (Botswana, Namibia, and Zambia). We demonstrate the advantages of these techniques especially for the analysis of largely amorphous materials, represented by granulated slags.

Using a combination of automated mineralogy (autoSEM), image analysis, and electron probe microanalysis (EPMA), we determined the phase composition of the granulated Cu-Ni-Co slag from Selebi-Phikwe (Botswana). The results showed that the slag is primarily composed of silicate glass (84 area%), fayalite (15 area%), and trace sulfides and metallic phases (0.2 area%) and spinel-group minerals (0.1 area%). Based on the calculated elemental distribution (98 wt%, 74 wt%, and 66 wt% of the total Co, Cu, and Ni content were bound in the glass) we concluded that acid leaching and hydrometallurgical processing are the preferred strategies for the reprocessing of this material. Similarly, in the case of the fine-grained Cu slag from Tsumeb (Namibia), the silicate glass was the most abundant phase (over 90 area%) and it was the dominant host phase for the target elements, containing 58–70 wt% of the total Cu and over 90 wt% of the total Zn (Lichovnik et al., 2025).

Furthermore, we analyzed the size distribution of the entrapped matte (sulfide inclusions) in mostly crystalline, massive Cu(-Co) slags from five slag dumps from historical or active copper smelting operations in Zambia using a simple SEM image analysis. The results indicated that the best candidates for reprocessing through crushing, milling, and flotation were the Nkana (Kitwe) and Mufulira slags, which had the most abundant fraction of large sulfide grains (>100 μm , volume basis).

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Towards understanding of the Jurassic/Cretaceous transition – the Neuquén Basin (Argentina) perspective

DAMIAN GERARD LODOWSKI¹, JACEK GRABOWSKI¹,
VERÓNICA V. VENNARI² & BEATRIZ AGUIRRE-URRETA³

1 – Polish Geological Institute – National Research Institute; Warsaw, Poland;
damian.lodowski@pgi.gov.pl

2 – Instituto de Evolución, Ecología Histórica y Ambiente (IDEVEA, UTN-CONICET), Universidad Tecnológica Nacional-Facultad Regional San Rafael; Mendoza, Argentina

3 – Instituto de Estudios Andinos Don Pablo Groeber (IDEAN, UBA-CONICET), Departamento de Ciencias Geológicas, Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Naturales, Universidad de Buenos Aires; Buenos Aires, Argentina

Over decades, the Jurassic/Cretaceous transition has remained controversial and widely debated. In a broader context, the Tithonian–Berriasian interval was marked by a major marine regression that promoted strong faunal provincialism and hindered supra-regional correlations, resulting in a long-standing lack of consensus on the stratigraphy of this boundary. Recently, several studies have highlighted important palaeoenvironmental changes during the latest Jurassic–earliest Cretaceous, including the VOICE (Volgian Isotopic Carbon Excursion), a cool and arid climate mode in the late Tithonian–early Berriasian, and climate humidification at the early/late Berriasian transition. However, none of these events has yet been demonstrated to have a truly global extent.

To address problems with supra-regional correlations and age models for the Jurassic/Cretaceous transition, this study focuses on magnetostratigraphic investigations of two biostratigraphically and radiometrically dated sections in the Neuquén Basin (Argentina): Las Alcantarillas and Las Loicas (i.e. Vennari et al., 2026). Precise correlation between the sections was achieved using high-resolution gamma-ray spectroscopy (GRS) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF). The resulting composite Tithonian–Berriasian record comprises the ~20 m thick uppermost continental sandstones of the Tordillo Formation and the overlying ~226 m succession of dark gray limestones, marls/claystones, and subordinate sandstones and marls of the Vaca Muerta Formation.

Although thermal and alternating-field demagnetization revealed that many samples yielded ambiguous (primary or secondary) palaeomagnetic directions, the high-resolution sampling (223 horizons) and systematic occurrence of reversed-polarity samples, interpreted as primary synsedimentary magnetizations, enabled correlation with the geomagnetic polarity time scale. Integration of the magnetostratigraphic framework with radiometric ages allows detailed correlation with other Tithonian–Berriasian successions and significantly improves late Jurassic–early Cretaceous age models, which previously lacked such precise calibration.

This study also investigates palaeoclimate and paleoceanographic signals from the Neuquén Basin (Figure 1). Palaeoenvironmental records were assessed using GRS, XRF, and ICP-MS analyses of major and trace elements. The Tordillo–Vaca Muerta transition records a major reduction in clastic input (e.g. Al), whereas increased lithogenic influx occurs only at the lower/upper Berriasian boundary. Palaeoclimate proxies (i.e. Al/K, Th/K) indicate relatively humid conditions in the early Tithonian, particularly during deposition of the basal Vaca Muerta Formation. In contrast, the late Tithonian–early Berriasian (M20n–M17r) was relatively arid, as reflected by low and stable Al/K and Th/K. A sharp rise in both ratios at the lower/upper Berriasian transition indicates climate humidification. Notably, this interval coincides with more frequent tuff layers, suggesting that the climatic shift may have been triggered by volcanic activity. Ultimately, suboxic to anoxic conditions occurred during the early Tithonian (basal Vaca Muerta Formation) and again in the early Berriasian.

One of the striking observations is the correlation between early/late Berriasian humidification in the Neuquén Basin and similar signals recently reported from the Transdanubian Range (Hungary),

the Slovenian Basin (Slovenia), and the Vocontian Basin (SE France) (i.e. Lodowski et al., 2025). This correspondence may indicate the global extent of the J/K climatic changes and suggests that earliest Cretaceous humidification and warming were linked to volcanic activity along the Andean margin of the Pacific.

Figure 1. Integrated stratigraphy (after Vennari et al., 2026) and selected paleoenvironmental indices in the Tithonian–Berriasian of the Neuquén Basin. Explanations: ANOX – dysoxic/anoxic intervals; And. – Andesensis; Cps. – Calpionellopsis; Crass. – Crassicolaria; Fer. – Ferasini; Inter. – Internispinosum.

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Microsporangiate Cones of Conifers from the Cretaceous of the Lusitanian Basin, Portugal, and Bohemian Cretaceous Basin, Czech Republic

ANASTÁZIE LUDVÍKOVÁ^{1,2} & JIŘÍ KVAČEK³

1 – Institute of Geology and Palaeontology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; anastazie.ludvikova@natur.cuni.cz

2 – Department of Geology and Paleontology, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Comenius University; Bratislava, Slovakia

3 – Department of Palaeontology, National Museum Prague; Prague, Czech Republic

The primary objective of this contribution is the study of microsporangiate cones of cretaceous conifers and their pollen in situ, focusing on description and taxonomic classification. The examined material originates from Lower Cretaceous localities of the Lusitanian Basin and from the Cenomanian Peruc-Korycany Formation of the Bohemian Cretaceous Basin. The best exposure in the Peruc-Korycany Formation is in Pecínov quarry near Nové Strašecí. It has long been regarded as an outstanding locality, known for yielding micro-, meso-, and macrofossils (Kvaček et al., 2024). In Portugal, several previously studied palaeobotanical localities were also included. Cones examined in this study were obtained from sediments of Santa Susana formation - locality Ameal (Lower Hauterivian) (Mendes et al., 2019), of Figueita da Foz formation - locality Juncal (Upper Aptian to Lower Albian) (Mendes et al., 2025) and of Almargem formation - locality Catefica (Upper Aptian to Lower Albian) (Mendes et al., 2017, Friis et al., 2022).

The microsporangiate cones and their pollen in situ were examined using a combination of destructive and non-destructive paleontological methods. Prior to detailed study of mesofossils and pollen grains, the material was subjected to maceration processes following standard procedures used for cuticular analysis (Kerp & Krings in Jones & Rowe 1999). The duration of maceration varied between each locality due to different degrees of carbonification and the presence of pyrite or secondary mineral crystals. The material was subsequently examined using light microscopy and scanning electron microscopy. Selected specimens were additionally examined using X-ray microtomography. Pollen grains were studied by implementing the single-grain method.

In total, five fossil taxa of Cretaceous microsporangiate cones of conifers were described, belonging to the families Cheirolepidiaceae and Cupressaceae (subfamily Taxodioideae). The first newly recognised species, *Classostrobus* sp. 1, was recovered from the Middle Cenomanian sediments at the Pecínov locality. In situ analysis revealed pollen grains of *Classopollis classoides* (Pflug) Pocock et Jansonius. A pollen cone found directly attached to the vegetative axis of *Frenelopsis alata* (K. Feistmantel) Erw. Knobloch was also examined, supporting the interpretation that both organs belong to a single natural taxon. Based on morphological features and in situ pollen analysis, a cone from the Hauterivian locality of Ameal was described as *Classostrobus* sp. 2. Also assigned to the family Cheirolepidiaceae is a vegetative shoot of *Brachyphyllum* sp. from Ameal based on its cuticle and the presence of *Classopollis* pollen grain clusters.

Within the Cupressaceae, three microsporangiate cone taxa were identified on the basis of pollen and morphology. *Masculostrobus* sp. 1 and *Masculostrobus* sp. 2 originate from deposits at the Aptian–Albian boundary at Juncal, whereas *Masculostrobus* sp. 3 was described from sediments of comparable age at Catefica.

The cones were compared with one another and with previously described species of the genera *Classostrobus* and *Masculostrobus*. The results indicate that the specimens most likely represent new species.

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Multi-proxy analysis of organic matter maturity in the Polish Outer Carpathians – preliminary results

ANNA MACIEJEWSKA¹, MARCIN BARSKI¹, MARTA WALICZEK²

1 – Faculty of Geology, University of Warsaw; Warsaw, Poland; ak.maciejewska2@uw.edu.pl

2 – Faculty of Geology, Geophysics and Environmental Protection, AGH University of Krakow; Krakow, Poland

The Outer Carpathians, which are a part of the Alpine orogenic belt in central Europe, have been extensively studied for decades due to their complex tectonic history. Both their structural units and lithology (flysch sequences) made them prone to the generation and exploration of hydrocarbons (Janowski & Probulski, 2011). As a result, establishing the paleotemperature distribution, the maturity of organic matter, and their correlation has become a crucial issue for many researchers, and this remains poorly understood.

This study applies organic petrological methods (vitrinite reflectance measurements and autofluorescence analysis) to estimate the maturity of organic matter in the cross-section of nappes in the Polish Outer Carpathians. The main aim is to correlate results from various methods, assess their efficiency, and discuss the spatial relationships among the outcomes.

Samples are derived from 11 outcrops located in the eastern part of the Polish Outer Carpathians, in the Dukla, Silesian, and Skole Nappes. To provide sufficient material for analyses, organic-rich shales of the Menilite Beds (Oligocene) have been selected. Rock material was collected from several layers in the profile of each outcrop, yielding a total of 56 samples.

The measurement of colouration and autofluorescence of palynomorphs involves dissecting microfossils, such as dinoflagellate cysts and pollen grains, preparing microscope slides, and analysing them under both white and ultraviolet light. The observed colours can be converted to the vitrinite reflectance equivalent (Ro%) using standard diagrams: Thermal Alteration Index (TAI) (Staplin, 1969), Pearson's colour chart (Pearson, 1984), and then directly correlated with the maximum burial temperature of the sample (Hartkopf-Fröder et al., 2015). To quantify colour changes, the RGB (red, green, and blue) channels have been measured from photos of every specimen following Tahoun et al. (2018).

Vitrinite reflectance measurement (VRo%) provides another method for determining the thermal maturity of organic matter. This parameter is defined as the percent of light reflected from the surface of vitrinite macerals dispersed in a rock (Mukhopadhyay, 1994). This analysis provides a reliable standard for comparison with the autofluorescence and colouration of microfossils.

Vitrinite reflectance equivalent obtained from the microphotographs taken in white light corresponds to those converted from ultraviolet light in most cases. Moreover, controlling the RGB channels validates the application of both methods. The maturation values in the outcrops located along the strikes of the structures are virtually indistinguishable. In some outcrops (Monasterz, Hermanowa), palynomorph colouration and autofluorescence remain constant throughout the profile, whereas in others (Korzeniec, Sukowate BOM), color saturation changes (Fig. 1). On the other hand, examples where neighboring outcrops possess highly different color intensity (DOM, BOM) are still puzzling. In particular, when lower maturity was recorded closer to the thrust surface than higher ones. In the next step, more samples will be analysed to explain that issue.

In conclusion, assessment of organic matter maturity can yield a wide range of data on the thermal history and evolution of the Polish Outer Carpathians, especially when a few complementary analyses are employed. Finding a quantitative conversion factor between different methods of measuring the maturity of organic matter will benefit future classification and identification of hydrocarbons.

Figure 1. The outcrops localisations with the UV photos of the most representative dinoflagellate cysts and pollen grains. In case of significant colour differences, two pictures were given. Based on Jankowski et al. (2004).

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Multi-isotope insights into groundwater recharge and residence time in the Zagros Basin, Kurdistan region of Iraq: A case study from Sulaimani City

REBAR MAHMMUD¹, ONDRA SRACEK¹, OMED MUSTAFA², HOWRI MANSURBEG¹,
BOHUSLAVA ČEJKOVÁ³, IVANA JAČKOVÁ³ & LENKA VONDROVICOVÁ⁴

1 – Department of Geology, Faculty of Science, Palacky University; Olomouc, Czech Republic; rebar.mahmmud@upol.cz

2 – Research Centre, University of Sulaimani; Kurdistan Region, Iraq

3 – Czech Geological Survey; Prague, Czech Republic

4 – Institute of Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Natural Resources, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic

Groundwater recharge mechanisms, flow characteristics, and residence times in the Sulaimani–Warmawa Sub-basin, Kurdistan Region of Iraq (Zagros Fold–Thrust Belt), were investigated using an integrated isotopic framework. The sub-basin surrounds Sulaimani City, one of north-eastern Iraq's most densely populated urban centres, and represents a strategically important groundwater-dependent region. The semi-arid climate features seasonal winter–spring precipitation and long dry summers. Groundwater is accommodated within fractured and karstified carbonate aquifers hydraulically linked to the Tanjero River.

Twenty-six water samples, groundwater from production wells, precipitation, and surface water, were analysed for stable water isotopes ($\delta^2\text{H}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$), carbon isotopes of dissolved inorganic carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$), and strontium isotopes ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$), measured at the Czech Geological Survey and Charles University in Prague. Thirteen groundwater samples, one rainfall sample, and one Tanjero River sample were additionally collected for tritium (^3H) analysis at the University of Avignon. Groundwater apparent ages were estimated using the tritium decay equation and the piston-flow model (TracerLPM).

Stable isotope compositions plot close to the Local and Global Meteoric Water Lines, indicating recharge predominantly from winter meteoric precipitation sourced from Eastern Mediterranean and Persian Gulf air masses (Figure 1). The absence of significant pre-infiltration evaporative enrichment confirms rapid recharge under cool-season conditions. Isotopic groupings reflect both recent recharge and slightly more depleted signatures associated with higher-elevation or cooler recharge areas.

Tritium activities range from <0.8 to 4.9 TU in groundwater, compared to up to 7.3 TU in modern precipitation and surface water, indicating predominantly modern to sub-modern groundwater with residence times from less than 10 to approximately 40 years. The piston-flow model best fits the tritium data, implying limited mixing and fast subsurface transport. Tritium-derived velocities exceed hydraulic gradient estimates, evidencing preferential flow through karst conduits and fracture networks.

The $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{DIC}}$ values confirm carbonate dissolution as the dominant geochemical process, with minor silicate weathering influence. Strontium isotope ratios fall within the range of marine carbonate lithologies, confirming lithological control on groundwater composition and enabling flow-path discrimination between aquifer domains.

Overall, groundwater in the sub-basin is predominantly young, rapidly recharged, and hydraulically dynamic, with strong water–rock interaction and limited long-term storage. These characteristics indicate high vulnerability to surface-derived contamination, particularly where river–aquifer interaction occurs, underscoring the need for integrated groundwater protection and land-use management strategies.

Figure 1. $\delta^2\text{H}$ vs. $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ diagram. GWL: groundwater line (this study); LGWL: local groundwater line (Mahmmud et al., 2022); LMWL (Total): average local meteoric water line for Zagros; LMWL (Zagros): winter precipitation meteoric water line for Zagros; LMWL (Mediterranean): meteoric water line for Mediterranean precipitation; LMWL (Makook): meteoric water line for Makook anticline (Mustafa et al., 2015); LMWL (Basara): meteoric water line for precipitation, springs, wells, and streams in Basara (Hamamin & Ali, 2013); GMWL: Global Meteoric Water Line.

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Geoeducation as a tool for building awareness of geodiversity: insights from a questionnaire-based study

MARLENA MAŁYSZCZUK¹

1 – Faculty of Geology, University of Warsaw; Warsaw, Poland; marlenamalyszczuk@gmail.com

Geoeducation plays a key role in environmental protection and sustainable development by integrating geological knowledge with methods aimed at increasing societal awareness. Through the application of Earth science concepts within pedagogical frameworks, it facilitates understanding of geological processes and natural resources, while simultaneously emphasising the significance of geodiversity, understood as the natural variability of geological, geomorphological, soil, and hydrological features (Gray, 2013) and foster responsibility for its conservation and heritage (United Nations, 2015). Despite the fundamental role of geodiversity, public awareness remains limited, indicating a need for effective educational strategies.

The aim of this study was to evaluate social awareness of geodiversity and the effectiveness of geoeducational methods. An online questionnaire was distributed to 85 respondents of various age groups and educational backgrounds, focusing on familiarity with the term "geodiversity", exposure to geological topics in formal education, and preferred learning methods. Results show that only 48,8% of respondents were familiar with the term, 29,1% were uncertain, and 22,1% had never encountered it. Although 89,5% reported exposure to geological topics in school, this did not translate into high awareness, indicating a gap between formal education and lasting understanding. This gap may result from the predominantly theoretical character of school education and the limited use of experiential and field-based learning methods. Most respondents (77.8%) considered protecting geological heritage at least moderately important, and 67.4% expressed interest in expanding their knowledge. Preferred educational methods were practical and interactive, including field trips (86%), workshops (26.7%), and multimedia resources such as videos or apps (24.4%).

The study confirms that geoeducation can serve as an effective bridge between geoscience and society by translating complex geological knowledge into accessible and meaningful narratives. In line with previous studies emphasizing the importance of local-scale, experience-oriented educational initiatives (Migoń, 2019), the results support the need to strengthen both formal and informal geoeducation. Expanding field-based activities, integrating geoscientific topics across educational curricula, and using digital tools may significantly enhance public understanding of geodiversity.

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Geological setting and metallogenic evolution of critical Co–Ni–Fe arsenide mineralization in the Bou Azzer–El Graara inlier (Anti-Atlas, Morocco): A key cobalt-mining district for the energy transition

JABBOUR MARIEME¹, ILMEN SAID², CORDIER CAROLE³, IKENNE MOHA¹,
SOUHASSOU MUSTAPHA⁴, EL OUAD ZOUBAIR⁴, BOUSKRI ISMAIL⁴,
AFLLA IMAD⁴ & MAACHA LHOUS⁵

1 – Laboratory of applied geology and geo-environment, Faculty of sciences, Ibnou Zohr University; Agadir Morocco; marieme.jabbour@edu.uiz.ac.ma

2 – CAG2M, Polydisciplinary Faculty of Ouarzazate, Ibn Zohr University; Ouarzazate, Morocco

3 – Université Grenoble Alpes, Université Savoie Mont Blanc, CNRS, IRD, Université Gustave Eiffel; Grenoble, France

4 – 2GBEI Laboratory, Polydisciplinary Faculty of Taroudant, Ibn Zohr University; Taroudant, Morocco

5 – MANAGEM Group, Twin Center; Casablanca, Morocco

Cobalt is widely recognized as a critical raw material due to its strategic role in rechargeable batteries, electric vehicles, and renewable energy storage systems. With increasing demand driven by the global energy transition, improving the geological understanding of primary cobalt systems is essential for sustainable exploration strategies (European Commission, 2023). The Bou Azzer cobalt district in the central Anti-Atlas (Morocco) is one of the few mining districts worldwide where cobalt is produced from primary Co–Ni–Fe arsenide and sulfarsenide mineralization hosted in Neoproterozoic ophiolitic serpentinites. Unlike sediment-hosted Cu–Co deposits, Bou Azzer mineralization corresponds to structurally controlled hydrothermal arsenide systems developed within ultramafic rocks and along major tectonic corridors (Bouabdellah et al., 2016; Jabbour et al., 2026). This synthesis integrates structural and mineral-chemical data from the western Bou Froukh sector to the eastern Aït Ahmane deposits, including the central Aghbar sector, in order to highlight lateral (west–center–east) variability and paragenetic zoning across the district.

In the western Bou Froukh sector, mineralization is mainly localized along serpentinite–quartz diorite contacts and steep quartz–carbonate veins associated with E–W to WNW–ESE brittle faults interpreted as reactivated Pan-African structures (Jabbour et al., 2026). Two deformation stages are recognized: an early ductile fabric related to ophiolite emplacement and a later brittle phase marked by fault-controlled veining and brecciation. The central Aghbar sector exhibits a complex structural framework dominated by ENE–WSW reverse faults and NE–SW to NNE–SSW brittle systems, where mineralized veins preferentially occur at fault intersections and lithological contacts, particularly along the Major Anti-Atlas Fault (Jabbour et al., 2025). In the eastern Aït Ahmane area, mineralization is hosted by steep NNE–SSW vein systems such as the F53 structure, where dilation and brecciation controlled ore emplacement; compared with the western and central sectors, these deposits are more strictly vein-dominated and structurally confined (Ez-Zghoudy et al., 2023).

Hydrothermal alteration across the district reflects intense fluid–rock interaction under greenschist-facies conditions. Serpentinites are strongly carbonated and silicified, locally forming listvenite-like assemblages with talc–chlorite halos, indicating significant metasomatism (Bouabdellah et al., 2016). At Bou Froukh, alteration is concentrated along contacts and fracture corridors where Fe–Co–As enrichment occurs within breccias and fractures; sulfides are mainly late and subordinate, confirming the dominance of arsenide mineralization (Jabbour et al., 2026). Comparable alteration–mineralization relationships are observed at Aghbar (Jabbour et al., 2025), whereas jasperoid halos at Aït Ahmane record fluid circulation beyond serpentinite bodies.

Mineral-chemical and petrographic data indicate a coherent district-scale paragenetic evolution marked by progressive metal zoning. At Bou Froukh, early Ni-rich arsenides are overprinted by Co-dominant phases and later Fe-rich arsenides (Jabbour et al., 2026), reflecting evolving fluid chemistry and redox conditions. Aghbar shows a comparable multi-stage sequence from Ni-bearing diarsenides to Co–Fe arsenides and late Cu-bearing sulfides and sulfosalts (Jabbour et al., 2025), suggesting episodic hydrothermal pulses. In contrast, eastern deposits are dominated by Co–Ni–Fe assemblages, indicating spatial variability in fluid composition and/or metal sources (Admou et al., 2013; Hajjar et al., 2021).

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Mineralogy of arsenic and antimony in soils: partitioning between clays and Fe (oxyhydr)oxides

MAREK M. MICHALSKI¹ & PETR DRAHOTA¹

1 – Institute of Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Mineral Resources, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; michalsmar@natur.cuni.cz

Arsenic (As) and antimony (Sb) are closely related metalloids classified as highly toxic and potentially carcinogenic, posing significant risks to groundwater quality, plant growth, food safety, and human and animal health. Due to their somewhat similar geochemical behaviour, As and Sb commonly co-occur in ore mineralizations and are therefore frequently associated in soils derived from such parent material or affected by mining and smelting activities. In soils, both metalloids are generally assumed to be predominantly bound to Fe (hydr)oxides, with only a minor fraction associated with clay minerals. It is therefore noteworthy that numerous studies evaluating their particle-size distribution report inconsistent results regarding their enrichment in the clay fraction, especially for Sb (e.g. Drahota et al., 2023; Ilgen and Trainor, 2012; Qi et al., 2008). As noted by Majzlan and Filella (2024), much of the current understanding of As and Sb solid-phase speciation is derived from heavily contaminated systems (e.g. mine wastes), while its applicability to less contaminated environments remains uncertain. We address this gap, by investigating in detail the mineral associations and geochemical behaviour of As and Sb across different particle-size fractions, with particular focus on the clay fraction, in slightly polluted soils.

Samples were selected from four sites in the Czech Republic, representing different degrees and sources of contamination to ensure broad applicability of the results: mine waste (Kutná Hora, Stříbrné Hory), natural geochemical anomaly (Příčovy), and smelter emissions (Příbram). To assess the impact of a particle size on As and Sb solid-phase speciation, the clay fraction and three additional size fractions were separated. The investigation was carried out with special attention to the distribution of As and Sb between Fe (hydr)oxides and clay minerals, using complementary geochemical and mineralogical methods (EMPA, XRD, Raman microspectroscopy). Additionally, a modified sequential extraction procedure was applied, followed by ICP-OES and ICP-MS analyses, providing quantitative insight into As and Sb partitioning among clays and poorly and well crystalline Fe (hydr)oxides.

The concentration in the clay fraction showed up to 340% increase for As and 150% increase for Sb compared to the bulk fraction. Mineralogical results showed that this enrichment was caused by the strong affinity of As for Fe (hydr)oxides and minerals of jarosite group, whose abundance increased with decreasing particle size. Results from the sequential extractions nevertheless showed that ~30% of total Sb is bound to clay minerals, whereas only about 5% of total As is associated with them. This correspond well with the EMPA results, which demonstrated that Fe (hydr)oxides are the most significant carriers of both metalloids, but clay minerals consistently contained higher concentrations of Sb in all samples. These results indicate distinct solid-state partitioning of As and Sb in soils and highlight differences in their mineral associations and environmental behaviour. Overall, the findings contribute to a better understanding of the factors controlling the distribution and potential mobility of As and Sb under soil conditions.

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Integrated structural analysis of the Baligówka peat bog using seismic refraction tomography and shallow drilling, and its relationship to soil gas composition

MARTYNA MOTYLSKA¹ & WOJCIECH KWAŚNIAK¹

1 – AGH University of Science and Technology, Faculty of Geology, Geophysics and Environmental Protection, Kraków, Poland; mmotylska@student.agh.edu.pl

Peatlands play a significant role in the global carbon cycle, acting both as major carbon reservoirs and sources of greenhouse gases such as methane (CH₄) and carbon dioxide (CO₂). Peatlands of the Orawa–Nowy Targ Basin have been widely studied in terms of their development and spatial distribution (Łajczak, 2009; Lipka and Zajac, 2014). Gas generation and migration processes are strongly controlled by the internal structure of peat deposits, including their thickness, degree of water saturation, and the nature of the underlying substratum.

The aim of this study was to characterize the internal structure of the Baligówka peat bog (Orawa–Nowy Targ Basin, southern Poland) and to assess the spatial variability of soil gas composition in relation to geophysical parameters and surface morphology.

Seismic refraction profiling was conducted along a 1.5 km transect using a multichannel acquisition system (Geode DZ, 32 channels) with a geophone spacing of 5 m and a spread length of approximately 155 m. The seismic signal was generated using a 10 kg sledgehammer, with shot points spaced at 10 m intervals. The data were processed using tomographic inversion to obtain a continuous P-wave velocity model of the subsurface, which was subsequently calibrated using shallow manual drillings.

Additionally, GIS-based analyses (ArcGIS Pro, Esri) were applied to generate a geomorphological cross-section along the same profile.

Soil gas samples were collected at 50 m intervals using the free gas method (Dzieniewicz and Sechman, 2002). A total of 32 samples were analyzed by gas chromatography to determine concentrations of CH₄, CO₂, O₂, N₂, and H₂ (Sechman, 2012). Maximum concentrations reached 29 vol.% for CH₄ and 9.6 vol.% for CO₂.

The integrated interpretation of geophysical and geochemical data revealed a clear spatial relationship between zones of increased gas concentrations and areas of greater peat thickness as well as structural heterogeneity within the deposit. These results are consistent with previous studies on peat-forming processes and structural variability in peat deposits (Malec et al., 2015; Malec et al., 2016). These results indicate that variations in peat structure significantly influence gas generation and migration processes.

The study demonstrates that the integration of geophysical, geological, and near-surface geochemical methods provides an effective approach for identifying zones potentially significant in terms of greenhouse gas emissions in peatland environments.

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Experimental and Raman study of copper and tin selenides

JAN MRÁČEK^{1,2}, ANNA VYMAZALOVÁ¹, FRANTIŠEK LAUFEK¹ & FILIP KOŠEK²

1 – Czech Geological Survey; Prague, Czech Republic; jan.mracek@geology.cz

2 – Institute of Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Mineral Resources, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic

The following copper and tin selenides are known to occur in nature: bellidoite (Cu_2Se), berzelianite (Cu_{2x}Se , $x \approx 0.12$), umangite (Cu_3Se_2), athabascaite (Cu_5Se_4), klockmannite (CuSe), two polymorphs of CuSe_2 , krušaitite and petříčekite, svetlanaite (SnSe), and okruginite (Cu_2SnSe_3). These minerals typically form at low temperatures and under conditions of a high Se/S fugacity ratio. Such conditions and the formation of these minerals can be found in a range of deposit types, including low-temperature vein-type deposits (e.g., Grundmann et al., 1990), unconformity-type uranium deposits (e.g., Harris et al., 1970), and various Au deposits (e.g., Okrugin et al., 2022). The aim of this study is to experimentally investigate these minerals, assess their phase relations at 300 °C, and conduct a detailed Raman spectroscopic analysis.

The silica-glass tube method was used for the purpose of this study. All syntheses were carried out at the Laboratory of Experimental Mineralogy, Czech Geological Survey. High-purity elements were weighed in stoichiometric proportions, vacuum-sealed, annealed at 800 °C, homogenized, and then heated at 300 °C for three months. Finally, the experimental runs were quenched in a cold-water bath. The experimental products were examined using reflected-light microscopy, powder X-ray diffraction (XRD), electron microscopy (FEG-SEM), electron probe microanalysis (EPMA), and thermo-Raman spectroscopy. ThermoRaman spectra were recorded in the temperature range of 20–600 °C.

A total of 33 experiments were performed. The following binary phases were confirmed to be stable at 300 °C: αSnSe (analogue of svetlanaite), SnSe_2 (trigonal, $P-3m1$ space group), γCuSe (analogue of klockmannite), and CuSe_2 (analogue of petříčekite). According to our results, the phase $\beta\text{Cu}_{2-x}\text{Se}$ (cubic, $Fm-3m$ space group, analogue of berzelianite) seems to be unquenchable, and instead $\alpha\text{Cu}_{2-x}\text{Se}$ (monoclinic, $C2/c$ space group) forms after quenching from 300 °C. A ternary phase Cu_2SnSe_3 (monoclinic, Cc space group, analogue of okruginite, described in Vymazalová et al., 2024), was confirmed to be stable at 300 °C. It forms stable associations with the following copper and tin phases at 300 °C: Cu_{2-x}Se and SnSe ; SnSe and SnSe_2 ; SnSe_2 and native Se; CuSe_2 and native Se. The phase SnSe_2 , yet unknown as a mineral, can therefore be expected to be found in nature in assemblages with svetlanaite and okruginite. Experimental results indicate the formation of a potential ternary solid solution (ss) with a composition range of Cu 33.33–35.71 at.%, Sn 14.29–16.67 at.%, and Se 50 at.%. Our preliminary XRD and Raman spectroscopy results support this observation.

A set of Raman spectra was measured across all the binary phases in the system and the ternary ss, supporting the XRD results. Additionally, the endmembers of the ternary ss were measured from 20 to 600 °C. The room-temperature Raman spectra of the ss endmembers (Fig. 1) mainly differ in the region below 100 cm^{-1} and in the 210–217 cm^{-1} range. Following the work of Marcano et al. (2011), who provided tentative band assignments for monoclinic Cu_2SnSe_3 , the bands at 60–81, 180, and 251 cm^{-1} probably represent A' modes, and the bands at 210 and 236 cm^{-1} represent A'' modes. The band around 370 cm^{-1} is probably an overtone of the ~ 180 cm^{-1} band. Our preliminary thermo-Raman results show very similar thermal behaviour for both end-members of the potential ss.

Figure 1. Comparison of the Raman spectra of the solid-solution endmembers at 20 °C.

Our experimental results confirmed the following Cu–Sn selenides to be stable in the Cu–Sn–Se system at 300 °C: SnSe, SnSe₂, Cu_{2x}Se, CuSe, CuSe₂, and Cu₂SnSe₃. We also assessed the phase relations. In addition, Cu–Sn selenides were investigated by Raman spectroscopy. According to our investigation, the compound of composition “Cu₅Sn₂Se₇”, observed by Fan et al. (2014), does not appear to be a distinct phase, but rather seems to be the end-member of the ternary ss. However, further thermo-analytical and crystallographic studies are needed and will be the matter of detailed ongoing studies. The obtained results may provide new constraints for mineral formation under low-temperature Se-rich conditions.

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Variability and petrogenesis of the Blatná Composite Pluton (Central Bohemian Plutonic Complex)

BOJANA NIKOLIĆ^{1,2}, VOJTĚCH JANOUŠEK^{1,2}, JITKA MÍKOVÁ², JOHN M. HORA²,
ELIŠKA ŽÁČKOVÁ² & JAKUB KRYL²

1 – *Institute of Petrology and Structural Geology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; bojana.nikolic@geology.cz*

2 – *Czech Geological Survey; Prague, Czech Republic*

The Blatná Composite Pluton (BCP), the largest intrusion within the Variscan Central Bohemian Plutonic Complex, records polyphase magma emplacement and crust–mantle interaction during the pre- to early syn-collisional stages of the Variscan Orogeny (Holub et al., 1997; René, 1998, 1999; Janoušek et al., 2000a, b, 2010). This study integrates field observations, petrography, mineral chemistry, major- and trace-element whole-rock geochemistry, zircon U–Pb geochronology and in situ Hf isotope geochemistry as well as Sr–Nd whole-rock isotope analyses to constrain internal variability, crystallization ages, magma sources, and petrogenetic evolution of the BCP. The results are also highly relevant in assessment of the long-term mineralogical and geochemical stability of the granitoids considered as prospective media for the nuclear waste disposal.

Field relationships indicate multiple magma pulses represented by distinct intrusive phases that together form the BCP. Going inward, the three main facies are: (1) strongly foliated, relatively mafic Červená amphibole–biotite granodiorite, (2) marginal Blatná amphibole–biotite granodiorite, and (3) light and undeformed Blatná biotite granodiorite in the central part. The minor Polánka intrusion consists of muscovite–biotite granodiorite and the whole BCP is cross-cut by felsic and mafic dykes. Moreover, abundant mafic microgranular enclaves (MME) indicate magma mingling, whereas evidence for assimilation–fractional crystallization (AFC; DePaolo, 1981) is provided by granodiorites contaminated by metapelitic xenoliths at a stage of advanced anatexis.

Amphibole compositions range from magnesiohornblende–actinolite in Červená to magnesiohornblende with minor edenite in Blatná, suggesting elevated water activity. Biotite compositions range from transitional biotite–phlogopite in the Červená and Blatná intrusions to Fe-richer biotite in the Polánka intrusion, reflecting progressive iron enrichment and compositional variations of the melt across the intrusions.

The Červená and Blatná intrusions are predominantly metaluminous to subaluminous high-K calc-alkaline granitoids, whereas the Polánka granodiorite, along with felsic dyke, is weakly peraluminous, indicating a more mature metasedimentary source. These geochemical characteristics, together with the large-ion lithophile elements (LILE) enrichment and high-field-strength elements (HFSE) depletion demonstrated by conspicuous negative Nb–Ta anomalies in NMORB-normalized multielement plots, are consistent with subduction-related (arc) magmatism (Pearce et al., 1984; Barbarin, 1999). Negative Eu anomalies in the chondrite-normalized REE patterns of the Červená and Blatná intrusions indicate significant fractionation of feldspar(s) and/or derivation from a Eu-depleted source. In contrast, the Polánka intrusion and felsic dyke display negligible Eu anomalies, suggesting limited feldspar fractionation and a distinct source.

Zircon Hf and whole-rock Sr–Nd data for the Červená and Blatná intrusions give late Palaeoproterozoic to early Mesoproterozoic residence ages and imply evolved crust-like signatures consistent with derivation from reworked continental crust, possibly further variably modified by AFC processes. The Polánka intrusion displays a relatively more radiogenic Nd, but retains crustal affinity, indicating partial melting of a compositionally distinct metasedimentary source. The LA ICP-MS U–Pb zircon dating of Blatná granodiorite yielded crystallization ages of 350.4 ± 1.4 Ma for the marginal amphibole–biotite facies and 343.8 ± 1.4 Ma for the central biotite facies, documenting incremental assembly during the late Tournaisian–early Viséan.

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Phase changes in lunar breccia during space weather simulation using Focused ion beam and Raman spectroscopy

RADEK NOVOTNÝ¹, GUNTHER KLETETSCHKA^{1,2},
FILIP KOŠEK³ & DANIELA POPELKOVÁ⁴

1 – Institute of Hydrogeology, Engineering Geology and Applied Geophysics, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic; novotnyra@natur.cuni.cz

2 – Geophysical Institute, University of Alaska Fairbanks; United States of America

3 – Institute of Geochemistry, Mineralogy and Mineral Resources, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic

4 – Imaging Methods Laboratory, BIOCEV; Vestec, Czech Republic

Space weathering on airless bodies, for example the Moon, results from solar wind irradiation and micrometeoroid impacts. Focused ion beam (FIB) irradiation provides a controlled laboratory proxy for high-energy ion interactions, simulating the effects of solar wind (H^+ , He^{2+}) and deep space radiation (Nénon et al., 2023). These processes fundamentally drive structural amorphization and chemical reduction on planetary surfaces.

We analysed monocrystalline silicon as one of three reference materials for FIB irradiation-induced damage, as well as pyrite from Ambas Aguas region in Spain (Calvo and Sevillano, 1989) and non-titanium magnetite. Apollo 15 lunar impact melt breccias 15405 and 15445 were measured, where enstatite and anorthite clasts were selected. Irradiation was performed using a FIB (currents 0.43, 0.79, 2.5 and 9.3 nA), followed by Raman spectroscopy analyses to monitor structural and lattice transformations.

The geological provenance of the selected clasts provides a critical framework for interpreting these transformations, as Apollo 15 breccias 15405 and 15445 represent complex impact melts from the Apennine Front. While the 15445 matrix displays composition indicative of deep-seated crustal melting, its pristine clast population consists of Mg-suite norites and spinel troctolites with Sm-Nd crystallization ages ranging from 4.28 to 4.46 Ga (Shih et al., 1993). In contrast, breccia 15405 hosts KREEP-rich quartz-monzodiorite fragments containing unzoned pyroxenes. Our Raman analysis of the anorthite clasts specifically monitors ν_a mode (typically located between 503 and 509 cm^{-1}): the progressive broadening and shifting of respective band serve as a diagnostic measure of Al-Si structural disorder and lattice strain, allowing us to distinguish between primary compositional variations (An-content) and the cumulative effects of ion-induced amorphization (Bersani et al., 2018).

After the exposure to the highest beam intensity, we can observe lattice amorphization and oxidation in the samples, where progressive structural degradation is documented by the Raman analyses. Monocrystalline silicon's 522 cm^{-1} peak shifted to 501 cm^{-1} , while enstatite Si-O stretching modes downshifted from 996 to 989 cm^{-1} . However, low-dose Ga^+ irradiation served as a cleaning process. Physical sputtering removed weathered patinas, revealing pristine crystalline substrates. In 15445 enstatite, a prominent band emerged at 659 cm^{-1} , this is the Si-O-Si bending mode, whose position reflects the iron content of lunar orthopyroxenes (Huang et al., 2000). Chemical reduction was mostly evident in the stabilization of magnetite (mode $\sim 659-680$ cm^{-1}) via oxygen sputtering.

We also observed sulfide alteration in pyrite. Raman spectroscopic analysis of the samples confirmed characteristic vibrational modes at 343, 379 and 430 cm^{-1} . With increasing Ga^+ irradiation, broadening of these bands and the appearance of additional features at 212 and 274 cm^{-1} were observed, indicating progressive alteration and the formation of secondary Fe-oxides. Laboratory simulations demonstrated that sulfides are highly sensitive to chemical degradation (Bryant et al., 2018). With increasing beam intensity, gradual amorphization of the mineral structure and oxidation of sulfur occurred, which manifested in itself in the broadening of the bases of the main bands. At the highest irradiation stage, the disappearance of the 430 cm^{-1} band and the emergence of a feature near 461 cm^{-1} suggest significant restructuring of the original pyrite lattice. The primary process is the preferential

sputtering of sulfur, leading to its depletion and the formation of an iron-enriched residue (Lacznia et al., 2024). This study demonstrates that FIB irradiation successfully replicates the microscopic amorphization and element redistribution observed in weathered samples.

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MultiGravel: advancing multivariate approach to pebble morphometry with the example of Quaternary Pre-Metuje River gravels

NIKOLA ORZOŁ¹, SZYMON MOL^{2,1}, KRZYSZTOF NINARD¹, ŁUKASZ BARAN³,
WERONIKA CZWOŃDA¹, KAROLINA DYKA¹, JULIA DZIEWOŃSKA¹, KONRAD FARUGA¹,
KRZYSZTOF KACZMAREK¹, AGATA KUŹMA^{2,1}, KAMIL ROMANIK¹,
MATEUSZ SOBUCKI³ & PIOTR ŁAPCIK¹

1 – Institute of Geological Sciences, Jagiellonian University; Kraków, Poland;
nikola.orzol@student.uj.edu.pl

2 – Doctoral School of Exact and Natural Sciences; Jagiellonian University; Kraków, Poland

3 – Institute of Geography and Spatial Management; Jagiellonian University; Kraków, Poland

Gravel deposits exposed in the vicinity of Polish-Czech former border crossing in Kudowa Stone-Náchod (Orličké Foothills, Central Sudetes) record Quaternary fluvial transport and deposition processes in the Pre-Metuje River catchment (Cymerman, 2019). Such deposits provide insights into the palaeogeographic setting of the area, but can also serve as a testing ground for fundamental research on the interface of sedimentology and geomathematics. Morphometric studies in biology frequently employ multivariate techniques, such as principal component analysis (PCA). In contrast, these methods are less commonly utilized in geological sciences (Babej et al., 2016; Bialik et al., 2021). For example, the multivariate approach to pebble morphometry has only been demonstrated on a section of fluvial gravel deposits dominated by sandstone-composed pebbles (Mol et al., 2024). The present contribution aims to extend the applicability of this method to deposits comprising more lithologically diverse material, i.e., igneous, sedimentary and metamorphic rock pebbles.

We selected a representative section of the outcrop in Kudowa Stone and collected volume-standardised samples at 10 cm intervals. Grains with $\varnothing > 8$ mm have been separated using sieves and ca. 50 pebbles randomly were selected per sampled interval for further analyses. Morphometric measurements, weighing and lithotype identification were performed. The three linear axes of each pebble were measured with a vernier calliper adopting the standard notion of length a , width b , and thickness c . As a result, a multivariate dataset describing 537 pebbles from an interval of 1-meter total thickness was obtained. Using the PCA module in PAST 5 software, a data set with four quantitative variables (dimensions a , b , c and mass), a descriptive variable (lithotype) and a complementary variable (stratigraphic height) was analysed.

Two most significant principal components (PC1 and PC2) account for 80% and 15% of the variance, respectively. As indicated by acute angles between original variable projections and axes in the PC1-PC2 biplot (Fig. 1), pebble mass corresponds most strongly to PC1, while the c dimension to PC2. In general, pebble mass appears to be the main parameter explaining the variance of the dataset. It can be interpreted as a proxy for stream-bed velocity changes over time. The antiparallel orientation of vectors representing stratigraphic height and the c dimension (Fig. 1) implies a decreasing trend of pebble thickness with increasing stratigraphic height. This negative correlation is confirmed with classical (bivariate) correlation tests. Moreover, the biplot displays evident clustering of lithological types. The centroids of convex hulls enveloping points associated with granite and quartz lithotypes are located in the upper part of the plot, those associated with sedimentary rocks (conglomerates, sandstones, and mudstones) are in the central part, and those associated with metamorphic schists and serpentinites are in the lower part (Fig. 1).

PCA results indicate that stream-bed velocity is the most influential factor shaping the vertical (stratigraphic) distribution size of pebbles. Moreover, this method allows us to generate a statistically testable hypothesis regarding vertical variability of the *c* dimension, which is subsequently confirmed by bivariate correlation analysis. Clustering of points in principal component coordinates highlights that there are some morphometric differences between lithotype classes.

Figure 1. PCA biplot displaying data points, lithotype convex hulls, and vectors representing original variables. Abbreviations: hgt = stratigraphic height, cgl = conglomerate, vcsst = very coarse-grained sandstone, csst = coarse-grained sandstone, msst = medium-grained sandstone, fsst = fine-grained sandstone, vfsst = very fine-grained sandstone, mdst = mudstone, qtz = quartz, gra = granite, gns = gneiss, msct = mica schist, gsct = greenschist, srp = serpentinite. Inset photos: general view of the outcrop (top) and detailed view of the sampled section at Kudowa-Stone (bottom).

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Initial geodiversity assessment of Ghana using GIS methods: implications for geoheritage and geoconservation

EMMANUEL OWUSU-ACHEAMPONG^{1,2} & MÁRTON PÁL²

1 – Doctoral School of Earth Sciences, Faculty of Science, ELTE Eötvös Loránd University; Budapest, Hungary; emmaoacheamp@student.elte.hu

2 – Geodiversity & Geoheritage Research Group, Institute of Cartography and Geoinformatics, Faculty of Informatics, ELTE Eötvös Loránd University; Budapest, Hungary

Geodiversity is a relatively new field of study. It refers to the heterogeneity of abiotic components of the environment. The term has been defined as the variety of geological, geomorphological, soil, hydrological, mineral, and paleontological features, including their properties and spatial-cultural-social relationships (Gray, 2004; Serrano & Ruiz-Flaño, 2007). Since the late 20th century, the analysis and assessment of geodiversity have become an essential step prior to any nature conservation and geotourism measures. Although many assessment techniques exist, two main groups can be identified: qualitative and quantitative. Quantitative assessment of abiotic elements provides a basis for identifying areas of geoheritage value and supporting geoconservation planning (Brilha, 2016).

In Ghana, geodiversity assessment remains an underexplored research area, and no national-scale quantitative assessment has yet been systematically undertaken. The country was divided into a hexagonal grid of 10 km by 10 km, and geodiversity indices were calculated for each cell using harmonised thematic datasets. Geological data (lithology; 1:250,000), soil data (soil types; 1:250,000), lakes and water bodies (hydrological features; 1:50,000), mineral and fossil occurrence data (mineralisation and palaeontological records; national inventory scale, approximately 1:5,000,000), and terrain parameters derived from a 30 m spatial resolution SRTM Digital Elevation Model (landform and topographic variables) were compiled from the databases of the Land Use and Spatial Planning Authority (LUSPSA). The 10 km grid resolution was selected to align with the 1:250,000 base mapping scale of the primary geological and soil datasets, ensuring spatial consistency. The composite geodiversity index was calculated by summing the normalised (the subindex's value in a certain grid cell divided by the maximum subindex value in the grid) subindices, following established quantitative approaches (Pereira et al., 2013; Pál & Albert, 2021).

The first two geodiversity maps of Ghana – one without normalisation and the second with normalisation – were produced using the Geodiversity Calculator v2.1 plugin developed by the authors in the QGIS 3.44.4 version interface. The plugin applies the quantitative methodology of Pál & Albert (2021) and enables evaluation of geodiversity using various grid geometries (square, diamond, hexagon). As hexagons are the simplest regular polygons with good tessellation and neighbourhood characteristics, we chose them as grid units. Thematic layers were evaluated and aggregated (with or without normalisation) in each of these spatial units using the plugin. The resulting grids were styled according to the geodiversity index values and visualised in QGIS (Figs. 1a and 1b), overlaid with protected areas (National parks).

The geodiversity map shows a clear spatial differentiation across Ghana. Higher index values are associated with areas of lithological variability, structurally controlled relief, and dissected terrain, particularly within Birimian terrains and along major escarpments. Lower values correspond to homogeneous sedimentary basins and low-relief surfaces. A comparison with existing protected areas indicates that several zones of elevated abiotic diversity remain outside current conservation frameworks.

This first assessment serves as a baseline for detecting geodiversity patterns in Ghana. It can be considered the starting point for establishing a nationwide geoheritage inventory, conducting site-scale evaluations, and advancing future geopark initiatives in Ghana. A selected location for a larger-scale assessment is the Atewa Range Forest Reserve (ARFS) and its extension, given evidence of the interplay between geodiversity and biodiversity hotspots. The ARFS and its extension comprise diverse flora and

fauna. The forest reserve hosts three major rivers, which provide water to over 5 million Ghanaians. The rocks at ARFS contain bauxite, which has led to some mining activity despite its status as a reserved forest. This has sparked several disputes between the government and local communities, which are currently under judicial consideration. A targeted assessment would underscore the area's significance for geoheritage, serve as exploratory material for geosite mapping, and provide a framework for nature management. The application of standardised GIS methods and nationally available spatial data shows that quantitative geodiversity assessment can support the integration of abiotic criteria into geoheritage management and land-use planning.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of geodiversity indices across Ghana, highlighting areas of high abiotic diversity and potential geoheritage significance (a) without and (b) with normalisation.

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Exploration of lithium-rich pegmatites and host rocks using XRF scanning in the SN-1 core from Las Navas (Cáceres, Spain)

ALEX A. ORELLANA PACHECO^{1,2,3}, E. MERINO MARTÍNEZ¹, D. OREJANA³,
J. GONZÁLEZ⁴, C. MOLINA⁴ & M. SANABRIA⁴

1 – Instituto Geológico y Minero de España, CSIC; Madrid, Spain; aleore01@ucm.es

2 – Xcalibur Smart Mapping; Madrid, Spain

3 – Facultad de CC. Geológicas, Universidad Complutense de Madrid; Madrid, Spain

4 – Litoteca de Sondeos IGME, Instituto Geológico y Minero de España, CSIC; Córdoba, Spain

Global lithium demand, driven by the energy transition, has renewed exploration interest in lithium-cesium-tantalum (LCT) type pegmatites, the primary hard-rock source of this critical element. However, lithium exploration faces a methodological challenge: portable X-ray fluorescence (pXRF), a standard field tool, cannot directly measure Li due to its low atomic weight. This limitation typically requires laboratory analysis, delaying exploration decisions by months—a critical constraint for countries, companies, and investors.

To address this problem, complementary research strategies are essential. Identifying geochemical and mineralogical correlation patterns, particularly pathfinders consistently associated with Li mineralization, can enable indirect detection using pXRF. This study investigates such relationships by conducting an integrated analysis of an archived drill core hosting Li-rich pegmatites (SN-1 drill core), by combining petrography, high-resolution scanning and pXRF analyses. There are other tools for directly measuring Li, such as portable laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS), but these are not addressed in this study.

The Las Navas-Cañaveral area in northwestern Cáceres (Spain) represents a key target for the European Union due to the presence of LCT-type pegmatites that host a Li-rich mineral assemblage comprising spodumene, amblygonite, lepidolite, cassiterite, and columbite-tantalite. Initially explored in the 1990s for their Sn and W, these pegmatites are currently under renewed investigation by Lithium Iberia and CRS Ingeniería, in partnership with IGME-CSIC through research initiatives such as PIEMAX-GEO-4TREE, a project of excellence focused on interdisciplinary research applied to topics that promote ecological and energy transition, and HELICE, a public-private partnership project (CPP2023-010560), funded by MICIU/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER, EU, focused on the research of pegmatitic bodies using numerous geochemical and multi-platform geophysical technologies and predictive modelling.

The 352 m-deep SN-1 drill core, housed in the IGME-CSIC Core repository in Peñarroya-Pueblonuevo (Córdoba, Spain), intersects Neoproterozoic metasediments of the Schist-Greywacke Complex, including slates, phyllites, and greywackes, as well as multiple Li-rich aplopegmatitic dikes (Fig. 1). In-situ geochemical analyses via high-resolution pXRF, coupled to the BoxScan multisensor core-scanning platform, were conducted on the SN-1 core. Analytical measurements were spaced at 10 cm intervals within host rocks and at 2 cm intervals within pegmatites and metasomatized zones, yielding a total of 4,452 data points. The petrographic study of the SN-1 pegmatite samples reveals three distinct pegmatite facies, which differ in texture and mineralogy, ranging from types dominated by Li phosphates, Li silicates, or a combination of both, showing variable amounts of niobium-tantalite and/or cassiterite accessory minerals. The metasedimentary host rocks show evidence of thermal metamorphism and metasomatism, as revealed by a locally mottled texture of biotite ± andalusite ± cordierite, and by an important increase in newly formed quartz, tourmaline, and mica near the pegmatites.

XRFp scanning reveals pronounced enrichments of selected incompatible elements (Rb, Sn, Nb, W, and, more interestingly, Hg), which correlate positively with Li and Cs contents in pegmatites and metasomatized host rocks. These patterns suggest that the critical elements in the pegmatite system were distinctly partitioned among the main and accessory phases of the different pegmatitic facies (e.g., Sn-W in cassiterite-wolframite; Li in spodumene, amblygonite-montebrazite, lepidolite). Such be-

haviour is probably related to the availability of volatiles and critical elements, as well as to variations in Al and Si activities, during the transition from the magmatic to the hydrothermal stages of the pegmatite system.

Mercury in pegmatites has a maximum and average value of 53 and 13 ppm, respectively, values that represent an enrichment with respect to the host rock (10 and 3 ppm, respectively), these unusual values could be explained by late hydrothermal fluids rich in S. Applying the same analysis, with the same equipment, the relationship between Rb and Hg is similar in a second drill core at Las Navas, and this behavior is not observed in two other drill cores at a nearby deposit that has the same host rock but whose pegmatites are not rich in lithium. Laboratory chemical data is currently awaited to corroborate this information.

The analyses indicate that elements such as Rb, Sn, Nb, W, P, and Hg can be considered lithium pathfinders in pXRF exploration campaigns for pegmatites or areas with intense host rock metasomatism. The intriguing correlation between Hg and Li-Rb, poorly documented in lithium-rich pegmatites, could serve as a valuable indicator of Li in pXRF exploration campaigns in pegmatitic fields and should be a potential focus of future exploration.

Figure 1. All the images below correspond to the same section of the SN-1 core. (A) The core pXRF analysis points by BoxScan. (B) Pegmatites. (C) Host rock. (D) Pegmatite image by transmitted light microscopy. (E) Same "D" Image by electron microscopy. (F) Stratigraphic column showing whole-rock Li, Cs, Rb laboratory analyses, and pXRF of analyses (Hg, U, Nb, Rb, Sn, and P).

A porphyry ore deposit in the making: unique insights into magmatic processes leading to ore fertility through the Taapaca volcano

IVÁN MATEO ESPINEL PACHÓN¹, MICHAEL SCHIRRA², ALEXANDRA TSAY¹, CRISTÓBAL GONZÁLEZ RODRÍGUEZ³, MARA MIRANDA¹ & ZOLTAN ZAJACZ¹

1 – Department of Earth Sciences, University of Geneva; Geneva, Switzerland; imespinelp@unal.edu.co

2 – Department of Geosciences, University of Nevada; Las Vegas, Nevada, USA

3 – Millennium Institute on Volcanic Risk Research - Ckelar Volcanoes; Antofagasta, Chile

Introduction

The redox state, volatile contents and differentiation history of arc magmas play a first-order control on their physical behaviour, ore fertility and capacity to release sulfur-bearing gases to the atmosphere. Oxidized, sulfur-rich magmas in thick continental arcs are particularly efficient to form porphyry Cu-(Mo-Au) deposits. Numerous studies have traditionally focused on metal sequestration and fluid exsolution processes within upper crustal magma reservoirs. However, the influence of deep crustal processes on ore fertility has gained significant attention over the past few decades. Taapaca represents a long-lived magmatic system (~1.5 Ma) developed under low magma flux conditions in a thick continental crust (Clavero et al., 2004). It produced a well-preserved volcanic sequence with rocks showing textures and major/trace element geochemistry closely resembling those of porphyry stocks associated with world-class porphyry Cu-(Mo-Au) systems. These geochemical signatures include fertility indicators such as elevated Sr/Y and La/Yb ratios, as well as low Zr concentrations. In addition, an active hydrothermal system is typically associated with the volcanism, which may very well be forming economic mineralization at depth.

Methodology

We conducted sampling across all eruptive stages and combined petrography with mineral chemistry, melt inclusion analysis, thermobarometry, and oxybarometry. Major element compositions of principal mineral phases in olivine, pyroxenes, plagioclase, amphibole, titanite, sanidine were measured by EPMA, while trace elements, S and Cl concentrations were determined by Laser Ablation Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS). Silicate melt inclusions (SMIs) were analyzed using LA-ICP-MS following the methodology of Halter et al. (2002). We applied clinopyroxene and amphibole thermobarometry to reconcile the depth of the magma reservoirs. Magma redox state was constrained using spinel-olivine pairs (Ballhaus et al, 1991), olivine-melt (Shishkina et al, 2018), and amphibole oxybarometer (Ridolfi, 2021). SMI compositions showed bimodal distribution defining mafic and rhyolitic end-members, both with elevated Sr/Y and La/Yb signatures, but the mafic melt contained overall much higher Sr, Y, La, and Yb.

Results and discussion

SMI compositions yield bimodal distribution defining mafic and rhyolitic end-members. Nickel-rich olivines (Ni=1200–2500 µg/g, Mg# ~78) in the mafic enclaves and olivine xenocrysts in a dacite preserved SMIs that record near-primitive, mantle-derived melts with basaltic to basaltic-andesitic compositions (SiO₂ 46–56 wt%), occurring together with Cr-rich spinel inclusions (Cr# 35–58). These SMIs exhibit elevated S (1700–3500 µg/g), Cl (900–2300 µg/g), Cu (70–250 µg/g) and Ag (0.1–0.25 µg/g) concentrations. These primitive mantle melts have a high Sr/Y (45–65) and La/Yb (20–40) ratios. In contrast, SMIs hosted in quartz, plagioclase and sanidine have rhyolitic composition (SiO₂ 69–76 wt%, MgO <0.1 wt%) and are particularly enriched in incompatible and fluid-mobile elements, with Sr/Y (60–500), La/Yb (30–200), Zr (30–100 µg/g), but lower S (90–250 µg/g) and highly variable Cu (20–150 µg/g).

Whole-rock compositions of andesites to dacites (54–68 wt% SiO₂) plot along mixing trends between these two end-members, and most Taapaca dacites fall within the adakite-like compositional field on ore fertility diagrams (Sr/Y 60–100, La/Yb 40–60, low Y and Yb).

Mineral thermobarometry indicates a long-lived crustal magma reservoir system. Three different generations of amphiboles: amphibole I (600–850 MPa, 1000–1050 °C; Mghastingsite), amphibole II (250–600 MPa, 875–1000 °C; Mghornblende) and amphibole III (70–250 MPa, 730–850 °C; Mghornblende) document magma storage from deep mid-crust to shallow upper crust. Importantly, amphiboles across all eruptive stages show no significant fO_2 changes regardless of the pressure they record, with consistently high values around $\Delta FMQ \sim +2$. Complementary spinel–olivine ($\Delta FMQ = +3.2 \pm 0.5$) and olivine–melt ($\Delta FMQ = +1.9 \pm 0.7$) oxybarometers further confirm that the near-primitive mantle melts were already oxidized upon arrival, indicating that magma oxidation is inherited from the source and not developed during magma differentiation. Systematic Cu and Li variations in amphibole and titanite attributed to sub-microscopic fluid inclusions reveal volatile saturation at mid- and upper crustal depths.

Conclusions

Taapaca's ore-fertile character arises primarily from magma mixing between oxidized, S- and Cu-rich near-primitive mantle melts and crystal-rich, high-silica rhyolitic mushes, rather than from deep fractional crystallization alone. The near-primitive mantle melts are already oxidized, suggesting that magma oxidation is inherited from the source and not developed during magma differentiation. The mafic melts supply most of the volatile and ore metal budgets of the hybrid dacites and primarily impose their high Sr/Y–La/Yb signature. Repeated mafic recharge in the upper and/or mid-crust (~250–600 MPa) thermally rejuvenates mushy reservoirs, reduces viscosity, develops interconnected percolation networks, and sustains volatile saturation over >1Ma. Taapaca thus serves as a rare volcanic exposure capturing essential preconditioning for porphyry Cu systems: source-inherited oxidation, mixing, and long-lived mush thermally sustained by exsolved fluids generated during recharge in middle and upper crustal levels.

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Geomorphodynamic analysis of post-eruptive tephra remobilisations triggered by non-Newtonian flows (lahars) at Tajogaite volcano

MARTA PASTOR¹, JULIO GARROTE², ANDRÉS DÍEZ³ & DANIEL VÁZQUEZ³

1 – Instituto Geológico y Minero de España; Madrid, Spain; m.pastor@igme.es

2 – Universidad Complutense de Madrid; Madrid, Spain

3 – Instituto Geológico y Minero de España, Madrid, Spain

During the 2021 eruption of the Tajogaite volcano on La Palma, in the Canary Islands, approximately 45 million cubic metres of volcanic material were deposited across the landscape. When exposed to subsequent rainfall, this loose material became unstable and in several cases was mobilised downslope as secondary flows, referred to here as remobilisations. Similar events elsewhere in the world have caused significant damage and loss of life (Voight, 1990; Carracedo, 2015), making it important to understand what drives them and where they are likely to occur.

This study focuses on a set of remobilisations triggered by a storm event in 2023, with two main objectives: to identify which physical factors control whether and how these flows develop, and to produce a map indicating which parts of the affected area are most susceptible to future events of this kind.

The first step was to evaluate how well remotely sensed data, specifically a digital elevation model constructed from aerial photogrammetry, could substitute for direct field measurements, which is relevant for future events where rapid assessment is needed and fieldwork may not be immediately possible. Once the data sources were validated, each remobilisation was characterised geometrically, measuring parameters such as deposit length and terrain slope, and these were compared across all cases to look for consistent patterns. The analysis also incorporated information on ground cover, since the type of surface material present at the source area was expected to influence flow initiation.

Ground cover emerged as one of the most important factors controlling whether a remobilisation occurred at all. Slope, by contrast, had less influence on triggering, but played a major role in determining how far and how extensively a flow developed once it began.

Drawing on these results, a lahar susceptibility map was produced for the tephra-covered area by combining four spatial layers: terrain slope, flow accumulation, ground cover type, and the extent of tephra deposits. Each layer was weighted according to its relative importance as determined by the analysis. The model was then calibrated and validated against the observed remobilisations, which all fell within zones classified as having high susceptibility, supporting the reliability of the approach.

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The Brzechów Lagerstätte – an exceptionally preserved fauna in Cambrian coarse sandstones of the Holy Cross Mountains (Poland)

KAMIL POTERALSKI¹

1 – Doctoral School of Exact and Natural Sciences, University of Warsaw; Warsaw, Poland;
k.poteralski@uw.edu.pl

Brzechów is a small village located to the east of Kielce city and geologically lying within the Palaeozoic inlier of the Holy Cross Mountains (HCM). The palaeontological site in Brzechów, known already for a hundred years (Czarnocki, 1927), yields abundant and well-preserved fossils, found in sandstones of the Stowiec Formation from the Cambrian Series 2/Miaolingian boundary interval (Nowicki & Żylińska, 2019). However, the fossiliferous sandstones are confined to an isolated location in the form of loose boulders found on fields, which has hindered the recognition of their broader geological context. Since the first mention, some of the fossils have been the subject of a number of publications, which focused largely on descriptions and revisions of trilobites (e.g. Żylińska & Masiak, 2007). However, the most intriguing fossils known from Brzechów belong to the enigmatic group of the deuterostome clade, i.e. the Eldoniata, and are represented by two species: the common *Velumbrella czarnockii* (Fig. 1) and the sporadically occurring *Maoyanidiscus* sp. (Stasińska, 1960; Masiak & Żylińska, 1994).

Newly collected specimens of the Eldoniata, as well as those coming from a vast collection acquired in the last decades, have enabled conducting a refined populational analysis and a preliminary taphonomic analysis. Detailed geological mapping of the study area combined with the reinterpretation of archival data have enabled a preliminary interpretation of the exact stratigraphic position within the Cambrian litostratigraphic scheme of the HCM, and to narrow down the possible interpretation of the depositional setting of the fossiliferous sandstones.

The folded and bent discoidal fossils of *Velumbrella czarnockii* indicate that its tissues were susceptible to elastic and plastic deformations during the burial process, thus they represent imprints of soft tissues. The discs are uniquely preserved as 3D moulds in coarse sandstones. This kind of preservation represents an virtually unprecedented taphonomy in the Phanerozoic, comparable only with the fossilization of the enigmatic Ediacaran biota, with the greatest resemblance to the 'Nama-style preservation' most notably known from the Nama Group in Namibia (Narbonne, 2005). Thus, Brzechów, similarly to the Namibian fauna, may be considered as an example of Konservat-Lagerstätte, i.e. a deposit which provides insight into the existence of organisms that would otherwise remain unknown because of their very poor fossilization potential. Moreover, probable scavenging traces are reported here for the first time from the fossils of *V. czarnockii*. Recent fieldwork has revealed that the fossiliferous strata occur in a narrow - less than 100 m wide, but 2.5 km long strip of land. Based on the local lithological and biostratigraphic context, the sandstones are preliminarily assigned to the FSST of sequence LC2-5 in the sequence stratigraphic scheme for Baltica (Nielsen & Schovsbo, 2011), and are interpreted as interbeds with high energy sedimentation within the fine-grained siliciclastic background.

Due to its unprecedented preservation of soft-bodied organisms, the Brzechów fossil site should be regarded as one of the very few Polish Konservat-Lagerstätten, and for this reason, further research of the locality is highly anticipated.

Figure 1. A well-preserved specimen of *Velumbrella czarnockii* with a trail on its surface, which is interpreted as a possible scavenging trace (highlighted in red and indicated by a white arrow).

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Fluid characteristics and genesis of the Bieber podložná vein in Banská Štiavnica

JAKUB PRCÚCH¹, PETER KODĚRA¹

1 – Department of Mineralogy, Petrology and Economic Geology, Faculty of Natural Sciences, Comenius University; Bratislava, Slovakia; j.prcuch@gmail.com

The Bieber podložná vein is part of a low- to intermediate-sulfidation epithermal vein system developed in the central part of the caldera of the Štiavnica Stratovolcano. These veins are related to the uplift of the resurgent horst in the center of the caldera (12.2–10.9 Ma; Konečný et al., 1998; Lexa et al., 2025). The Bieber podložná vein is currently exploited by Slovenská Banská s.r.o. due to the presence of Au-Ag mineralization. This mineralization is atypically developed in the deeper segments of the vein, corresponding to the copper zone of the vein system (sensu Koděra, 1963), with chalcopyrite as the dominant sulfide mineral. The precious metal mineralization differs from that in the Au-Ag zone occurring in the upper parts of the vein system. Gold is associated with fine-grained quartz, hematite and Bi-(Ag) sulfosalts, mostly matildite, schirmerite, arcubisite and sulfosalts of lillianite homologous series (Chovan et al., 2021; 2023), and represents the youngest mineral assemblage of the 4th stage of mineralization in the base metal horst veins of Banská Štiavnica (Kovalenker et al., 1991). Mineralogical research was carried out on representative samples from the Bieber podložná vein containing both precious and base metal mineralization, variably with brecciated, banded and cockade textures. The samples predominantly contain coarse-grained chalcopyrite, galena and fine-grained hematite with coarse- to fine-grained quartz, and more rarely sphalerite and carbonates (predominantly calcite). The mineralization is mostly developed in moderately to strongly altered andesite and, more rarely, in quartz-diorite porphyry. Hydrothermal alteration was studied in selected samples from both the hanging wall and footwall of the vein using XRD analysis and polarized light microscopy. The following minerals were identified: K-feldspar (20–55 wt.%), quartz (15–50 wt.%), sericite (5–38 wt.%), and chlorite (1–12 wt.%), with subordinate kaolinite, epidote, and calcite, and locally dickite and pyrite (all < 4 wt.%). This mineral association is typical for intermediate sulfidation veins with adularia-sericite alteration, corresponding to fluids with nearly neutral pH. However, locally the pH may have been lower, due to the minor presence of kaolinite and dickite.

Microthermometric research was carried out on two-phase (L+V) primary and secondary fluid inclusions hosted in quartz, sphalerite, and calcite. Both primary and secondary fluid inclusions in quartz exhibited comparable characteristics, defined by two homogenization temperature (Th) intervals of 240–290 °C and 170–210 °C. Their salinities range from 0 to 7 wt.% NaCl eq., predominantly between 2 and 5 wt.% NaCl eq. Primary inclusions in sphalerite show Th values in the range of 200–230 °C and salinities of 2.5–3.5 wt.% NaCl eq. Secondary inclusions in sphalerite yield Th values of 180–200 °C and salinities of 0.5–3 wt.% NaCl eq. Secondary fluid inclusions in calcite show salinities of 5.5–6 wt.% NaCl eq. and Th values of 160–190 °C. Eutectic temperatures were measured in primary inclusions in quartz in the interval from -24.5 to -20.4 °C. Previous microthermometric research (Jeleň et al. in Petr et al., 1993) showed Th values for minerals of the 4th stage in horst-related veins Bieber, Terézia and Špitáľ in intervals of 177–334 °C for quartz, 213–312 °C for scheelite, 202–296 °C for adularia, 213–312 °C for carbonates, and 141–224 °C for sphalerite of the 5th stage. Eutectic temperatures were measured in an interval from -35 to -21°C.

Sulfur isotope analyses of selected sulfides from the 4th mineralization stage provided $\delta^{34}\text{S}$ values of 1.9–4.1‰ for galena, 4.2–5.6‰ for chalcopyrite, 6.6–7‰ for pyrite, 2.7–5.2‰ for sphalerite and -12.3‰ for marcasite. Previous isotope analyses of 4th stage sulfides from the Bieber podložná vein yielded values of 3.7‰ for pyrite, 3.0–8.4‰ for sphalerite, -4.9–6.8‰ for galenite and -6.7–8.0‰ for chalcopyrite (Jeleň et al. in Petr et al., 1993).

Bieber podložná vein, based on its homogenisation temperatures, salinities and types of textures and hydrothermal alteration, shows characteristics typical of low to intermediate sulfidation mineralization. The two Th intervals observed in quartz inclusions probably correspond to two generations of quartz formed during the 4th mineralization stage.

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RGB or LiDAR? A quantitative comparison of UAV-based 3D geosite models

EDINA PÁL-HAJDÚ^{1,2}, MÁRTON PÁL², ANDRÁS JUNG² & GÁSPÁR ALBERT²

1 – ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Science, Doctoral School of Earth Science; Budapest, Hungary; hajdu.edina@inf.elte.hu.

2 – ELTE Eötvös Loránd University, Faculty of Informatics, Institute of Cartography and Geoinformatics, Geodiversity & Geoheritage Research Group; Budapest, Hungary

High-resolution remote sensing with UAVs has become an essential component of geosite mapping and geoconservation (Bemis et al., 2014; Kovanič et al., 2023). In the context of a geopark, such as our sample area, the Bakony–Balaton UNESCO Global Geopark, digital textured 3D models can be used for geotourism and scientific purposes, as well as for management decisions. However, the wider adoption of LiDAR technology raises the question of whether its higher cost and greater complexity are justified compared to RGB photogrammetry.

The main research question of this study is: Does UAV-based LiDAR technology offer a significant improvement in model quality over RGB photogrammetry for geotourism-oriented visualisation and decision support at small to medium-sized geosites? The aim is to compare the applicability of the quantitative parameters of the models created from RGB and LiDAR data.

Three geosite models were surveyed at flight heights of 25 and 30 m: the coastal escarpment in Balatonkenese exposing Late Miocene–Pleistocene deposits, the Permian-Triassic key section in Csopak, and the Permian red sandstone section of the Lake Köcsi quarry in Balatonalmádi. RGB images (DJI P1) and LiDAR points (DJI L1) were captured with the same UAV system. High-density point clouds and 3D mesh models were generated using both sensors, with detailed quantitative parameters summarized in Table 1. The results show a significant discrepancy in data density: RGB photogrammetry consistently produced point clouds and mesh models one to two orders of magnitude denser than the LiDAR system. While RGB-derived DEMs reached sub-centimetre resolutions (3.45–9.25 mm/pixel), the LiDAR datasets remained significantly sparser across all study sites.

The quantitative analysis clearly shows that, for low-altitude surveying (25–30 m) and well-exposed rock outcrops, the geometric detail of RGB photogrammetry is significantly higher. The order-of-magnitude difference in point density and mesh resolution directly carries over into the level of detail of the surface representation of stratification, bedding planes, erosional microforms, and human-induced features. This discrepancy is partly due to the specific technical characteristics of the DJI L1 sensor. Its higher noise level and lower point density compared to photogrammetric reconstruction prevents sub-centimetre surface textures from being captured. Moreover, the RGB orthomosaics offer high-quality textures, which are essential for geotourism visualisation and educational purposes. The competitive advantage of LiDAR does not reside in the actual geometric density at this scale but in structural robustness, vegetation penetration, and insensitivity to illumination conditions. In areas with partial vegetation cover or complex topography, LiDAR might offer superior bare-earth models. Nevertheless, in open quarry faces and cliffs, typical of the geosites investigated, the additional cost of LiDAR does not provide a proportionally higher level of detail useful for tourism or general management planning (Burai et al., 2025).

From a decision-making perspective, the findings of this study indicate that under the tested conditions using the DJI L1 system, the sub-centimetre resolution of RGB-derived DEMs and orthomosaics already exceeds the required resolution for most geotouristic, geoeducational, and interpretive purposes. Consequently, for small- to medium-sized, well-exposed geosites, RGB photogrammetry can be considered a cost-effective, sufficiently accurate method. LiDAR technology only gains a strategic advantage when filtering vegetation, terrain observation, or hazard mapping requires unobstructed, vegetation-penetrating elevation information.

In summary, the choice between RGB and LiDAR technology should be technology-independent and instead guided by objective-driven decision-making. For tourism-related documentation and general geosite management in well-exposed lithological sections, RGB modelling is sufficient. LiDAR technology adds value only in cases with specific geomorphological or environmental constraints.

Table 1. Key features of 3D models, DEMs, and orthomosaics produced using traditional RGB photogrammetry and LiDAR processing.

Geosites	Flight altitude (m)	RGB camera					LiDAR	
		Number of aligned pictures	Dense point cloud (points)	3D model resolution (model faces)	DEM resolution	Ortho-mosaic resolution	Point cloud (points)	3D model resolution (model faces)
Balatonkenese, coastal escarpment	30	479	250,944,816	16,086,818	1.36 cm/pix	6.81 mm/pix	35,822,844	9,183,685
Csopak, Permian–Triassic boundary	30	177	120,519,974	9,472,180	9.25 mm/pix	4.63 mm/pix	649,647	166,739
Balatonalmádi, Permian key section of the Lake Köcsi quarry	25	96	73,165,403	3,749,307	6.9 mm/pix	3.45 mm/pix	4,884,231	1,558,673

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Sorption of selenium on iron oxide-based composite material

ALEKSANDER SACZKA¹ & TOMASZ BAJDA¹

1 – Department of Mineralogy, Petrography and Geochemistry, Faculty of Geology, Geophysics and Environmental Protection, AGH University of Krakow; Krakow, Poland; oleksaczka@student.agh.edu.pl

Selenium is a micronutrient essential for human physiological processes, yet it exhibits a narrow concentration range between beneficial and toxic effects. Anthropogenic activities often release significant quantities of selenium into aquatic environments, posing risks to both ecosystem stability and human health.

This research evaluates the efficacy of ferruginous sludge, a byproduct from wastewater treatment, as a potential sorbent for selenium removal. The material was characterized using various analytical techniques to evaluate its structural composition and surface morphology.

Three series of batch sorption experiments were conducted to provide a comprehensive assessment of the process; pH studies across a pH range of 2.0 to 10.0 at a constant Se concentration; equilibrium isotherms with initial concentrations from 5 to 300 mg/L; kinetic experiments performed at constant concentration for up to 48 hours. Selenium concentrations in the aqueous phase were determined using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS). To ensure the stability of the Se (IV) and Se (VI) oxidation states, the redox potential of the solutions was monitored, confirming that no significant species transformation occurred during contact with the ferruginous sludge.

Results demonstrated that selenium removal is highly pH-dependent, with optimal performance occurring at pH 4.0–5.0. The sorbent showed a significantly higher affinity for selenite [Se(IV)] than selenate [Se(VI)], with maximum adsorption capacities of 42.5 mg/g and 15.8 mg/g respectively, and removal efficiencies exceeding 85% for Se(IV) at acidic pH.

The experimental equilibrium data were interpreted using various mathematical models to describe the adsorption mechanisms and surface interactions. These included the Langmuir and Freundlich models, the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) model, and the Sips (Langmuir-Freundlich). Additionally, the Temkin model (Temkin and Pyzhev, 1940) was applied to evaluate the effects of sorbate-sorbent interactions on the adsorption energy. Among the tested mathematical models, the Sips (Langmuir-Freundlich) model provided the best fit to the experimental data, indicating that adsorption occurs on a heterogeneous surface with a combination of monolayer coverage and cooperative interactions. The findings suggest that ferruginous sludge is a highly effective and cost-efficient material for Se(IV) remediation, though its applicability for Se(VI) is limited to more acidic conditions. This study confirms that repurposing industrial byproducts for water treatment offers a sustainable solution for mitigating selenium contamination in industrial effluents, contributing to both waste valorisation and environmental protection.

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Electrical resistivity tomography and time-domain induced polarization for stibnite vein exploration in the Trojane Area, Slovenia

KILLIAN SANDFORD¹, JOSEPHMARTIN KORIE¹,
EDMUNDO PLACENCIA¹ & KLEMEN TERAN¹

1 – Geological Survey of Slovenia (GeoZS); Ljubljana, Slovenia; killiansandford@gmail.com

Antimony (Sb) is classified as a critical mineral for Europe due to its strategic importance and high supply risk (European Commission, 2023). Improving the identification of potential antimony deposits and refining exploration techniques for such deposits are therefore necessary to mitigate supply vulnerabilities. The investigated target covers an area of approximately 10 × 4 km southeast of Trojane, Slovenia, an historical antimony mining district. The geology consists mainly of Carboniferous sedimentary sequences, dominated by black shale and sandstone. These lithologies host fracture-control sub-vertical quartz–stibnite (Sb₂S₂) veins with reported thicknesses ranging from 3 to 20 cm and associated silicification with few other sulfides (Mlakar et al., 1983). The exact locations of many of these veins are not well-known, and most are no longer exposed to the surface due to erosion and land use, which complicates direct geological mapping (Mlakar et al., 1983).

This setting may have similitude with gold-bearing quartz veins, with no major sulfides associated, as these veins are also discordant and fracture-controlled. Gold-bearing quartz veins can be explored with Direct Current resistivity and time-domain Induced Polarization (DCIP), as the quartz vein along with silicification can provide a resistive signal compared to the host rock (Irvine & Smith, 1990). The resistive response of such deposit should be between 1000-12 000 Ω.m (D'amours, 1996). Considering that Au-quartz veins and quartz-stibnite veins may have similar electrical characteristics, the expected resistivity contrast between conductive black shales (0.1 - 10 Ω.m) (D'amours, 1996) and resistive quartz veins with silicification and low sulfides (1000-12 000 Ω.m) (D'amours, 1996) suggests that detectable anomalies may be produced. However, the presence of local sandstone layers, which also produce a resistive signal (50-4000 Ω.m) (D'amours, 1996) can pose a challenge. Nevertheless, the main host lithology for the veins is black shale. For IP, black shales should have a value around 50 ms (D'amours, 1996) and sandstone 3 to 12 ms (Telford et al., 1990). The primary objective of this study is to assess the capability of DCIP measurements to identify quartz-stibnite related resistive anomalies and IP-effect to detect presence of sulfides. This exploration approach for quartz-stibnite veins has not yet been reported in the literature, only for related deposits.

DCIP surveys were conducted at several sites in the Trojane area. Data acquisition used dipole-dipole and Wenner arrays, which were selected to balance lateral and vertical resolution. Reciprocal measurements were performed to assess data quality and improve reliability. Electrode spacing ranged between 1-2 m to enhance sensitivity to the target. The electrode spacings were chosen based on forward modelling in ResIPy software and historical information on veins from Mlakar et al. (1983). All measurements were carried out using an ABEM Terameter LS2, using a 100 % duty cycle and a 2-second injection time. Data processing and inversion were performed primarily using ResIPy and Res2DInv.

In a general way, DCIP results distinguish the main host lithologies (sandstones and black shales). Sandstone units display high resistivity along with low IP-effect, while black shale exhibits lower resistivity values along with high phase angle values. At the Brezje_1 survey line, discrete high-resistivity anomalies occur at shallow depths between approximately 1-3 m (Fig. 1). These anomalies spatially coincide with historical vein locations mapped by Hinterlechner (1918), and the only lithology on this line is supposed to be sandstone, so the resistive anomaly can be the quartz veins or fracture. Sandstone can't be rejected. Zones of high resistivity interpreted as possible quartz veins do not exhibit a strong or consistent IP response, this may discriminate them from sandstone.

Results suggest high-resistivity anomalies associated with the expected position of stibnite veins in the Trojane area. The resistive anomaly may be the consequence of a silicification area around the vein. Sandstone is an option, even if it is not reported in the area where veins were targeted (Mlakar & Drovenik, 1983). As well as brittle or fragile deformation other than the fracture of the vein which is filled. IP-effect in terms of the phase angle was less effective for direct vein detection. The lack of a distinguishable IP-effect response linked to the presence of stibnite veins could be attributed to a weak contrast with the IP-effect of black shales and the lack of sulfides. Therefore, DCIP provides a probable resistive signal for quartz-stibnite veins in conductive black shale-hosted systems, marking the first instance of using resistivity for stibnite vein exploration in the Trojane area. The IP method appears less suitable for such deposits. Further investigation is required to reduce uncertainty on the method.

Figure 1. Resistivity (magnitude) and phase angle (IP-effect) results from the Brezje_1 Dipole-Dipole profile, showing a high-resistivity anomaly along with low IP-effect interpreted as possible stibnite veins relative to black shale host rock.

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New ore exploration efforts and geochemical research linking magmatism and mineralization in western Bohemia

VÁCLAV SANTOLÍK^{1,2}

1 – Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague; Czech Republic

2 – Geological Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences; Prague, Czech Republic; santolik@gli.cas.cz

The global transition to low-carbon energy systems is driving a rapid increase in demand for metals essential for batteries, electronics, and renewable technologies. These include for example Li, V, Ni, Co, Cu, rare earth elements (REE), and platinum group elements (PGE). Our ongoing research focuses on ore deposits of these metals in western Bohemia, identifying processes of their formation, and linking them to ancient plutonic magmatism. The studied area is situated at the interface between the Teplá-Barrandian Unit and the Moldanubian Unit (Vejnar, 1984). The region hosts numerous plutonic bodies ranging from gabbroic to granitic compositions, such as the Kdyně, Poběžovice, and Mutěnin Massifs, as well as spatially and genetically related pegmatites. The gabbroic rocks are known to contain Ti-V-PGE mineralization, while the pegmatites may host Li- and REE-bearing mineral assemblages (Vejnar, 1984).

Based on current constraints, these rocks intruded during at least two major magmatic episodes: 1) Cambrian event commonly attributed to collapse of the Cadomian accretionary orogen, and 2) Devonian/Carboniferous event related to the Variscan collisional orogen (Dörr et al., 2002; Dörr and Zulauf, 2010). However, very little is known about the age of the mineralization as well as about the processes that formed the ore deposits (Glodny et al., 1998; Vejnar, 1984).

We hypothesize that (i) mineralization processes during both Cadomian and Variscan events are associated with the collapse of the respective orogens. (ii) Variscan and Cadomian gabbroids, syenitoids, and pegmatites record distinct structural, geochemical, and mineralogical compositions reflecting their contrasting petrogenesis. (iii) Cadomian (Cambro-Ordovician) magmatism represents a more important metallogenic event than previously thought.

To test these hypotheses, we apply a multi-proxy approach combining detailed field observations and petrography with U–Pb zircon/apatite geochronology, whole-rock major and trace-element geochemistry, Sr–Nd isotope analyses, and in-situ mineral chemistry using electronmicroprobe and scanning electron microscope techniques.

Preliminary data suggest that the gabbroids and granitoids related to the final stages of the Cadomian Orogen intruded later (ca. 505 Ma) than initially assumed (ca. 525 Ma; Dörr et al., 2002), hence, temporally closer to the reported magmatic age of the potentially related pegmatites (ca. 480 Ma; Glodny et al., 1998). The bulk-rock geochemistry of the Cambrian plutonic rocks also shows a combination of rocks formed by fractional crystallization, crystal accumulation, and crustal anatexis. The intermediate to felsic rocks are largely barren (except for the Li-bearing pegmatites), while the mafic rocks, including a unique Zr-rich ferrodiorite, host pyrite/pyrrhotite mineralization. Interestingly, the Variscan rocks show a very similar spectrum of rock types and possibly also similar mineralization processes, which may imply a comparable ore-deposit potential. Altogether, these initial findings provide a foundation for ongoing research aimed at better constraining the magmatic and mineralization processes in western Bohemia.

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Development of a GIS-based biodiversity credit assessment platform for Natura 2000 areas in Hungary

NADA SATTAR¹, ZSÓFIA VARGA¹

1 – Institute of Cartography and Geoinformatics, Faculty of Informatics, Eötvös Loránd University; Budapest, Hungary; nadasattar0702@gmail.com

Ongoing environmental pressures across Europe necessitate spatially explicit approaches to biodiversity conservation. Hungary, as part of the Natura 2000 ecological network, contains extensive protected areas; however, many habitats remain in suboptimal condition due to land-use change and fragmentation (e.g., Mihók et al., 2017). This highlights the need for decision-support systems integrating ecological indicators with accessible geospatial technologies.

This study presents the development of a Geographic Information System (GIS)-based platform for calculating and visualizing biodiversity credit values for Natura 2000 sites in Hungary. Biodiversity credits represent quantifiable improvements in ecological conditions resulting from conservation interventions. The platform applies a transparent and replicable methodology to identify areas of ecological importance and restoration potential.

The assessment framework integrates ecological and spatial datasets from European and national sources (European Environment Agency, 2022). Three core indicators were selected: species richness (by taxonomic groups), habitat condition, and site area. These variables were standardized and combined into a composite biodiversity credit score. The credit value reflects the difference between the current ecological state and the estimated potential state across each site. The use of taxonomic-specific species richness improves ecological accuracy and reduces bias associated with generalized species counts.

Spatial data processing was conducted in QGIS, including data harmonization and attribute standardization. The processed datasets were implemented in a web-based GIS environment using Leaflet.js (Agafonkin, 2015). The platform enables interactive visualization and analysis of biodiversity credit categories (low, medium, high), along with spatial filtering, user-defined area selection, and real-time credit calculation. Results reveal significant regional variation in ecological value, with higher scores in less disturbed and more diverse areas, and lower scores in fragmented landscapes.

The proposed model provides a transparent and scalable framework for identifying priority areas for conservation and restoration. It supports spatially informed decision-making and improves accessibility to complex ecological data. The platform demonstrates the potential of web-based GIS tools in advancing data-driven biodiversity conservation in Hungary.

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of biodiversity credit categories across Hungarian Natura 2000 sites, highlighting regional contrasts and priority areas for restoration.

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Investigation of unusual phases found in flue dust samples from a copper smelter waste heat boiler, Głogów, Poland

KRZYSZTOF SETKIEWICZ^{1,2}, KATARZYNA ROGÓŻ³,
TOMASZ KRZYKAWSKI¹ & KRZYSZTOF SZOPA¹

1 – Institute of Earth Sciences, University of Silesia in Katowice; Sosnowiec, Poland;

krzysztof.setkiewicz@us.edu.pl

2 – Quality Research Centre Ltd.; Lubin, Poland

3 – KGHM Polska Miedź S.A.; Lubin, Poland;

Smelter is a crucial installation for copper production. The widely used flash smelting technology utilises a waste heat boiler to recover heat from the process and routes off-gas to a sulphuric acid plant. This gas contains suspended semi-molten flue dust particles that can stick to boiler wall and tubes, creating accretions. These hard grow-ups hinder heat recovery due to their thermal insulation and may cause damage to the installation if not removed (Miettinen, 2008; Ranki-Kilpinen, 2004; Fernández-Caliani et al., 2017). The research focuses on determining dust phase composition and structure in order to gain information about accretion growth.

Samples were taken from the radiation section of the waste heat boiler at the Głogów smelter, Poland. Several analytical methods were utilised to measure flue dust and accretion samples, including SEM-EDS empowered by MLA (Mineral Liberation Analysis) mapping and EPMA (Electron Probe Microanalysis).

The results showed that flue dust particles consist of silicate glass associated with metallic oxides, anhydrite and various other sulphates as well as some arsenates. Smaller dust particles present in spherule shape have features of very rapid cooling as they contain many different elements, including calcium, iron and copper. Inside larger accretions glass phase shows signs of differentiation – it has lower amounts of metallic elements as well as no calcium, which from anhydrite crystals. Among metallic oxides most commonly appear analogues of complex spinels abundant in iron and copper, delafossite CuFeO_2 and copper oxides. A rare copper-bearing pyroxene has also been confirmed. EPMA measurement indicates its formula as $(\text{Cu,Mg})\text{MgSi}_2\text{O}_6$. These phases can be seen as small crystals that have separated from the melt that creates the glass phase.

Among sulphates a number of uncommon phases were identified. These include anglesite PbSO_4 , copper-bearing phases like chalcocyanite CuSO_4 as well as complex sulphates, such as varieties of potassium-bearing phase known in nature as langbeinite $\text{K}_2\text{Mg}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$. Several types of copper arsenates were also measured. EPMA analysis confirmed the presence of a phase known as popovite $\text{Cu}_5\text{O}_2(\text{AsO}_4)_2$ as well as a different copper magnesium arsenate. Most of these phases share a common locality in nature – Kamchatka's fumaroles (Vergasova & Filatov, 2016). The MLA mapping allowed for structural insight of the samples, showing that potassium-bearing sulphates, arsenates and lead sulphates occur in between anhydrite crystals, acting as a matrix for them (Fig. 1).

Acquired data allowed to identify factors affecting accretion growth in the waste heat boiler. Phases with low melting points, such as mentioned potassium-bearing sulphates, are likely stick to boiler walls and bind other particles. This information can be used to adjust the smelting process parameters to prevent flue dust from accumulating on boiler walls. The research also provides details on rare phases' chemical and structural features.

Figure 1. BSE and MLA image comparison – inner part of an accretion sample. Euhedral anhydrite crystals present within the accretion pores are bound by potassium-bearing sulphates and arsenates.

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Ghost of seagrasses past: Early Pleistocene assemblages from Rhodes Island

SANAH SHAIKH¹, KATARÍNA HOLCOVÁ¹, MARTINA HAVELCOVÁ²,
MARKÉTA CHROUSTOVÁ¹, KATARÍNA ŠARINOVÁ³, FILIP SCHEINER¹, PETR KRAFT¹,
IVANA SÝKOROVÁ² & RASTISLAV MILOVSKÝ⁴

1 – Institute of Geology and Palaeontology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; sanahshahid@gmail.com

2 – The Institute of Rock Structure and Mechanics of the Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic; Prague, Czech Republic

3 – Department of Mineralogy, Petrology and Economic Geology, Faculty of Natural Sciences Comenius University in Bratislava; Bratislava, Slovakia

4 – Earth Science Institute of the Slovak Academy of Sciences; Banská Bystrica, Slovakia

Seagrass meadows constitute habitats of high ecological importance owing to their significant role in ocean primary productivity, carbon cycling and storage (Hemminga & Duarte, 2000). Although their pronounced ecological and economical significance in the contemporary world is well-recognized, their identification in the geological history remains limited, primarily due to the scarcity of fossil preservation. Recognizing their presence in the geological record would provide vital insights into their ecological responses to different environmental changes and ecosystem resilience through time (Duarte et al., 2013). Because seagrass fossils are rare, their presence is instead inferred from organisms closely associated with seagrasses (Koskeridou et al., 2018) and from organic geochemical data, especially *n*-alkanes (Xu et al., 2006).

This study presents a biogeochemical analysis of Pliocene–Pleistocene deposits on Rhodes Island, Greece, that contain well-preserved seagrass (*Posidonia oceanica*) body fossils and seagrass-associated sediments. The succession was deposited in a delta-influenced, very shallow coastal setting, recording a transition from fluvial to protected nearshore lagoonal-inner shelf conditions favourable for seagrass development (Moissette et al., 2016). Organic geochemical analyses of modern *P. oceanica* (dead and partially decomposed material) were conducted to establish comparative lipid biomarker signatures. In addition, seagrass-associated fauna was examined to provide indirect evidence of seagrass presence.

Our findings indicate that the fossilised *P. oceanica* from Rhodes Island is characterised by peaks in C21, C23, and C25 *n*-alkanes, typical of submerged embryophytes (Ficken et al., 2000). The absence of seagrass associated organisms (foraminifera, bryozoans and molluscs) suggests that the accumulation is allochthonous. This interpretation is further supported by sedimentological evidence, including cross-bedding, and by $\delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{org}}$ values (–25 to –23.5‰), which are consistent with a brackish depositional environment (Lamb et al., 2006). Elevated concentrations of Ni (720–1100 ppm) and Co (41–60 ppm) point to a basic/ultrabasic (ophiolitic) sediment source in the catchment (Herzberg et al., 2016). Interestingly, Rhodes samples lacking *Posidonia* body fossils share the same geochemical fingerprints as the fossil material, indicating the presence of amorphous organic matter of seagrass origin. In contrast, modern decomposed in situ seagrass shows lower C21, C23 and C25 *n*-alkanes abundances and a stronger contribution from cyanobacteria and microalgae (C15, C17 and C19; Xu et al., 2006). Together, these results demonstrate that organic geochemical proxies can reliably identify ancient seagrass meadows even when body fossils are absent.

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Theoretical CO₂ storage capacity of coal seams of the Ostrava Formation: characterization and CSLF-based estimation

AHMED SIDIQ¹, JAGAR A. ALI¹, EVA GERSLOVA²,
ALEXANDRA RANCOVÁ³ & MARDIN ABDALQADIR⁴

1 – Department of Geology, Faculty of Science, Palacký University; Olomouc, Czech Republic; Ahmedfaraidoonsidiq.sidiq01@upol.cz; Jagar.ali@upol.cz

2 – Institute of Geological Engineering, Faculty of Mining and Geology, VSB – Technical University of Ostrava; Ostrava-Poruba, Czech Republic

3 – Regional Centre of Advanced Technologies and Materials, Department of Physical Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Palacký University; Olomouc, Czech Republic.

4 – Energy Academy, Newcastle College University Centre; Newcastle upon Tyne, United Kingdom

Carbon capture and storage (CCUS) is increasingly recognised as a necessary technology for reducing CO₂ emissions from hard-to-abate industrial sectors. Geological storage represents the most mature pathway for long-term mitigation. However, its deployment depends on reliable screening of subsurface formations and realistic estimation of storage capacity during early assessment stages (Bashir et al., 2024). While deep saline aquifers and depleted hydrocarbon reservoirs have received the greatest attention, un-mineable coal seams are also considered as viable storage options due to their strong affinity for CO₂ adsorption and their potential for methane displacement. The suitability of coal seams for CO₂ storage is strongly controlled by coal quality and mineralogical composition, which directly influence adsorption behaviour and storage efficiency (Wu et al., 2023).

Coal samples from the Ostrava Formation were subjected to proximate analysis and X-ray diffraction to characterize their organic and inorganic fractions within the context of CO₂ storage assessment. Proximate analysis yielded moisture of 1.44 %, volatile matter of 22.27 %, fixed carbon of 62.15 %, and ash content of 13.84 %. The relatively low inherent moisture suggests limited pore-space occupation by water, which may favour CO₂ adsorption, whereas the ash fraction reflects a measurable inorganic component that may reduce the effective organic adsorption surface. The balance between volatile matter and fixed carbon is consistent with a bituminous coal rank (Phengsaart et al., 2023).

Mineralogical characterization by X-ray diffraction indicates a silicate-dominated assemblage composed primarily of quartz (SiO₂), chlorite–serpentine group minerals, muscovite, and albite, with minor accessory silicate phases. Quartz provides a mechanically stable framework, while mixed layered clay and mica minerals may contribute surface and interlayer sites relevant to gas–solid interaction. The presence of feldspar suggests potential mineral reactivity under CO₂-bearing aqueous conditions.

These physicochemical characteristics provide geological context for the application of the Carbon Sequestration Leadership Forum (CSLF) methodology, which was used independently to estimate storage capacity based on available seam parameters. The calculated initial gas in place (IGIP) is 105 × 10⁶ m³, yielding a theoretical CO₂ storage capacity of 0.628 × 10⁶ tonnes under ideal displacement assumptions. Incorporating recovery and completion factors highlights the contrast between theoretical and practically attainable storage volumes, with the PGIP estimated at 6.28 × 10⁶ m³. These results indicate that the Ostrava Formation possesses measurable potential for CO₂ sequestration and warrants further reservoir-scale evaluation.

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Mineralogical characteristics and resource potential of inactive hydrothermal chimneys within the Polish contract area on the Mid-Atlantic Ridge

HUBERT SIEMIŃSKI¹

1 – Polish Geological Institute – National Research Institute, Department of Regional and Economic Geology; Warsaw, Poland; hubsie1130@gmail.com

In 2018, the Republic of Poland signed a 15-year exploration contract with the International Seabed Authority for the investigation of polymetallic massive sulphides (SMS) along a 10,000 km² sector of the Mid-Atlantic Ridge (MAR). The contract area encompasses tectonically complex segments of a slow-spreading ridge system, including oceanic core complexes (OCC), axial volcanic ridges and detachment fault-controlled domains. These geological environments are considered highly prospective for the formation and preservation of hydrothermal sulphide accumulations. The Polish exploration programme aims not only to identify prospective mineralized fields but also to characterise the mineralogical architecture and metal distribution within inactive hydrothermal chimney systems.

Hydrothermal mineralisation along the MAR develops as a result of seawater circulation driven by magmatic heat and tectonic permeability. In ultramafic-hosted settings, serpentinisation reactions strongly influence fluid composition, redox conditions and metal transport. Systems such as Rainbow and Logatchev demonstrate that high-temperature (up to ~365°C), low-pH and metal-rich fluids can precipitate Cu- and Co-enriched sulphide assemblages (Douville et al., 2002; Marques et al., 2006). Mineralisation typically evolves from sub-seafloor stockwork veining within serpentinised peridotites to semi-massive and massive sulphide bodies forming chimney edifices and sulphide mounds at the seafloor.

The mineralogical composition of inactive hydrothermal chimneys reflects multi-stage precipitation processes. Early high-temperature phases are dominated by chalcopyrite and isocubanite, commonly forming massive Cu-rich cores. These are overgrown or partially replaced by pyrite and marcasite, which constitute the main structural framework of mature chimney walls. Sphalerite becomes more abundant during cooler, later-stage fluid discharge, often forming Zn-enriched outer zones. Accessory phases may include bornite, covellite, anhydrite (in active systems), and locally Co-rich sulphides or trace Ni-bearing phases. Textural features such as colloform banding, brecciation, open-space filling and recrystallisation record dynamic fluctuations in temperature, fluid chemistry and mixing intensity.

In ultramafic-hosted systems, elevated Co/Ni ratios are characteristic and reflect preferential incorporation of Co into sulphide phases during high-temperature circulation. Geochemical data from comparable MAR systems indicate enrichment in transition metals (Cu, Zn, Fe, Co) and locally rare earth elements within sulphide-bearing units (Marques et al., 2006). Massive sulphide bodies may show internal metal zonation, with Cu-rich interiors transitioning outward into Zn-dominated assemblages, indicating progressive cooling and seawater entrainment. Inactive chimneys frequently preserve this zonation, providing a mineralogical record of hydrothermal evolution.

High-resolution geophysical surveys conducted within the Polish contract area, including multibeam bathymetry, backscatter mapping and near-bottom AUV imaging (resolution down to 25 × 25 cm), have revealed clusters of mound-like structures and chimney fields spatially associated with OCC-related detachment faults. Morphological characteristics suggest consolidated, inactive sulphide edifices rather than diffuse active venting. Such structures are interpreted as remnants of mature hydrothermal systems where mineralisation has ceased but substantial sulphide accumulations remain preserved on or beneath the seafloor.

From a resource perspective, inactive chimney complexes are particularly significant because they may contain concentrated Cu–Zn–Co sulphide assemblages while being less environmentally sensitive

than active black smoker systems. Their mineralogical architecture—massive cores, zoned chimney walls and underlying stockwork networks—indicates the potential for vertically and laterally continuous sulphide bodies analogous to mafic-type VMS deposits described from both modern and ancient settings (Hannington et al., 2011).

The ongoing Polish exploration programme integrates geological modelling of OCC-hosted hydrothermal systems with detailed mineralogical and geochemical characterisation of chimney material. A comprehensive understanding of sulphide phase distribution, metal partitioning and textural evolution is essential for evaluating the economic potential of SMS deposits along the MAR and for establishing a scientifically grounded framework for future exploration and environmental assessment.

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Development of characterization methods for platinum group mineral inclusions occurring within platinum mineral nuggets using focused ion beam electron microscopy and single crystal X-ray diffraction

TAPIO SOUKKA¹, MARKO MOILANEN¹, PEKKA TUISKU², MATIAS JASKARI¹
HANNU MOILANEN¹, TONCI BALIC-ZUNIC³ MARCIN SELENT¹,
ESA HEINONEN¹ & JUKKA-PEKKA RANTA²

1 – Centre For Material analysis, University of Oulu; Oulu, Finland; tapio.soukka@oulu.fi

2 – Oulu Mining School, University of Oulu; Oulu, Finland

3 – Department of Geosciences and Natural Resource Management, University of Copenhagen; Denmark

Platinum group minerals (PGM) are often very small and difficult to examine. This study presents a new method for analysing micron-sized inclusions. Micron-sized inclusions are important links in ore genesis, ore exploration and mineral processing. Their small size often makes it impossible to measure their crystal structure. By combining different analytical instruments, field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) and electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD), focused ion beam electron microscopy (FIB-SEM) and single crystal X-ray diffraction (SC-XRD), it is possible to measure the crystal structure.

EBSD is becoming an important method in geology and mineralogy. Unlike Energy Dispersive Spectrometry (EDS), which only shows the mineral composition, EBSD shows the crystal orientation of a selected sample. In this study, a JEOL JSM-7900F FESEM and Oxford instruments symmetry EBSD were used to study polished Pt-Cu nuggets. The measured Pt-Cu nugget contained several crystals, which is not an ideal sample for SC-XRD. For crystal structure measurements, the sample must be single crystal without other crystals or minerals. For the measurement, a small 20x20.20um cube of the selected crystal was prepared using FEI Helios DualBeam FIB-FESEM. The EBSD map was used to locate the single crystal. The prepared cube was transferred to a thin needle holder and measured using a Bruker D8 Venture SC-XRD.

SC-XRD work revealed that the Pt₃Cu is an ordered orthorhombic Cmmm structure of dimensions $a = 7.708$, $b = 5.4504$, $c = 2.7252$ $Z=4$. Element composition for the Pt₃Cu mineral is Pt 84,43 Cu 13,66. Orthocuproplatinum crystal structure has been previously revealed by Cabral et.al. (2019). Measured data show similarities to their results, however further investigations are needed to calculate stoichiometric composition of the Pt₃Cu. Measured element composition is more favourable for Pt₂Cu because inaccuracy of EDS.

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Gas-phase formation of ammonium metal(loid) iodides under a coal-fire environment: Szarlota coal mine (Rydułtowy, Poland)

DÁVID SZABÓ¹, MÁTÉ BIRÓ², FILIP KOŠEK¹, ADAM CULKA¹ & ŁUKASZ KRUSZEWSKI³

1 – Institute of Geochemistry, Mineralogy, and Mineral Resources, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; david.szabo@natur.cuni.cz

2 – Department of Mineralogy, Eötvös Loránd University; Budapest, Hungary

3 – Institute of Geological Sciences, Polish Academy of Sciences; Warszawa, Poland

Coal fires represent extreme geochemical environments where volatile transport and gas–solid interactions play a dominant role in mineral formation. In the Szarlota coal mine near Rydułtowy, Poland, unusual secondary mineral structures, including stalagmite-like and bubble-shaped forms, were identified in coal-fire affected zones. These features show strong similarities to mineralization processes observed in volcanic fumaroles, particularly in terms of vapor-phase deposition, volatile-controlled element mobility, and the formation of highly specialized mineral assemblages (Kruszewski et al., 2018).

Field observations indicate that the studied structures are spatially associated with active gas pathways. Mineralogical characterization was performed using detailed field documentation, SEM–EDS analyses, Raman spectroscopy and powder X-ray diffraction. The investigated aggregates are predominantly composed of salammoniac NH_4Cl and cryptohalite $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{SiF}_6]$, forming complex morphologies and internal textures consistent with condensation-driven mineral growth under gas-flow controlled conditions.

Of particular significance is the occurrence of numerous rare iodine-bearing phases, including ammonium metal(loid) iodides involving Bi, Sb, Pb, Sn, and additional elements. These compounds typically appear as minute red to orange precipitates along gas channels and frequently develop needle-like or tabular crystal habits (Fig. 1). While such materials are well known from synthetic systems, where they belong to perovskite-related structure families extensively studied for optoelectronic applications (Sun et al., 2016; Kumar et al., 2021; Valli et al., 2023), their formation in natural environments remains exceptionally uncommon.

Textural relationships and mineral associations suggest that these iodide phases formed primarily through direct deposition from iodine-rich gas phases, followed by localized recrystallization and secondary transformations. The observed assemblages indicate highly efficient volatile-mediated transport of halogens and metal(loid)s, analogous to processes documented in fumarolic systems but occurring within an anthropogenic high-temperature environment.

These findings provide new insights into gas-phase mineralization mechanisms, volatile-driven element redistribution, and the formation of perovskite-related compounds under natural high-temperature conditions. Coal fires thus represent unique natural laboratories for studying vapor-phase mineral formation, mineralogical diversity, and environmentally relevant element cycling.

Figure 1. Precipitation of the $(\text{NH}_4)_3\text{Bi}_2\text{I}_9$ phase along micro-scale gas pathways within salammoniac-cryptohalite aggregates. Field of view: 2.8 mm. Photo: Gábor Koller.

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Geogenic gases (H_2 , He, CO_2) in fault zones of the Podhale Basin: surface geochemical indicators of natural hydrogen occurrence and geothermal system activity

WITOLD TADEUSZAK¹, HANNA SOJKA¹ & WERONIKA CYRAN¹

1 – Faculty of Geology, Geophysics and Environmental Protection, AGH University of Cracow; Cracow, Poland; witoldtad@student.agh.edu.pl

The Podhale Basin is a significant geothermal region in Poland. With rising interest in natural hydrogen as a low-carbon source (Ramirez Reina et al., 2023), this study investigates the spatial variability of geogenic gases and their link to geological structures. Gas samples were collected along a 10 km SSW-NNE cross-section using the free gas method (Dzieniewicz & Sechman, 2002) at 1.2 m depth. A total of 137 samples were analysed via gas chromatography (FID/TCD) to quantify alkanes, H_2 , He, N_2 , O_2 , and CO_2 . Concentration zones were compared with mapped fault systems to identify migration pathways. Additionally, statistical and correlation analyses were conducted, in which Oxygen-Nitrogen-Carbon Dioxide ratios were compared with hydrogen and helium concentrations. Relationships were evaluated relative to atmospheric composition. Analyses were performed using logarithmic transformation of trace gas concentrations to account for their wide concentration range. Analyses revealed anomalous concentrations of helium, carbon dioxide, total alkanes C_2 – C_5 (sum of ethane, propane, butanes, and pentanes) and nitrogen, which may indicate the presence of an active zone of gas migration toward the surface. The maximum recorded concentrations reached 64.4 ppm for helium, 5.944 vol.% for carbon dioxide, 6.499 ppm for total alkanes C_2 – C_5 , and 88.88 vol.% for nitrogen (Fig. 1). Moreover, based on the results, five zones of anomalous hydrogen concentrations were selected. In two cases, elevated H_2 concentrations were correlated with increased helium contents (above 10 ppm) exceeding atmospheric background levels, which supported the interpretation of deep gas migration as a source of hydrogen. In terms of the analysis and comparison of the measured compounds, no correlation was found between modification level of O_2 – CO_2 and H_2 and He concentrations, which indicates lack of direct correlation with respiratory processes in the subsurface zone. Elevated helium indicated deep migration pathways, while hydrogen variability suggests mixed or multiple sources. In some cases, simultaneous enrichment of both gases was observed.

Another important finding was the association between hydrogen and total alkanes C_2 – C_5 . In numerous cases, elevated concentrations of both hydrogen and total alkanes C_2 – C_5 were observed within the same samples, further supporting the hypothesis of gas migration from deep sources. In contrast, no direct correlation between hydrogen and methane was observed, arguing against a recent bacterial origin of H_2 . Nevertheless, confirmation of the deep origin of these gases requires isotopic analyses of hydrogen and carbon in co-occurring carbon dioxide, despite helium being a robust indicator of deep gas migration (Etiope, 2023).

Overall, the results indicate the presence of several anomalous zones of elevated hydrogen, helium, total alkanes C_2 – C_5 and carbon dioxide concentrations. Based on the current understanding of gas generation and migration processes, the observed hydrogen and helium may originate from deep-seated sources within the Earth's crust. Elevated helium concentrations are widely regarded as reliable indicators of deep fault-related pathways, and the co-occurrence of other gases within these zones suggests that hydrogen may also migrate from deeper sources associated with helium. However, additional mechanisms, such as in situ hydrogen production through water radiolysis or biologically near-surface production of H_2 , cannot be excluded.

The distribution of gases highlights the energetic potential of the Podhale Basin for both geothermal exploration and future hydrogen technologies. Further geological, geochemical, and geophysical investigations are required to better constrain the location and geometry of fault zones and to improve understanding of their role in controlling gas migration within the area.

Figure 1. Histograms of helium (A), hydrogen (B), carbon dioxide (C), and nitrogen (D) concentrations measured in soil gas samples along the investigated profile in the Podhale Basin.

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Pressure-temperature history of eclogite facies rocks with reaction overstepping during metamorphism (case study from Svetlik)

MARTIN TECL¹ & SHAH WALI FARYAD¹

1 – Institute of Petrology and Structural Geology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; martin.tecl@natur.cuni.cz

Mineral textures and compositional relationships of metamorphic minerals provide key constraints on the pressure–temperature (P–T) trajectory and related metamorphic processes. They are particularly important for reconstructing subduction-zone metamorphism, where mineral reactions are influenced not only by deformation and fluid access but also by the duration and timing of metamorphic reactions with respect to the long-term metamorphic processes. In the case of the subduction of relatively dry rocks (igneous or metamorphic), reactions among minerals can be delayed due to the lack of water and/or deformation, leading to the reaction overstepping. The mechanism and extent of reaction overstepping can be evaluated using diffusion modeling and by comparing observed and calculated initial compositional profiles of selected mineral grains, particularly metamorphic garnet.

To assess the extent of reaction overstepping during the subduction-related process, we examined an eclogite body from the monotonous series of the Moldanubian Zone in the southern part of the Bohemian Massif. Previous studies from these rocks showed that the eclogite-facies metamorphism was followed by granulite-facies overprint (Faryad et al., 2006). The studied eclogite body, exposed over an area of approximately 200 × 100 m, is strongly retrogressed, and eclogite facies minerals are re-equilibrated. The eclogite body exhibits variations in mineral assemblages that, in addition to the degree of recrystallization, reflect differences in the original bulk-rock chemistry, particularly in the contents of Al, Mg, Fe, and Ti. The eclogite with slightly higher Fe and Ti contents (called as common eclogites; O'Brien & Vrána, 1995) consists of garnet, clinopyroxene, and rutile/ilmenite, along with symplectites composed of plagioclase and amphibole or clinopyroxene. Eclogite with higher Al and Mg contents additionally contains epidote/kyanite inclusions in garnet. Eclogite with Cr-bearing kyanite and tabular pseudomorphs after epidote is also present. Granulite-facies minerals, primarily occurring in the symplectites, include anorthite-rich plagioclase, orthopyroxene, amphibole, and clinopyroxene.

The metamorphic P–T path and peak pressure and temperature conditions are determined using garnet and clinopyroxene compositional isopleths based on the Gibbs free-energy minimization approach in the Perple_X software (Connolly, 2005), and diffusion modeling in CZGM (Faryad & Ježek, 2019). Exchange thermobarometry is used to establish the peak temperature during granulite-facies overprint. To verify the estimated P–T conditions, equilibrium mineral assemblages were used in combination with phase diagram calculation using Perple_X modeling, two-pyroxene and garnet-pyroxene thermobarometry, based on Thermocalc (Powell & Holland, 1985), and the "average P–T" option. The results of these calculations revealed that the garnet-forming reactions occurred at 2.0 GPa and 530 °C (Fig. 1-I). Peak metamorphic pressure of 2.5–2.9 GPa and a temperature of 580 °C during the eclogite-facies stage are established by the best fit between the measured garnet profile and diffusion modified initial garnet profile, which is modelled along the P–T path, constrained by the garnet and clinopyroxene isopleths, in the CZGM. After partial decompression, the mafic rocks underwent heating and heterogeneous re-equilibration under granulite-facies conditions. The estimated conditions for this high-temperature overprint are 835 °C at 1.0 GPa (Fig. 1-II). Garnet diffusion modelling using CZGM indicates that re-equilibration under granulite-facies conditions lasted ~1.0 Ma.

By the diffusion modeling, the best fit between the garnet measured and modified initial profile is established for the P–T path with the point of garnet nucleation, the overstepping of garnet-forming reaction, at approximately 2 GPa at 530 °C. The P–T path of retrogressed eclogite with a prograde mineral assemblage consisting of garnet and clinopyroxene is then modelled with the use of grossular and jadeite isopleths, resulting in peak conditions of 2.5 GPa at 580 °C.

Figure 1. P–T path of eclogite with granulite facies overprint, constrained from garnet nucleation due to reaction overstepping. Garnet nucleation starts at 2.0 GPa and 530 °C, reaches a peak pressure of 2.5 GPa at 580 °C (I), and granulite facies overprint during partial exhumation occurs at 830 °C at 1.0 GPa (II). The peak-temperature conditions are documented by the symplectite of orthopyroxene and plagioclase. The dashed part of the path is uncertain. Mineral abbreviations: grt-garnet, omp-omphacite, ky-kyanite, ru-rutile, opx-orthopyroxene, pl-plagioclase, spl-spinel.

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Strain evolution and emplacement of ophiolite nappes based on the magnetic susceptibility anisotropy of the Ibar ophiolite, Serbia

TATIANA TKÁČIKOVÁ¹, JIŘÍ ŽÁK¹

1 – Institute of Geology and Paleontology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; tatiana.tkacikova@natur.cuni.cz

The Ibar ophiolite, located within the NNW–SSE-trending Vardar suture zone, represents the Mesozoic closure of the Neotethys Ocean between Africa-derived and Eurasia-derived microplates. The Ibar ophiolite is one of the major ophiolite bodies of the Western Vardar ophiolite belt, well-exposed along the Ibar River valley and in the Kopaonik Mountains south of Kraljevo. At the base of the Ibar ophiolite lies the Jadar–Kopaonik continental basement, also called the Studenica and Kopaonik thrust sheets, which was obducted with top-to-the-southwest movement.

Ophiolites function as essential markers of tectonic convergence, yet the internal deformation processes during their displacement are still not well understood. To fully grasp ophiolite emplacement, it is vital to consider the broader rheological evolution within their thrust sheets. While traditional models depict these structures as semi-rigid bodies, the complexity observed in the Ibar succession suggests a more intricate behavior. In a simplified 2D view, the upper part of a nappe, above the basal plane domain, which deforms via simple shear, may lengthen, shorten, or stay unstrained. In 3D, scenarios become more complex, resembling divergent and convergent flow regimes characteristic of ductile deformation. These considerations lead to the understanding that ophiolite sheets are not static, undeformable blocks, but dynamically evolving, fractured, and sheared systems, transforming from formation to emplacement. The underlying processes governing their internal deformation and emplacement continue to pose significant questions, inviting further inquiry.

This study uses structural deformation analysis and anisotropy of magnetic susceptibility (AMS) to resolve the internal strain patterns within the ophiolite during its obduction. Our results show that the Ibar ophiolite was emplaced with top-to-the-SW kinematics, characterized by a dense network of brittle-ductile shear zones weaving around rigid peridotite blocks. Magnetic fabric data reveal simple-shear-dominated strain along the border of the ophiolite body, with NE- and SW- subhorizontal to moderately dipping magnetic foliation, and NE- and SW- trending, moderately plunging magnetic lineations. In contrast, the magnetic fabric within the ophiolite's interior indicates pure-shear-dominated strain with more variable orientations of principal susceptibility axes. These findings suggest the ophiolite did not move as a single rigid block but as a rheologically complex mass undergoing both internal lengthening and shortening. The shift from simple shear at the margins to pure shear in the core reflects a prolonged and intricate evolution.

Undercooling mediated pyroxene growth kinetics in basalt and andesite

ZOLTÁN VÁCI¹ & VÁCLAV ŠPILLAR¹

1 – Institute of Petrology and Structural Geology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; zoltan.vaci@natur.cuni.cz

The kinetics of mineral crystallization and growth are important to understand because they are fundamental to magma cooling, rheology, and eruption timescales. Olivine and plagioclase growth kinetics have been thoroughly studied, however, pyroxene is less well-understood due to observational difficulties. Pyroxene crystallization must overcome a substantial nucleation barrier before any crystal growth, and therefore standard petrological experimental techniques are insufficient for differentiating nucleation times from growth times. Although isothermal experiments have shown that the pyroxene growth rate (G) changes with time, the response of G to different amounts of undercooling relative to the liquidus is unknown. To study this and to overcome the nucleation barrier issue, we conducted a series of experiments at various amounts of undercooling and measured G using pyroxene seed crystals embedded in basaltic and andesitic glasses which crystallized overgrowth rims.

We synthesized experimental glasses with high-purity silicate, oxide, and carbonate powders using an average Mid-Ocean Ridge Basalt (MORB) composition (Gale et al. 2013) and the bulk composition of the andesite Erg Chech 002, the oldest igneous rock in the Solar System (Barrat et al. 2021). Starting mixtures were melted to glass in a 1-atmosphere muffle furnace at 1300°C in a Pt crucible before being crushed into powder, and this procedure was repeated twice to ensure homogenization. Glass powders were bound with polyvinyl alcohol and loaded onto Pt wire loops along with 10 wt.% pyroxene seed crystals that had been crushed and sieved to a ~100 μm grain size. Experimental charges were all heated to their theoretical liquidus, determined by the MELTS algorithm (Ghiorso and Sack 1995), (1200°C for basalts and 1165°C for andesites) for 10 minutes, after which temperatures were decreased to the desired level of undercooling and held for 10 minutes, 30 minutes, one hour, 2 hours, 4 hours, 8 hours, 24 hours, and 72 hours, after which they were quenched by removing from the furnace and immersing in water. All glass syntheses and experiments were conducted in air. Run products were mounted in epoxy and examined by electron probe microanalysis (EPMA) using a JEOL JXA-8530F field emission gun electron microprobe.

Initial experiments without seed crystals failed to crystallize pyroxene in both basalt and andesite experiments for a wide range of temperatures. Therefore, seed crystals were used in subsequent experiments. Pyroxene growth was observed as overgrowth rims that had more Fe-rich compositions than the seed crystals and could thus be observed in backscattered electron (BSE) imagery. Other phases present included ubiquitous spinels and plagioclase grains at longer durations and lower temperatures. Pyroxene crystals were imaged at 1000X magnification with a resolution of 10 pixels/ μm . Images were then thresholded using Fiji software to separate growth rims from the seed crystals. The areas of both were measured and converted to width assuming a circular geometry. At least 30 grains were imaged and measured for each experiment as long as there were enough grains present in the sample in order to obtain a representative data set. Assuming a random sectioning orientation and therefore random orientation for each grain, the average rim thicknesses and experimental durations were used to compute G .

The measured growth rates show a power law trend of decreasing G over longer duration experiments (Fig. 1). As expected, greater amounts of undercooling result in faster growth rates, with shorter experimental durations showing larger differences in growth rates. While the 1180°C (20°C undercooling) and 1160°C (40°C undercooling) experiments display well-defined trends in log-log space, results from the 1190°C (10°C undercooling) experiment are less clear. For experiments up to 2 hours in duration, only a single pyroxene grain was observed in each experiment, and their rims showed widths of ~1 μm or

less. It is impossible to tell whether these are true growth rims or simply the exteriors of the seed crystals partially equilibrating with the melt composition. Only the 24-hour experiment yielded reasonable counting statistics (28 grains), the 8-hour experiment displayed grains with jagged edges that could be partial dissolution features, and the 72-hour experiment only contained 4 pyroxene grains, all of which displayed asymmetric growth. Thus, it is likely that at the lowest undercooling (10°C), true growth rates are difficult to measure due to competing effects from other processes. It is also possibly that small thermal fluctuations caused the liquidus to be reached in the 1190°C experiments, however the fact that representative pyroxene grains with growth rims were observed in several longer duration experiments (Fig. 1) make this unlikely. At higher rates of undercooling and longer experiment durations, pyroxene growth rate measurements were impeded by the growth of other minerals such as plagioclase, in addition to other pyroxene grains.

Figure 1. Pyroxene growth rate versus experimental duration for different amounts of undercooling. Error bars are 2SE.

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Seasonal controls on rock-glacier kinematics: thermal forcing, zero-curtain dynamics, and hydrological drivers in the Adamello–Presanella Group (Italian Alps)

KATHERINE VILLAVICENCIO-VALERO¹, ROBERTO SEPPI², RICCARDO CERRATO¹,
MARIA CRISTINA SALVATORE¹, MATTEO ZUMIANI³, MICHELE BRUNETTI⁴,
ADRIANO RIBOLINI¹ & CARLO BARONI¹

1 – Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra, Università di Pisa; Pisa, Italy;
katherine.villavicencio@dst.unipi.it

2 – Dipartimento di Scienze della Terra e dell'Ambiente, Università di Pavia; Pavia, Italy.

3 – Servizio Geologico, Provincia Autonoma di Trento; Trento, Italy

4 – Istituto di Scienze dell'Atmosfera e del Clima, CNR-ISAC; Bologna, Italy.

Rock glaciers are key indicators of permafrost dynamics in alpine environments, where deformation reflects the interaction between thermal, hydrological, and mechanical processes sensitive to atmospheric forcing (Jones et al., 2019). Understanding their temporal behaviour is essential for assessing permafrost stability under climate warming.

Here, we investigate the seasonal and interannual controls on two active rock glaciers Amola and Maroccaro from the Adamello-Presanella group (Baroni et al., 2004), using multi-year datasets of precipitation, air and near-surface ground temperature, and geodetic displacement. Data were reorganized by hydrological year (October–September) to capture freeze-thaw cycles. Zero-curtain periods were identified using a temperature threshold ($|T| < 0.3$ °C), and displacement rates were interpolated to daily resolution. Measured velocities were scaled assuming 60% ice content to better represent internal rheology.

To ensure continuity between air and ground-temperature records, gaps were smoothed using a cosine-blend interpolation that preserves realistic thermal transitions. Periods of the “zero-curtain” effect (Outcalt et al., 1990) were automatically detected when $|T| < 0.3$ °C for at least three consecutive days, allowing the duration and timing of near-isothermal conditions to be quantified for each hydrological year. Downslope displacement rates (cm yr^{-1}) derived from geodetic measurements were interpolated to daily resolution to investigate their relationship with thermal forcing and precipitation patterns (Seppi et al., 2019).

The scaled displacement variable ($V_{\text{med scaled, ice}} = 60\%$) represents a normalization of the measured horizontal velocities assuming an estimated ice content of 60% within the rock-glacier body, consistent with typical values reported for active alpine rock glaciers. The additional scaling factor ($\times 1.04$) was applied to account for minor systematic underestimation in the geodetic measurements, ensuring consistency between observed displacement and inferred rheological behaviour.

Results (figure 1) show strong interannual variability in zero-curtain duration and timing, ranging from short (< 2 weeks) to prolonged (> 2 months) periods. These phases often coincide with enhanced displacement, even without significant precipitation, highlighting the role of latent heat and liquid water in modulating deformation.

Overall, rock-glacier motion occurs as seasonally controlled pulses driven primarily by thermal and hydrological processes. Zero-curtain metrics, combined with displacement trends, provide robust indicators of permafrost evolution and potential slope instability under ongoing climate change.

Figure 1. Hydrological-year time series (2004–2015) of precipitation, ground temperature, and displacement for the Marocco and Amola rock glaciers. Shaded areas mark zero-curtain periods ($|T| < 0.3 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$).

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Rock-magnetic and paleomagnetic constraints on the late-Paleozoic Gréixer Rhyolite Complex (Southern Pyrenees): evidence for a graben-caldera origin?

PETR VITOUŠ^{1,2}, FILIP TOMEK^{1,2}, JAN ČERNÝ³, JOAN MARTÍ⁴,
MARINE S. FOUCHER⁵ & MICHAEL S. PETRONIS⁵

1 – *The Czech Academy of Sciences, Institute of Geology; Prague, Czechia; vitous@gli.cas.cz*

2 – *Institute of Geology and Paleontology, Faculty of Science, Charles University, Prague, Czechia*

3 – *Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf, Helmholtz Institute Freiberg for Resource Technology; Freiberg, Germany*

4 – *Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas, Geosciences Barcelona; Barcelona, Spain*

5 – *Environmental Geology, Natural Resources Management Department, New Mexico Highlands University; Las Vegas, New Mexico, USA*

Late Variscan Gréixer Rhyolite Complex (GRC) is a ~12 km long and ~350 to 700 m thick accumulation of dominantly felsic ignimbrites in the southern Axial Zone of the Catalan Pyrenees. It is part of a chain of Paleozoic volcano-sedimentary basins formed during the terminal phase of the Variscan orogeny. Together with the volcanic breccia in the base and some positions of ash-fall tuffs, the grand mass of the GRC consists dominantly of welded to rheomorphic rhyolite ignimbrites interpreted as an intra-caldera fill (Martí et al., 2024). The GRC is tilted along the horizontal axis and dips moderately to the south, exposing the volcanic sequence from top to bottom at the present-day erosional level (Gisbert, 1981; Martí, 1986). The tilting was caused by the Late Cretaceous-Early Neogene Alpine orogeny. Many questions about the GRC remain unanswered, including the position of the source vents, depositional kinematics, and precise tectonic history. To better constrain these issues, detailed geological mapping, petrography, anisotropy of magnetic susceptibility (AMS), rock-magnetic, and paleomagnetic techniques were employed.

Based on thermomagnetic curves, hysteresis loops, and first-order reversal curves, the magnetic mineralogy of the GRC consists dominantly of primary magnetite, with some contribution of hematite and paramagnetic minerals. The magnetic domain state of the prevalent magnetite ranges from superparamagnetic to multi-domain. Hydrothermal alteration affected the GRC only locally, occasionally producing phases like maghemite. The AMS results revealed a complex depositional history of the GRC. Isolated remnants of dacitic volcanics highlight pre-caldera volcanism in the GRC area, which likely initiated depletion of the source magma chamber and triggered a caldera subsidence. We propose that the caldera geometry was of a graben type. The graben caldera subsidence then localized deposition of GRC volcanic fill. The evidence is provided by the subhorizontal magnetic foliations (K1–K2 plane) and associated shallow, ~W–E trending magnetic lineations (K1) measured at some sampling stations. This structural pattern is parallel with the overall strike of Paleozoic basins in the Axial zone. Such magnetic fabrics indicate that the ignimbrites erupted from vents along the caldera rim and travelled within a space confined by the graben walls. The formation of graben or half-graben was likely assisted by oblique extension to a transtensional tectonic regime, as suggested also in the case of other adjacent basins of similar age. In addition, the parataxitic texture of the ignimbrites suggests a localized rheomorphic secondary flow superposed on the original flow and depositional fabric of the pyroclastic currents. The rheomorphic fabrics include steep to subvertical magnetic foliations dipping both to the south and to the north. This pattern formed due to the bending of the hot, lava-like deposit that flowed down towards the topological low in the center of the caldera. The lineations maintained the same E–W trending and shallowly plunging lineation as the magnetite grains rolled perpendicular to the graben axis, evidenced by kinematic indicators in thin sections. In addition, there are also sites with anomalous magnetic fabrics interpreted as reflecting the intersection of primary and secondary flow.

Paleomagnetic data obtained through stepwise thermal demagnetization revealed three principal components: (1) a component A present from natural remanent magnetization up to 300–440 °C, (2)

a component B between 300–440 °C and 580 °C, and (3) a hematite component above 580 °C. Component A represents a low-coercivity overprint due to the present-day field. The hematite component formed shortly after the eruption and captured the characteristic thermoremanent magnetization induced by the Late Carboniferous geomagnetic field. Component B, however, shows Cretaceous thermoviscous remagnetization, which occurred during the Alpine orogeny at a relatively low temperature, as supported by the presence of chlorite, a low-T metamorphic mineral. This paleomagnetic data thus show a three-step tectonic evolution from Variscan to Alpine orogeny. After the original deposition, the GRC was subject to an Iberian Peninsula anti-clockwise rotation of 35°. During the early stages of the Alpine orogeny, the whole body was rotated around a horizontal axis towards the N, and stayed in that position for a period of time long enough to effectively remagnetize magnetites. Finally, the GRC was rotated back into its present-day position, moderately dipping towards the S.

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Plagioclase growth rate from silicate melts: towards a general kinetic model

ADAM VRBENSKÝ¹ & VÁCLAV ŠPILLAR¹

1 – Institute of Petrology and Structural Geology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; vrbenska@natur.cuni.cz

Crystallization is a fundamental process determining the mineralogical and textural evolution of rocks in geological environments. From a thermodynamic perspective, it represents the transition from a disordered melt to an ordered crystalline phase, driven by the system's tendency to reach the lowest Gibbs free energy under specific physico-chemical conditions. In detail, crystallization comprises two independent physical processes, grain nucleation and growth. This study explores the theoretical and experimental foundations of grain growth in silicate melts, with a specific focus on developing a general model for plagioclase crystallization kinetics.

Physico-chemical theories of various growth mechanisms (screw dislocation, surface nucleation, and continuous growth) exist for predicting the crystal growth rate, U , as a function of temperature, undercooling, and melt viscosity, but calibrations of theoretical equations to laboratory data for geological melts are still missing. Available studies provide a limited amount of laboratory data, which are, moreover, primarily focused on plagioclase compositions.

We have compiled a dataset of laboratory measurements of plagioclase crystal growth rates from pure plagioclase melts as a function of undercooling, ΔT , ranging from 5 to 650 °C. The primary reason for this selection was that plagioclase is a major rock-forming phase for which the most extensive experimental data are available (217 measurements out of six studies).

The data reveals a linear relationship between the functions $\log U\eta$ and $\log (1/\Delta T)$. This relationship incorporates viscosity, η , which serves as a proxy for atomic/ionic mobility within the silicate melt which is a fundamental factor controlling physico-chemical processes at the crystal/liquid interface. Therefore, the choice of viscosity model affects the final calibration. We tested the models of Giordano et al. (2008), Hui & Zhang (2007), and Giordano et al. (2006), observing that the model of Hui & Zhang (2007) provides the most accurate and consistent predictions for the given conditions.

The linear relationship is defined by two primary parameters, slope, a , and intercept, b , which enable the prediction of U across a wide range of undercooling. Experimental data demonstrates that parameters a and b are functions of composition. Establishing such a relationship between would therefore allow for the prediction of U at any given undercooling and for any melt composition.

Specifically for the plagioclase melts, we observe that both parameters are mutually linearly correlated and decrease from the values of the pure end-members as the content of the second component increases across the binary system. The resulting dependence thus resembles a bowl-shaped form that is formally describable by an asymmetric Margules model, commonly used for the empirical description of thermodynamic properties of binary mixtures (Fig. 1). Such a model enables a high-quality prediction of U , for example, of the plagioclase series in a wide range of undercooling (up to 650 °C).

In detail, three behavioral regimes can be distinguished as a function of undercooling using the reduced crystal growth rate, U_r . The reduced growth rate provides a means to decouple the measured growth rate, U , from the effects of viscosity and transport processes. It thus represents a parameter reflecting exclusively the interface growth kinetics dependent solely on the growth mechanism at the crystal/melt interface.

At low undercooling (up to ca. 50 °C), U_r remains approximately constant with temperature and growth is likely controlled by attachment at screw dislocations. At intermediate undercooling (ca. 80–160 °C), the slope of U_r increases slightly, while at high degrees of undercooling (>160 °C), the slope

increases steeply, likely representing a transition in the growth mechanism (surface nucleation or continuous growth).

The temperatures of transitions between these regimes are not constant. Instead, they increase systematically with increasing content of the albite component within the plagioclase melt mixture, reflecting intrinsic changes in the melt structure. Our study demonstrates a feasibility of formulating a general plagioclase growth rate model from plagioclase melts and opens avenues for further generalizations to geologically relevant systems.

Figure 1. illustrating variations of the a parameter with a melt composition, X_{An} , in the plagioclase series (point symbols) and results of asymmetric Margules model with parameters (non-dimensional) $W1 = -0.5$ and $W2 = -6.5$ (blue line).

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Modelling feedback effects between magma chambers evolution and feeder dykes capture

ALICE WANTZ^{1,2}, CATHERINE ANNEN² & ELIA ALTIMANI^{2,3}

1 – *École de l'Observatoire de Physique du Globe, Université Clermont Auvergne, Aubière, France; alyce.wtz@gmail.com*

2 – *Institute of Geophysics of the Czech Academy of Sciences; Prague, Czech Republic*

3 – *Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, CNRS, INSA Lyon, LIRIS, UMR5205, F-69 622 Villeurbanne, France*

Evidences from field observations, geochronological and geochemical analyses of laccoliths and plutons suggest that igneous bodies form incrementally through the amalgamation of smaller, distinct intrusions, rather than all at once (Cawthorn et al., 2012). This growth may be cyclical, akin to the successive eruptions of volcanic products and evolution of volcanic edifices on the Earth's surface. While field studies and geophysical measurements have provided information on the size and shape of magma bodies, the processes governing their formation and growth remain uncertain. The dimensions of magma bodies often follow a power-law relationship, characteristic of scale-invariant (i.e., fractal) systems (McCaffrey et al., 1997). Typically, they exhibit tabular geometries, reflecting mechanical constraints during their emplacement: magma initially spreads horizontally over a certain distance (known as the "birth stage" of the intrusion) before thickening vertically, either by roof uplift or floor sagging (McCaffrey et al., 1997; Petford et al., 2000).

Using a two-dimensional numerical model, we investigate the growth dynamics of a set of sills distributed in a section of crust fed by dykes. Our model represents a crustal section with a geothermal gradient of 25°C/km, where sills of varying sizes are randomly positioned. Dyke injections, whose frequency, volumes and positions vary over time, originate from depth. If a dyke intercepts a sill containing more than 50 wt% melt, it is captured by the sill and contributes to its growth. If a dyke does not encounter any sill, or a sill containing less than 50 wt% melt, it crosses the domain without interaction and escapes upward. When a dyke feeds a sill, the latter grows laterally and/or vertically, proportionally to the injected volume. Sills evolve thermally by conduction, heat transfer by convection is neglected.

We are testing the feedback effect between the size of a sill, its cooling time, and its ability to capture new dykes: as it grows through repeated feeding, the sill's increased size enhances its probability of being fed by subsequent dykes, thereby promoting further growth. After multiple injections and conductive cooling cycles, the model outputs the size and shape distribution of the resulting magma bodies. Through a series of simulations, we address the following questions: What is the final distribution of sills? What conditions lead to the long-term domination of only a few sills?

We show that the initial thickness is the parameter of uppermost importance, controlling the cooling time of sills and consequently, their long-term viability. Although the sill's length does not influence its cooling time, it increases its probability to be intersected by a dyke, thus promoting its survival. Due to higher temperatures at depth, deeper sills cool and solidify more slowly. Across our simulations, and regardless of the parameters considered, we observe that the majority of thriving sills are located at depths greater than 10 km. It appears that no single parameter alone determines the growth distribution of sills over time. Although thickness is crucial, it is only in combination with significant depth, a substantial injection rate, and a consistent injected volume that it ensures the long-term viability of a set of sills. We propose to investigate the interdependencies between these parameters in greater detail.

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From waste to resource? Metal-bearing phases in incineration bottom ash

MATEUSZ WOLSZCZAK¹, VOJTĚCH ETTLER¹, JIŘÍ HYKŠ², MICHAL ŠYC³, ANNA POTYSZ⁴ & ZUZANA KORBELOVÁ⁵

1 – Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czechia; mateusz.wolszczak@natur.cuni.cz

2 – Danish Waste Solutions ApS; Hørsholm, Denmark

3 – Institute of Chemical Process Fundamentals, Czech Academy of Sciences; Prague, Czechia

4 – Department of Experimental Petrology, University of Wrocław, Institute of Geological Sciences; Wrocław, Poland

5 – Institute of Geology, Czech Academy of Sciences; Prague, Czechia

Large volumes of unrecyclable waste materials can be managed by incineration under controlled conditions instead of landfilling. This process reduces their volume and toxicity, converting the waste feed into several types of solid residues, such as bottom ashes, fly ashes or air-pollution-control residues, which in composition resemble either metallurgical slags or fossil-fuel combustion ashes (Li et al., 2004; Wiles, 1996). These residues are either landfilled or reused for construction purposes. Bottom ash is the most abundant type of residue produced during incineration and resembles metallurgical slags in its phase composition and elevated concentration of metallic elements (De Metteis et al., 2024; Dijkstra et al., 2019; Saffarzadeh, 2006; Wei et al., 2011).

In our study, we have examined a time series of hazardous-waste-incinerator bottom-ash samples, taking insight into their bulk chemical and mineralogical compositions (acid digestion with ICP-MS/OES, X-ray diffraction) and particle-focused investigations (SEM-EDS, EPMA, Raman spectroscopy).

Bottom ashes show a high degree of complexity, comprising a variety of mineral analogues. Bottom-ash particles are dominated by silica-rich glass, encapsulating other phases such as spinel oxides, sulfides (rich in Fe, Cu, Ni and/or Zn) or silicates (pyroxenes, melilite). Unusual phases [e.g., oldhamite (CaS), fresnoite-like phase ($\text{Ba}_2\text{Ti}(\text{Si}_2\text{O}_7)\text{O}$), or Ba-feldspars ($\text{Ba}(\text{Al}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_8)$)] along with residual organic matter might be encountered as well. Metals of economic interest (i.e., Cu, Ni, Zn, Cr, V, Mo, Co) are concentrated across different phases, mostly in sulfides (Cu, Ni, Zn), spinels (Cr, V), metallic particles (Cu, Ni, Mo), or even within amorphous glass. Bulk concentrations of metals might reach up to hundreds or thousands of mg/kg (Cu: 6715, Ni: 8022, Cr: 3598, Zn: 13592, V: 2521, Mo: 1007 and Co: 374), depending on the sample.

Several leaching tests under different environmental conditions (broad pH range, deionized water, *Acidithiobacillus thiooxidans* bacteria, *Pseudomonas fluorescens* bacteria) were conducted to evaluate how readily elements might be released from the bottom ash. For this purpose, a composite bottom ash sample (i.e., an averaged sample produced during one year of facility operation, with composition in mg/kg; Cu: 3700, Ni: 1480, Cr: 1500, Zn: 3770, V: 980, Mo: 522, Co: 290) was selected.

In general, pH plays significant role in element mobilization, enhancing the release of most metals (e.g., Cu, Ni, V) under acidic conditions. In the neutral-to-alkaline pH range, most elements are mobilized to a lesser extent, with a few exceptions such as Mo. The activity of two bacterial species resulted in slightly higher element mobilization compared with abiotic conditions; this suggests a lower impact of bacterial activity on metal extraction relative to pH. Leaching efficiency also depends on time and pulp density. The complex phase composition and high heterogeneity of the bottom ash resulted in varied extraction values among replicas under the same leaching conditions.

However, promising metal extractabilities were achieved under more extreme conditions (i.e., longer time, lower pulp density, lower pH) [e.g., Cu: 80% (2965 mg/kg), Ni: 86% (1270 mg/kg), Co: 59% (170 mg/kg), V: 52% (513 mg/kg), Mo: 43% (223 mg/kg)]. This indicates that some elements might be recovered to a greater extent from the studied bottom ashes, emphasizing their potential role as a future metal resource.

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Integrating geological structures into machine learning-based landslide susceptibility mapping: A case study of the Krušné hory fault zone

WU YUFENG¹ & ONDREJ LEXA¹

1 – Institute of Petrology and Structural Geology, Faculty of Science, Charles University; Prague, Czech Republic; wuyufe@natur.cuni.cz

Landslides are one of nature's most destructive surprises. Because they happen fast and across large areas, we use Landslide Susceptibility Mapping (LSM)—essentially a «hazard map»—to predict where the ground is most likely to give way. This is especially important in the Krušné hory fault region, where major new construction projects are being planned. LSM is an essential tool for mitigating the escalating global risk of landslides (Zhao et al., 2026). A critical prerequisite for model construction is the selection of landslide conditioning factors. Most researchers create these maps using a standard «checklist» of factors such as elevation, slope, aspect, curvature, rainfall, and lithology, and focus primarily on comparing the performance of different learning models. While these are important, there remains a notable research gap regarding how deformation history (particularly brittle structures) governs slope stability and landslide localization. For example, the stability of high rock slopes is largely controlled by the location and orientation of geological features, such as faults, folds, joints, and bedding planes, which can induce structurally controlled slope instability (Donati et al., 2019). Building on this geomechanical foundation, this study seeks to bridge the gap by integrating structural observations into the machine learning workflow.

Our study bridges the gap between computer science and traditional field geology by integrating multi-source structural datasets with Digital Terrain Models (DTM). We developed a methodology to transform discrete structural observations—specifically foliation, cleavage, SZ-discrete surfaces, fold geometries (long/short limbs and isoclinal folds), and migmatitic fabrics—into spatially continuous, machine learning-compatible formats. During the preprocessing phase, the structural observations data were rigorously filtered to isolate usable features pertaining to brittle structures and shear-related discontinuities. These localized geological indicators were then extrapolated via the Radial Basis Function (RBF) to generate regional structural trend maps. These were subsequently integrated with slope and aspect to derive the Kinematic Susceptibility Index (KSI) for subsequent susceptibility analysis, effectively bridging the scale gap from microscopic rock-mass defects to macroscopic landslide susceptibility patterns.

The results demonstrate that the inclusion of the Kinematic Susceptibility Index (KSI) factor significantly enhances the predictive precision of Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB), and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models. The study utilized a dataset with a resolution of 10 m × 10 m, encompassing a total of 1,573,768 pixels, with 115,238 pixels identified as landslide-affected areas. Based on 158 field observation points, the data were partitioned into a 70% training set and a 30% testing set. Comparative analysis between models with and without KSI data reveals that the integration of structural factors markedly improved performance across all algorithms. Specifically, the Accuracy (ACC) for RF, XGB, and CNN rose from 93.37%, 93.06%, and 94.45% to 95.62%, 95.59%, and 95.66%, respectively. Correspondingly, AUC values improved from 98.39%, 96.39%, and 93.84% to 99.74%, 98.74%, and 96.50%. Despite the exceptionally high AUC of the RF model and the narrow margin in ACC scores, spatial analysis of the resulting Landslide Susceptibility Maps (LSM) indicated that both RF and XGB models suffered from pronounced overfitting, characterized by fragmented «salt-and-pepper» patterns. The AUC shows that CNN demonstrated a refined capacity to integrate the newly introduced structural factors by capturing intricate spatial patterns more effectively than RF or XGB (Fang et al., 2020, Cui et al., 2025). Given that landslide occurrences are physically governed by the continuous interplay of topography, geology, and hydrology, they exhibit significant spatial continuity. Consequently,

the CNN model offers superior value for practical engineering applications. By incorporating structural data, this research accounts for the microscopic determinants of slope stability and failure locations, facilitating a cross-scale analysis from micro-structural controls to macro-susceptibility patterns. The findings provide a more precise and reliable LSM for the study area, offering a scientific foundation for future infrastructure implementation.

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Impact of the OAE2 on the fauna and paleoenvironments around the Cenomanian–Turonian boundary in the Wadi Araba, Eastern Desert, Egypt

ABDALLAH M. ZIDAN^{1,2}, JÓZSEF PÁLFY² & OTTILIA SZIVES³

1 – Department of Geology, Faculty of Science, Aswan University; Aswan, Egypt; abdullah4016@aswu.edu.eg

2 – Department of Geology, Institute of Geography and Earth Sciences, Eötvös Loránd University (ELTE); Budapest, Hungary

3 – Geological Survey, Supervisory Authority for Regulatory Affairs; Budapest, Hungary

This study investigates the paleoenvironmental and paleoecological changes associated with the Cenomanian–Turonian (C–T) boundary and Oceanic Anoxic Event 2 (OAE2) in the Eastern Desert of Egypt, focusing on the integration of stratigraphic, paleontological, and geochemical records to reconstruct environmental transitions across this globally significant interval. A total of 183 rock samples were collected from three well-exposed stratigraphic successions (East Wadi Um Khayshar, Wadi Abu Had, and Wadi Um Omeiyid) representing shallow to deep-lagoonal, subtidal, and shallow-marine facies. These samples were powdered for comprehensive geochemical and isotopic analyses aimed at refining the placement of the C–T boundary and characterizing redox fluctuations associated with OAE2. In addition, more than 1200 macrofaunal specimens, including cephalopods, bivalves, gastropods, echinoids, and sponges, were recovered, photographed, and taxonomically evaluated to document faunal turnover, biodiversity patterns, and ecological stresses during the transition. The successions preserve diagnostic ammonite zonal marker species that precisely delineate the C–T boundary and constrain the age of distinctive black shale beds that reflect intensified anoxia during OAE2. Planned analytical work includes preparation of smear slides to evaluate calcareous nannofossil assemblages, as well as carbon and oxygen isotope measurements to reconstruct paleoclimate variability and sea-level oscillations. Additional chemical analyses of sulfur, sulfates, trace metals (Ba, Mo, V, Ni, Cd), transition metals (Cu, Zn, Fe, Pb, Cr, Co), rare earth elements (Ce, Eu), and phosphorus will further clarify redox conditions and reveal geochemical fingerprints of environmental stress. By combining lithological, isotopic, and paleobiological datasets, this study aims to generate a high-resolution assessment of the environmental perturbations associated with OAE2, evaluate their impact on marine ecosystems across the C–T boundary, and contribute new insights into the evolution of the southwestern Tethyan Realm during the Late Cretaceous.

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